

The Correspondence between Spatial Organization in Fine Art and Tonal Organization in Music:

A Historical Overview.

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Introduction and Working Terms

Fine arts present the most obvious way of reflecting perceptual reality. The history of pictorial art demonstrates, quite clearly, the evolution of spatial representation in the depiction of observable objects. The “spatial” attributes of organization of pitch in music: its “vertical” (i.e., harmony) and “horizontal” (i.e., melody) parameters - are considerably less obvious to human senses, and the course of their evolution is substantially harder to grasp. By identifying the common cultural traits in tonal organization of music and spatial organization of pictorial art, we obtain a much clearer and thorough view on those aspects of perceptual reality that have been abstracted and represented in tonal schemata of music. The common example of such abstraction is a nearly ubiquitous practice of conceptualizing changes in pitch as changes in height, changes in rhythmic values as changes in width and changes in the number of simultaneously active parts/voices in a music texture as changes in depth within the imaginary space where music is perceived to unveil itself.

Understanding of how characteristic features of one’s living environment can be reflected in tonal organization of music can provide an insight into how the use of music according to such tonal principles could transmit and reinforce a particular culture of thinking. The latter is likely to underlie many domains of human activity, including fine arts and music.

In effect, producing and consuming a certain type of music might make one see the world in a certain way and, as such, depict it in drawings and paintings, accordingly. Cultural ubiquity of music, biological roots of musicality, its unprecedented capacity to entrain great number of individuals in sharing the same emotional experience – all can contribute to the “making” of one’s mind and attuning it to a mental model that is optimal for a given geographic environment and social engagement. Synesthetic equivalence of melodic and visual contours could provide the ground for “seeing” in terms of “hearing” – administered through *a set of instructions that stay embedded in structures of tonal organization* of one’s favorite music.

This paper seeks to establish the common ground between the schemes of structural arrangement of elements in 2-dimensional pictorial representation of 3-dimensional visual reality in fine art, on the one hand, and that of elements of musical composition in the temporal art of music, on the other hand. In essence, my idea is to track the analogies between the culturally preferred methods of organizing the encoding and decoding of data coming from the visual domain versus that of the auditory domain – and to trace their global historic development from the Paleolithic art to the Baroque period of Western civilization. I believe that this broad outlook can capture generalities that otherwise would require laborious task of statistical analysis of large pools of works of music and visual art – hardly available any time soon, judging from the modern trends in funding the scientific research in humanities.

The existing histories of music and histories of fine art at least partially reflect valid statistical generalizations by encompassing the cultural phenomena that are regarded significant by the consensus of scholars specializing in a given culture and by contemporary artists who keep using artistic devices that originate from specific cultures. The scope of global outlook on the entirety of world's cultures throughout the history and prehistory of known human societies also presents a form of statistical generalization that is likely not to miss an important method of compositional arrangement discovered by humanity at some point somewhere throughout cultural evolution.

Therefore, this paper will start by examining the correspondences between the principles of spatial organization in a work of visual art and the principles of tonal organization in a music work – provided that both belong to the same culture. For the analysis of prehistoric forms of music (which lack any documental evidence – archaeomusicology is capable to provide only the most general information, deficient for reconstructing the music form), we shall review those forms of music that are still in use by societies that retain the lifestyles similar to those that existed in prehistoric cultures, according to the evidence from paleoenvironmental studies.

We shall begin by examining the principles of composition for realistic painting and for music, focusing on the historic period when their ties appear the strongest, while the available data is well-documented – the Italian Renaissance. Specifically, we are interested to find out the earliest historic point at which the formative role of pictorial and musical compositionality received public acknowledgement and how the compositional schemes of that time related to the previous conventions of compositional organization. Once the important traits of compositional organization are identified, we can keep them in mind and chronologically review the entire course of evolution of spatial organization of pictorial representation of perceptual reality in fine art and of tonal organization in music – doing so in parallel, proceeding from one landmark that made an imprint on the history of art to another.

We shall move in chronological order and supply each model of fine art with the analogical musical model. The analogy will be estimated according to 3 factors: 1) similarity of the organizational schemes, 2) belonging to the same culture (for historic artefacts) or to the similar socio-cultural formations (for prehistoric artefacts), and 3) the overall trajectory of cultural evolution in relation to arts and music. There will be 45 audio and 40 visual examples to demonstrate the principal milestones in the evolution of treatment of pitch in musical texture and spatial representation of depth in pictorial images. Based on the cross-comparison of these examples, we will try to infer the general tendencies in the evolution of human conceptualization of space in art and music. This will lay down the foundation for future research of cross-modal cognitive correspondences between tonal organization in music and other non-musical cultural phenomena throughout cultural evolution of humanity.

But before proceeding further, we have to establish what exactly constitutes music texture, since its notion has been used primarily by musicians and musicologists. Texture is a specific scheme of hierarchical arrangement (melodic “horizontal” as well as harmonic “vertical”) of all tones within a musical work in a way that is different from purely melodic, harmonic, and rhythmic organization. Elements and components of texture are determined by the number of parts (monophonic music does not possess texture), their functional relations (e.g., accompaniment or counterpoint), and the presence

of conventional structural components (e.g., so-called “Alberti bass”) in harmonic/melodic arrangement (Huron, 1989). Music genres in polyphonic and homophonic music tend to cultivate characteristic textures through their application (Nazaikinsky, 2013). Thus, the genre of march is characterized by the texture consisting of the energetic melody in the highest register and the accompaniment by massive homogenous chords. In contrast, the genre of barcarole is characterized by the lazy ongoing wave-like melodic figuration in the accompaniment to the song-like melody.

Each texture breaks into a number of “stream segments” at its surface level of perception (Cambouropoulos, 2010), forming discrete components – “textural cells,” used as bricks in constructing a texture by vertical and horizontal grouping of various complexity, functionality and hierarchic relations (Nazaikinsky, 1972). Such “textural cells” are ascribed specific semantic values by means of public conventions (Kholopova, 1979). For instance, strictly chordal accompaniment is associated with the expression of determination, obsession, or strength - in contrast to the Alberti bass. The typology of textures varies along 3 axes: density (aka number of parts and/or voices), frequency range (Benward & Saker, 2009), and functions of parts (Berry, 1987).

Different textures are distinguished primarily by different arrangement of the thematic material. Musical theme can be defined as a musical idea that is fixed in musical structures, characterized by considerable completeness, salience, and originality – allowing one to recognize these structures upon hearing them again – and often used continuously or reused within the same musical work (Mazel, 1979). The notion of “musical theme” is often incorrectly described as peculiar to the Western classical music. In reality, many non-Western music traditions recognize thematic organization. Thus, in Carnatic tradition, a musical composition is often segmented in 3 sections (*Pallavi*, *Anupallavi* and *Caranam*) based on the treatment of a musical theme (Agrawal, 2018).

Although thematic analysis evolved within Western classical music, it should be applied to any form of music (Val’kova, 1992). The concept of *thema* (Greek ‘proposition’) emerged in rhetoric theory, and therefore suits any application where the listener needs to remember a particular expression essential for a musical work (Drabkin, 2001e). Thematic repetition, variation, contrast, or recapitulation (i.e., the return of a theme after some other material), recognizable by some salient feature(s), usually of melody and harmony, but sometimes of rhythm or texture - constitute a universal trait of music (Val’kova, 1992).

In cases, where “theme” lacks clear structural completion (e.g., in many preludes) or cannot be reduced to melody (e.g., chord progressions of jazz “themes”), we can talk of “thematic material” - i.e., the complex of musical structures employed towards making a given musical work – disregarding their completeness and salience (Mazel, 1979).

The Common Ground between the Rules of Linear Perspective and Polyphonic Composition

The first issue that needs to be addressed is the historic connection between the earliest forms of strict implementation of linear perspective and the earliest forms of building music textures in strict polyphony as both of them were crystallizing during the Early Renaissance (15th century) in Italy. However, since at the earliest stages the rules of perspectival composition of artworks and of tonal composition of music works were unclear, we shall start by comparing the compositional principles of linear perspective and functional tonality in their classic implementations as they became widely adopted in the 18th century Western Europe. The table below (Table-1) highlights three principal rules of linear perspective and shows how they find a close match in three main principles of tonal organization of music according to the functional tonality theory by Rameau (1971).

Table 1. Correspondence of the rules of canonic linear perspective and the standards of the 18th century Western tonality.

	Rules of Linear Perspective	Rules of Vertical Harmony	Rules of Horizontal Harmony
Centrality Rules	Single point of observation: Ideally, a spectator is supposed to stand where the artist stood while drawing - at the equidistant point where all the rays that are reflected from the depicted object join together, marking the center of projection. Observation from other points is regarded as inferior and has to be avoided (Greene 1983).	Single part principality: composer, performer, and listener are all supposed to focus on one part (voice) at a time. Their choice is determined by the placement of a musical theme in a musical texture. A theme is a distinct progression of motifs expressing the same character and reused in a work as a discrete unit of expression (Mazel 1979, 150).	Single tonic: A particular pitch class should be recognized by composer, performer, and listener as the strongest in stability for the entire set of tones used within a music work - thereby setting a single point where all these tones can be perfectly resolved, providing complete release of tension and enabling an ultimate termination of the melodic motion.
Single Ratio Rules	Single Scale of Proportions: A certain unit of measurement must be consistently applied to the entirety of the image to arrange the intervals of space as they appear between the depicted objects in the order of their appearance along the vector drawn from the observation (vantage) point, representing their relative distance.	Logarithmic Intervallic Spacing: The parts (voices) at the top of the musical texture must be closer to each other in comparison to the parts (voices) at the bottom of that texture – ideally, staying close to the logarithmic proportion, to maintain registral similarity to the intervallic distances between the partials within a harmonic series (Huron 2001).	Equal Temperament: The set of all pitch classes used in a music has to consist of tones that are equally spaced from one another by the interval of the equally-tempered semitone, which is defined by division of an octave into 12 equal parts – so that the same piece of music would maintain its intervallic integrity precisely, if transposed to a different key.
Vectorization Rules	Single Horizon: All the lines directed towards the depth of a depicted content, away from the spectator, must converge and vanish at the rational horizon line, defined by imagining an infinite horizontal plane. This line marks the “vanishing point” directly opposite to the “vantage point” occupied by the spectator. Only a slight deviation from the direct angle is afforded here: the line that joins the vantage and the vanishing points represents the depth aspect of an image.	Harmonic Pulsation / Implied Chord: All the parts/voices are supposed to comprise vertical relations as they appear on strong metric time (downbeat), forming one of legitimate harmonies that obtain the anchor function in harmonic progressions – especially in faster tempo music (Dubovsky et al. 1965, 420). This periodic vertical harmonic “slicing” of musical texture on metrically important time follows a set of rules for detection of legitimate chords – estimated from the lowest tone upwards.	Recapitulation / Key Relation: All tones of the composition must comply with the interval set model of major or minor keys, and follow the tonal plan suitable for a given genre and a type of a music form, where the music has to start and end in the same key, thereby securing tonal integrity (Kholopov 1988, 237). In this scheme, the "native" tonic of a key opposes the "foreign" tonic of another key, marking the vector of tonal development, indicative of the overall intricacy of music form.

“Vertical harmony” is a traditional Western discipline of harmony that regulates the simultaneous combinations of tones. “Horizontal harmony” is an older discipline of “*melopoeia*” [art of composing good melodies] that occupied the central place in Hellenic theory of composition and in music systems that inherited its framework (e.g., Octoechos, maqam, dastgah as well as Western Guidonian hexachordal system of the Middle Ages), gradually losing its ground in Western instructional literature from the Renaissance on and becoming the subject of personal training. Master-composers kept teaching their pupils the art of finding harmonious successions of tones in an informal way, without dedicated textbooks.

The correspondences highlighted in Table-1 are not coincidental. Analogies between the organization of a musical composition and ornamental design in fine arts as well as in architecture have been noticed for a long time (Galeyev 2003). From physical angle, these analogies take place because sound that determines perception of music works and light that determines perception of works of fine arts both share the wave-like nature: they both are subjected to the same natural laws of reflection, dispersion, absorption, diffraction, and interference.

Auditory and optical information is encoded essentially in a very similar way, differing primarily in wavelength: a sound-wave is comparable in size to objects about the size of humans or larger, while optical wave is microscopic (Nazaikinsky 1972, 116). The commonality of the behavior of waves should explain the commonality of rules of composition of the virtual space that constitutes a medium of music and a medium of fine arts and architecture – which all are perceived as changes within the horizontal-vertical axes of coordinates even by laypeople (ibid., p.127).

This is not to say that the assignment of a temporal dimension to the x-axis constitutes a biologically driven universality across the auditory and the visual domain. Such assignment, albeit cross-cultural, found in many different countries, seems to be learned in early childhood. Thus, English musicians represent pitch/time as vertical/horizontal axes; Japanese musicians raised on Western music share the same representation, while Japanese musicians raised on Japanese traditional music revert pitch/time as horizontal/vertical axes; and Papua musicians are not receptive to the x/y coordinates at all, instead, they categorize melody in terms of hue and loudness (Athanasopoulos & Moran 2013).

Similar results were confirmed by the comparative study of pitch perception by urban Canadian, Indian and Inuit children, suggesting that Western lifestyle cross-culturally promotes mapping of changes in pitch to vertical height: non-trained Inuit children seem to hear the changes in frequency, but are not capable of mapping them incrementally to vertical axis, although they favor it as a visual analog to frequency (Walker 1987). Similar dependencies were reported regarding the x/y mapping in pictorial strategies by Australian Aboriginal school children in relation to their exposure to Western cultural influences (Cox 1998).

What seems to constitute a cross-modal universality in spatialization of auditory and visual stimuli is not the assignment of axes to specific parameters of perception but the very issue of reducing the totality of dimensions naturally observed in stimuli to just a few ones in cultural conventions of representation of auditory and visual stimuli. Thus, pictorial art universally, across all known cultures, reduces 3 dimensions of perceptible visual objects (height, width and depth) to 2 dimensions (height and width) of the flat plane used for depictions. Music universally reduces the perception of multi-dimensional soundstage (4 domains of frequency, time, intensity and timbre generate at least 11 aspects of musical expression: melody, harmony, musical texture, articulation, tempo, rhythm, meter, dynamics, register, instrumentation, music form) to just 2 dimensions (pitch level and duration) of music notation (Nikolsky 2017).

Reductive conversion seems to characterize all traditional forms of art, including the art of literature that represents 4 dimensions of observable reality (height, width, depth and duration) in just 2 dimensions (word-per-time) of scripted language (Uspensky 1995, 80). It is the information loss that occurs during such conversion that appears to be responsible for the uniformity of human spatialization of auditory and

visual data – humans observe the world around them and learn its properties, after which they reduce the totality of learned information to a such volume that can be conveniently recorded (documented) for future retrieval of information. This filtering of “important” information, sufficient for effective retrieval, is responsible for the uniformity of certain cognitive schemes for representation of data collected from different domains (visual, auditory, and possibly other).

Visual objects fill up the visual space, whereas musical tones - the musical texture – i.e., the totality of all simultaneously active parts and voices. Percepts of pitch relations and visual size are cross-modally interconnected (Bien et al. 2012). We become aware of the disposition of tones in virtual music space essentially by the same mechanisms that we use to locate visual objects. Melodic layer in musical texture serves as a perceptual equivalent of the visible surface – in both cases we have to deal with an entity that is positioned the closest to an observer, in the foreground of an auditory or a visual scene.

Therefore, the principle of orientation remains essentially the same for both domains: in music, we relate one sound object to another in terms of intervals (of pitch, melodic and harmonic, as well as time); in visual art, we relate one visual object to another in terms of intervals as well (of distances). For this reason, perception of both, music and visual art, relies on perception of contours – i.e., lines drawn to connect the observed points in the continuity of the auditory and visual stimuli.

Visual contour equates melodic contour in its capacity to present an outline of the observed object (Terhardt 1995). This uniformity of contour representation is not limited to music and visual arts. Experimental research seems to confirm the above-mentioned semiotic generalization by Boris Uspensky. In general, contour models are found to be applicable to cross-modal contexts, confirming cross-modal sensitivity to contour (Prince, Schmuckler, and Thompson 2009). The contour representation might be the biologically driven cognitive adaptation to the need to generate auditory and visual percepts probabilistically (guessing how to connect the observable “dots”) to “guide biologically successful behavior in response to inherently ambiguous stimuli” (Schwartz, Howe & Purves 2003).

The congruence of melodic and visual contours explains long-known tradition of describing melodic structures in terms of visual shapes in music treatises (Galeyev 2007) as well as the experimental evidence of the ability of listeners (even musically untrained) to visualize their perception of different aspects of expression (melody, rhythm, meter, articulation) during their audition of music (Weinstein & Gridley 2010). Similar congruence seems to unite the perception of relative depth of the depicted images and of the perceived music texture – as long as both are estimated by drawing an “outline” of thickness.

In essence, we construct an intervallic projection for estimation of visual depth and auditory thickness. We interrelate audible parts in music by estimating the vertical intervals between them in terms of these intervals’ harmonic, rhythmic simultaneity of tones, and contrast of audible parts in their melodic contour – tracking them by their vertical order (Palmer & Holleran 1994). The importance of the vertical ordering for dealing with multi-part musical composition is evident in the long-standing compositional practice of avoidance of part-crossing in voice-leading (Huron 1991). The practice of ordering and enumerating parts in multipart music by no means is peculiar to the Western classical tradition – rather, it is peculiar to polyphonic music in general and is found in many traditions of folk music, such as Georgian polyphony (Jordania 2006).

The emergence of part-ordering might be the consequence of the psychophysiological limitations of human hearing. There is evidence that pitch changes are best detected in the upper part of a multi-part musical texture – which seems to constitute a default algorithm of perception of texture, judging from the fact that the upper part receives better recognition even when its contains a thematically unimportant material, and the theme is placed in a lower part (Palmer & Holleran 1994). The ERP studies of perception of polyphonic music suggest that listeners form their judgement of which musical material constitutes which part on the pre-attentive basis, largely automatically, and even years of experience playing a low-range instrument (e.g., bass) does not reverse the stable trend of better pitch encoding in the highest part - both, amongst musicians as well as non-musicians (Trainor et al. 2014). The upper part

bias was discovered even amongst 7-month-old infants, which leads one to believe that the segregation of audio streams into parts is done automatically (Marie & Trainor 2013).

On the other hand, the visual perception of direct motion reveals a similar ordering bias. We receive more information about the motion of those objects that are closer to us (optical invariants of distant motion are not picked up by the observer - closer motion is processed faster and with greater accuracy (DeLucia 2008). Yet another similarity with auditory segmentation is the numerosity of the moving objects perceptible by a viewer/listener. Here we can compare the number of simultaneously moving visual objects to the number of simultaneously active musical parts, where each part constitutes what appears as a “melodic motion” – i.e., changes of pitch values within the same audio stream.

Observers can estimate trajectories of up to eight simultaneously moving objects (DeLucia & Novak 1997). This is quite on par with the typical number of polyphonic parts in the most popular forms of Italian Renaissance music, where the 5-part setting was normative for a sophisticated style, and the 3-part setting was considered a sign of simple folk style (Dubravskaya 1996, 56). These numbers closely match the findings of the experimental studies: majority of laypeople can trace no more than 3 parts in their audition of polyphonic music, whereas musicians – 4 parts (Stoter et al. 2013), which can be extended to 5 parts once the trained listeners engage a special listening strategy by not counting parts but rather estimating by how many more parts the texture is thicker than 2 (Huron 1989). This method of holistic guessing of the relative thickness of a music texture appears to be to the holistic estimation of the extent of crowdedness in a segment of visual space.

Furthermore, in our estimation of visual motion and auditory motion of musical tones in multiple musical parts, we tend to be most sensitive to those changes that occur in the most proximal objects of observation. For music, creators and listeners of multi-part compositions tend to favor the upper part in containing the greatest number and the fastest rate of rhythmic changes in contrast to slower lower parts (Broze and Huron 2012). For visual motion, 6-month-old infants were found to use the spatial information provided by the motion parallax to perceive the relative distance between visual objects (Condry & Yonas 2013).

Greater acuity of perception of the most proximal data makes a lot of sense from the evolutionary perspective and very well could characterize not only human perception. It is crucial for the animal’s survival to give preference to the closest stimuli to enable the early detection of a predator or to help hunting a prey that lives in packs (multiple hunting objects).

Our tendency to ascribe greater importance to visual and auditory objects that are advancing towards us could be a part of this evolutionary trait. And the “upper-part bias” could be explained by human tendency to ascribe greater urgency to sounds higher in pitch: “raising voice” implies calling for attention (Nazaikinsky 1972, 156). The sensation of “greater in pitch” might be interpreted as “more urgent,” and therefore equivalent to “closer in space.” Similar perceptual association is observed in the Doppler effect as opposed to the static stimuli: ascending pitch is congruent with growing in size for the moving objects, whereas descending pitch - with shrinking in size – in accordance with the visual illusion that approaching us objects grow in size (Eitan et al. 2014).

As we see from this brief overview of the available scientific research, there are reasons to believe that similarities between the organization of spatial composition in works of fine art and texture of music composition in music works, so pronounced in the Baroque art, are not based only on the cultural conventions shared by the Baroque artists and composers in Western Europe. These similarities are at least partially based on the biological mechanisms of processing visual and auditory information, which are common to all humans. Therefore, it would be reasonable to expect to find such similarities across multiple cultures, both, historically (diachronic distribution) and geographically (synchronic distribution). And this is exactly what we are going to do. We shall start by tracing the historic roots of the “classic” implementation of linear perspective and tonality in Western Baroque as tabulated in Tab.1 with the aim to identify the set of structural principles that have played an instrumental role in their

formation. Then, we shall be able to approach the earlier forms of perspectival organization of realistic visual art and of tonal organization of music works – including non-Western civilizations.

The Origins of the Western Tonality and its Hierarchic Organization

At the heart of the spatiality of Baroque music compositions lies the theory of Western tonality, the basics of which were laid down during the 17th century. The result of this development was the “theory of harmony reduced to its natural principles” formulated by Rameau in 1722 in his highly acclaimed “Treatise on Harmony”, earning him the membership in many world’s Academies of Science and the reputation of “the Isaac Newton of Music” (Lester 2008). Rameau’s treatise exemplified the model of functional tonality for generations to come.

The essence of Rameau’s model was the idea that the integrity of harmonic organization of musical tones in a music composition is subjected to the same principles that determine the subharmonic structure of a musical tone. Let us sum up Rameau’s major points. A fundamental frequency of a tone marks bass as a textural part that sets the relations between the tones of all other parts and voices. Just like the lowest and the loudest harmonics within a harmonic series enrich and strengthen a fundamental tone by means of their harmonic ratios, the immense diversity of possible vertical combinations of musical tones within a music work is governed by their intervallic relations, where the tonal unity of an entire work is determined by the prominence of a tonic triad.

Unlike his predecessors, Rameau reduces all variety of chords to a single structure of a triad. Similarly, he reduces all variety of possible chord progressions to the schemata of just 3 harmonic functions: tonic, dominant (both borrowed from the earlier music theories) and subdominant (coined by Rameau) as embodiments of, respectively, stability (understood as an impulse to terminate a music movement and to rest or relax), instability (an impulse to gain stability by “resolving” the dominant function into tonic) and what I would term “pseudo-stability” (an impulse to challenge the stability of a tonic in favor of some tonal “development”).

Such functionality is determined by the intervallic relations between the roots of the basic triads: the tonic function marks the I degree as the principal anchor, the most stable pitch class in a key; the dominant function marks the V degree (a perfect 5th above the tonic) as the principal alternative anchor that supports tonic in cadences; and the subdominant function marks the IV degree (a perfect 5th below the tonic) as the principal anchor that challenges the tonic (since the relation of subdominant to tonic is the same as the relation of tonic to dominant – hence, the use of subdominant after tonic as though weakens the stability of tonic). All chords that are possible in a given key necessarily carry one of these three basic functions, distinguished by the intensity of representing a function (e.g., a triad of the II degree generates a stronger subdominant than a triad of the IV degree).

The interaction of these functions generates a harmonic unity within a music movement by means of standardizing a musical key: all keys of similar modal inclination share the same structure (which makes any music easily transposable) and complex compositions can be generated by modulating from one key to another (which generates the tonal plan for a composition).

As we can see from this brief summary, Rameau’s theory is all about centrality in tonal organization and grouping of its components. All possible combinations of tones in a key support a single most stable pitch class, tonic, in a way analogous to how combinations of harmonics in a harmonic series support a single fundamental tone (what Rameau considered a “natural” law). At the same time, the compositional integrity here is determined by the vertical relations of tones in texture – to a much greater extent than their horizontal relations.

There are relatively few horizontal rules that specify harmonic progressions of vertical harmonies. The latter come to dictate the construction of music. In contrast to melody-based pre-Baroque compositional

practices that estimated vertical relations through the reference of one part to another in terms of harmonic (vertical) intervals, Rameau's method was based on inferring chords – essentially, tones were grouped into a single harmonic entity (triad) that retained its functional property across all possible modifications, such as inversions of chordal tones and transpositions of chords. Hence, instead of the clutter of multiple parts and the myriad of possible combinations of tones, Rameau's model was operated by just 3 basic triads subordinated to a single root tone of the tonic triad.

Such “heliocentric” model necessarily puts in place a hierarchic system of subordination between all constituents. Not only the degrees of a key are subordinated to its tonic like planets keep rotating in a certain order around a star. Each of the planets obtains its own “moons”: each of the degrees houses a triad, where the root tone imposes its power to anchor the other two tones like a planet attracts its satellites. The chromatic alterations of tones add yet another level of complexity by engaging the tones “in-between” the degrees of a diatonic key.

All in all, the chromatically extended model of a diatonic key presents 4 levels of hierarchy, where each of the levels is subordinated to all higher-order levels. I shall list the functional characteristics and the hierarchic relations for each of the pitch classes (in the order of increasing instability) of a classic tonality (that became a standard in textbooks on Western harmony since the 19th century):

1. **Tonic** (the 1st level of hierarchy) – the I degree of a diatonic-based heptatonic key – the most stable pitch class and the principal anchor for all other pitch classes and their alterations (the tonal “center” for the entire key);
2. **Mediant** (the 2nd level of hierarchy, part of “tonic function” in vertical harmony) – the III degree – subordinated to Tonic (can be melodically resolved III-I) – the second most stable pitch class that can terminate a melody just like Tonic and a middle-tone in a tonic triad; it forms its own triad (III-V-VII) which carries the dominant function (contributed by primarily by the unstable VII degree) and constitutes the least unstable dominant chord in a key;¹
3. **Dominant** (the 2nd level of hierarchy, part of “tonic function” in vertical harmony) – the V degree – subordinated to Tonic (can be melodically resolved V-I or V-III), yet carrying the tonic function when used in a tonic triad; it can form its own triad (V-VII-II), in which case the dominant triad becomes the principal unstable function that supports tonic function in cadences; tonic and dominant functions are sufficient to support a musical composition (e.g., Chopin's Berceuse op.57 is all based on nothing but these two functions); dominant triad is more unstable than mediant triad (since it contains only one pitch class that belongs to the tonic function – the V degree);
4. **Submediant** (the 3rd level of hierarchy, subordinated to “tonic function”) – the VI degree – subordinated to Tonic, Mediant, and Dominant (can be melodically resolved VI-I, VI-III, VI-V), carrying the subdominant function, either as a middle-tone in a subdominant triad or as a root of its own triad (VI-I-III), which is the least unstable of 3 triads of the subdominant group (the other two are subdominant triad and supertonic triad) since it contains 2 pitch classes of the tonic function (the I and III degrees);
5. **Subdominant** (the 3rd level of hierarchy, subordinated to “tonic function”) - the IV degree - subordinated to Tonic, Mediant, and Dominant (can be melodically resolved IV-I, IV-III, IV-V), the root of the subdominant triad (IV-VI-I) that is more unstable than the submediant triad (since it contains only one stable pitch class – the I degree) and therefore is capable of

¹ Relative stability of a chord in Western music theory is usually estimated by the stability ranking of the constituent tones of that chord within a musical key. For C Major, the order of increasing instability is as follows: C->E->G->A->F->D->B. The more unstable the constituent tones, the more unstable the chord. For instance, the triad F-A-C is more unstable than the triad A-C-E, because the pitch class F is more unstable than A in the key of C Major.

challenging the anchoring power of the tonic function by opening some sort of tonal development;

6. **Supertonic** (the 3rd level of hierarchy, subordinated to “tonic function”) – the II degree - subordinated to Tonic, Mediant, and Dominant (can be melodically resolved II-I, II-III, II-V) and forming the triad that is the most unstable of all triads of the subdominant functionality (II-IV-VI), because all of its constituent tones are unstable;
7. **Subtonic** in major and natural minor keys, and “**Leading Tone**” in harmonic and melodic minor (the 3rd level of hierarchy, subordinated to “tonic function”) – the VII degree - subordinated to Tonic, Mediant, and Dominant (can be melodically resolved VII-I, VII-III, VII-V) forming the triad that is the most unstable of all triads of the dominant functionality (VII-II-IV), because all of its constituent tones are unstable;
8. **Chromatic alterations** form the 4th level of hierarchy, subordinated to pitch classes and triads of the 3rd level of hierarchy: IIb-I, II#-III, IV#-V, VIb-V, V#-VI, VIIb-VI, IIIb-II, I#-II, VI#-VII for major keys and VII#-I, IIb-I, IVb-III, IV#-V, III#-IV, Vb-IV, I#-II, VI#-VII, Ib-VII for minor keys.

The experimental research on perception of tonal organization in music leaves no doubt in validity of this hierarchic model of music theorists once it received a psychoacoustic rendition in the so-called “pitch space model” (Lerdahl 1988). The latter received a solid confirmation in numerous experimental studies (Krumhansl, 1996; Bigand, Parncutt, & Lerdahl, 1996; Cuddy & Smith, 2000; Smith & Cuddy, 2003; Frankland & Cohen, 2004; Lerdahl & Krumhansl, 2007; Hutchison, Hubbard, Hubbard, Brigante, & Rypma, 2015). In addition, Carol Krumhansl (1990) and David Huron (2006) presented well-verified thorough theories that explain the psychoacoustics behind the Western musicological theory of tonality.

The next question is which aspects of it are cardinal for perception of spatial attributes in tonal organization and at which point of music history did these aspects emerge?

There were 3 cornerstones of Rameau’s revolution in music theory that all find correspondences in the theory of perspective as shown in Table-1:

1. the centricity of a single anchor point (tonic) -> i.e., the rule of a single viewpoint;
2. the idea of harmonic (vertical) unity, determined by the distribution of harmonic intervals within the chords that carry certain harmonic functions -> i.e., the rule of a single scale of proportions;
3. the tonal plan, formed by the chain of harmonic modulations throughout a music work and implemented through successions of chords -> i.e., the rule of a single vectorization method (directionality).

Historians of music trace these traits of harmonic organization back to the mid-17th century Western Europe but the earliest of them, the concept of a chord, became widespread about a century earlier (Dahlhaus 2014). The principal force behind the genesis of a new chordal method of composition was the rise of secular monodic song in vernacular languages, promoted by the Renaissance ideology of restoring the principles of Ancient composition. The idea of restoration affected all arts, including music, poetry, literature, fine arts, architecture and dance.

The pioneer of a new popular genre of “*arie*” - i.e., a song, improvised solo to the strumming accompaniment of chords on a lute or a similar string instrument - Vincenzo Galilei (the father of the famous astronomer), deliberately was trying to merge the harmonic models of popular Italian folk songs of his time with the Hellenic tradition of improvising lyric poetry while playing on a lyre or harp (Palisca 1960). Galilei believed that in doing so, he was restoring the venerated principles of Greek composition by adopting simple folk melodies as perceptual analogs to Greek *tonos* and *modo*.²

² Such musical reform was supposed to address the problem of growing unintelligibility of extremely complex forms of polyphonic music that have dominated the practice of Western composition throughout the 14-16th

Renaissance ideology, without a doubt, nourished both, theory of perspective and new, monodic, harmonic theory that led to the institution of the accompaniment practice of “general bass” (aka “figured bass”, “basso continuo”, or thoroughbass) in early Baroque music (Cohen 2008). “General bass” was a codified practice of improvising a progression of chords to a given bass line in ensemble music. The earliest use of this practice is documented in a 6-part motet of the late 16th century, attributed to Palestrina (Barbieri 1994).

One of the pronounced traits that characterize the Renaissance aesthetic is the idea of syncretic unity of arts and sciences, best exemplified in a figure of a “Renaissance man”. Often, a renowned Renaissance artist was equally famous as a musician – take, Leonardo da Vinci. He was equally committed to the exploration of perspective in visual composition and of self-accompanied monodic composition in music, and it was the latter that actually opened doors of rich patrons for him when he strove to launch his artistic career (Winternitz 1982). Moreover, Leonardo directly applied the principles of music composition to visual composition – thus, his legendary “Last Supper” was based on the “musical proportions” (Brachert 1971).

The use of “musical proportions” was by no means exceptional: the idea of crossing spatial and musical organization stemmed from the deep-rooted tradition of associating science (especially geometry and astronomy) with music – the tradition that went unbroken from Pythagoras to the 18th century (Cook 2011). The treatises of the very same authorities of Antiquity were used by “Renaissance men” to educate themselves both in spatial organization and tonal organization of music: e.g., Ptolemy was one of the primary sources for Renaissance theorists of perspective (Edgerton 1974) as well as for Renaissance composers (Galilei 2003).

The Renaissance theory of perspective rests solidly on the Ancient theories of proportionality (Wittkower 1953). And the use of “musical proportions” in fine arts and architecture became a stable tradition after Leon Battista Alberti endorsed Peter Abelard’s idea of applying ratios of musical consonances to geometric figures (Pintore 2004). In 1425, perspective painting had its international breakthrough, gaining attention of many European artists (Edgerton 2009, 5).

In Renaissance culture, the advance in music theory generally lagged behind the advance in perspectival theory of visual arts. The latter experienced the great boom as the advances in geometry and the fashion for artistic innovations in a highly competitive market for large scale paintings have spread the new realistic art from Italy all over Europe. Consequently, the development of perspectival theory went ahead of other theories that were in use by Renaissance artists and musicians. Filippo Brunelleschi conducted his famous experiments on the accuracy of geometric projections in cityscapes in Florence, 1415-1420 (Wittkower 1953). And Paolo Uccello and Masaccio were the first internationally acclaimed painters to implement Brunelleschi’s conclusions during 1415-1423. Alberti was first to write a treatise on perspective in 1435.

On the other hand, the combined use of tonicity, chordal typology and pre-planned chordal progressions in music composition became adopted by first composers no earlier than in the 1490s, in the form of a method of tonal organization, transitional from the earlier forms of modality to the newly fledged “tonality” – what Wienpahl termed “monality” (Wienpahl 1971). Its cultivation was directly related to the international popularization of an Italian folk genre of *frottola* (Prizer 1975). Many frottolas by the Renaissance composers, Tromboncino and Cara, in fact, might fool a modern listener by sounding very

centuries (music works routinely used 5-8 part counterpoint, sometimes reaching up to 60 parts, which made it nearly impossible to hear holy text in the lyrics). This downside really bothered the Catholic authorities: there were numerous initiatives to ban polyphonic techniques altogether, and a popular legend tells that one of the leading Renaissance composers, Giovanni Palestrina saved Western music by demonstrating to the Council of Trent (that was about to ban polyphony) how the polyphonic technique could be compacted to keep the lyrics intelligible. Baroque music followed Palestrina’s direction and rarely used more than 4-5 parts in polyphonic settings (Berger 2006).

much like a diatonic major key (e.g., Tromboncino's frottola "*Ostinato vo' seguire*", 1509). Comic and amorous simple frottolas were often arranged for a solo singer with the self-accompaniment on lute, based on the formulaic repetition of the same progression of chord, where the return of the opening harmony would come after the end of the formula. Such solo frottolas presented the scheme of tonal organization that came the closest to the visual perspective of all the forms of Renaissance music.

Otherwise, the rule of vectorization did not contribute much to the tonal organization of Renaissance music genres. Its strongest manifestation – recapitulation of the thematic material that opened a music work at the end of that work, in the same key/mode – was non-existent during the Renaissance. The closest to it came the above-mentioned genre of *arie* that often made use of refrains, following folk-song prototypes (Ashworth and O'Dette 2007). Although *frottolas* and *aries* did not use recapitulation per se, they did mark the presence of some kind of tonal planning for a music composition.

In the same manner, despite the fact that *frottolas* and arias were not originally conceived as "in major/minor key" by their composers, they should be taken as a proof of composers' awareness of harmonic integrity of chords and their repeated progressions. In fact, the increased tonal homogeneity of *frottolas* could very well have been the reason behind a spike of frottola's popularity that rivaled the explosion of public interest to the visual perspective. Publication and distribution of *frottolas* in the beginning of the 16th century was one of the fastest growing industries that supplied a newly developing market of amateur household performance (the unprecedented number of 177 *frottolas* were printed in 1504 alone, in Venice, by the newly formed Petrucci publishing house), and simplicity of their style was supposed to enable the purchaser to build his own repertory of songs (Boorman 2005, 281–290). In this capacity, *frottolas* clearly opposed other music publications, such as masses. Not surprisingly, the tonal organization of *frottolas* had to be more uniformed and coherent, convenient for comprehension by a layman – unlike the intricate polymodal organization of polyphonic masses which required exquisite scholarship from their purchaser.

Codification of "tonality" in music theory took much longer than codification of perspective. Rameau's earliest writings on tonality came in 1720s. The very term "tonic", crucial for distinction between modality and tonality as forms of tonal organization, was introduced in 1710 by Saint Lambert (Lester 1989, 100). The antithesis between "tonality" and "modality" took even longer to form: it gained recognition in France at the turn of the 18-19th centuries (Blum 1985). Equally delayed was the crystallization of the theory of tonal plan that formulated the necessity for recapitulation. The technique of recapitulation was laid out by Johann Albrechtsberger (Beethoven's teacher) at the very end of the 18th century. Albrechtsberger defined the system of relative keys and outlined their succession for principal music forms, specifying that the initial key should return at the end (Kholopov 1988, 237).

However, the idea of musical recapitulation was not invented by Albrechtsberger. It originated from the Classic rhetoric theory of composition: *anakephalaiōsis* was the section dedicated to recounting in brief what has been said in the narration – required as a discrete part of composition in situations where refutations and confirmations were numerous and strong (Kennedy 2003, 28). The revival of interest in studying rhetoric composition for arrangement of preaches during the late Middle Ages involved the use of recapitulation (Murphy 1981, 313). And the rhetoric composition of sermons must have influenced the arrangement of music that was used in the same liturgy with the purpose to support the words. From the 16th century, the growing popularity of *musica reservata* (music designed to bring a listener into a specific emotional state suggested by the genre or lyrics of music) played a key role in maintaining close ties between the organization of words and music – which included compositional schemes amongst other things (McCreless 2002).

Albrechtsberger's concept of "tonal plan" had its precursor in Baroque music – the notion of "cadential plan." Although Baroque tonal rules required a thematic material to pass through a circle of keys throughout the composition, eventually returning back to the original one, the underlying idea for this return was to diversify the tonal content within a music work (and not to resume the key). In fact, the

cadential return was intended for reasons polarly opposite to Albrechtsberger's recapitulation: the *diversity in cadences* was supposed to *offset* the principal key (Kholopov 1988, 237).

Despite this fundamental difference and the fact that the Classicistic concern for integrity of tonal organization throughout a composition did not exist for Baroque composers, the latter, nevertheless, did conceive the totality of tonal content for a composed work and, therefore, exercised the perspective-like rule of the unity of vectorization (directionality) of a composition. For Baroque composers, music "ran" its course through the designated landmarks of tonal organization quite similar to an observation vector "running" from the "vantage" point to the "vanishing point" at the horizon line of a painting based on linear perspective.

The Renaissance composers were coming close to grasping the compositional importance of "cadential plan". In fact, it became one of the factors contributing to the identification of a particular mode by the times of Palestrina (Mangani & Sabaino 2008). Of course, cadential planning was motivated by purely melodic concerns back then: harmonic progressions were out of scope for the 16th century musicians. Even the most prominent Renaissance theorists as if "wore blinders that prevented them from seeing more than two chords at a time" (Palisca 1956). It would be justified to state that "cadential plan" was a reality of modal organization in Renaissance music, albeit understood *only* in horizontal rather than vertical dimension of musical texture.

It seems that the 16th century was the turning point for the genesis of homogenous perception of musical texture, especially evident in evolution of lute music, where uniformity of timbre in a multi-part instrument allowed for cultivation of proto-homophonic textures of chordal type (Comberiati 1983). Lute and guitar accompaniment cultivated the explicit "triadic thinking"—music was processed in terms of an expressive melody supported by progressions of chords rather than by a set of intricate counterpoint rules that still dominated vocal and keyboard treatises on music composition (Christensen, 1992). Many 3- and 4-part frottolas exposed the explicit chordal textures in vocal parts, while placing the melody in the upper vocal part, such as the famous frottola "El Grillo" (1505) by Josquin – quite similar to the later homophonic standards of the 18th century.

Yet another aspect of similarity was the manner of drafting a composition. Renaissance artists were empirically figuring out optimal methods of perspectival rendition, following the steps of Brunelleschi, who kept sketching the same building in a variety of methods and selecting the method that delivered the closest reproduction of the original. Along the same vein, Renaissance composers sketched compositions on erasable tablets that quickly became a common object of trade for professional composers and arrangers (Owens 2000). The very act of disposing pitches in vertical and in horizontal became visualized, which affected the way musicians mentalized music. Thus, in his instructional treatise on composition, in 1537, Auctor Lampadius distinguished the written stage of composition from the mental stage, and Claudio Monteverdi described his compositional process as "warping" parts in his head before notating the music (Owens 1998, 64-74).

By 1523, Renaissance composers religiously followed the established technique of a simultaneous conception of all parts in a prescribed order (Dahlhaus, 2014, p. 94)—very much like Renaissance artists were religiously applying perspective. One of the leading music historians, Edward Lowinsky (1989) characterized this new compositional method as analogous to perspectival rendition by contemporaneous artists.

Summing up, we can see that Renaissance culture provided almost all the basic features required for projecting a "heliocentric" worldview onto the realms of spatial organization in pictorial arts and tonal organization in music. The 18th century developments only capitalized on the tendencies already present in the Renaissance culture. The other aspects of perspective-like unity, present in Baroque composition, also find their roots in the Renaissance. Thus, the formulation of well temperament by Andreas Werckmeister theorizes the practical device of applying a single ratio of a chromatic semitone to the pre-compositionally selected keys for a music cycle – the device well known during the Renaissance. Thus,

in 1567, Giacomo Gorzanis wrote a collection of 24 dance suites for lute, using each of the 12 steps of the chromatic scale (Pirina 1985). The theoretic foundation for a tuning system to enable performance of such music was provided in 1584 by Vincenzo Galilei (Barbour 2004, 8).

The recognition of “tonicity” as an attribute of a chord rather than a tone also took place during the Renaissance. Especially in short musical compositions, a relatively strong sense of tonicity could be evoked by means of repeating the Dorian cadence (Lowinsky 1962, 4). Short miniatures made a substantial portion of the lute repertoire, in particular the dance genres (e.g., *passamezzo*). Popularization of this kind of music paved the way for Johannes Lippius in 1612 to declare that it was the tonic triad rather than the modal species that formed the basis for the modes (Berger 2006).

Certainly, we are looking back in history, having in mind concepts that the Renaissance musicians could not and did not have. Nevertheless, objectively speaking, marking of a single triad as the stability anchor for an entire piece was part of the experience of listening to at least certain types of music of the late 16th century. The standard chaining of a *passamezzo antico* in a minor mode by a *passamezzo moderno* in a major mode on the same “tonic” tone, without any stopping, was quite common in the dance guitar/lute practice of the mid-16th century (Hudson 1970).

But what about the pre-Renaissance culture? The Renaissance theorists claimed to have made the Ancient Greco-Roman Sources “born again.” Would the correspondence between perspective and early forms of tonality find its counterpart in arts and music of the Antiquity?

Composition in Art Works of Ancient Greece vs. the Renaissance

First of all, we should stress a principal difference between the Renaissance and Hellenic perspectives. Ancients' concept of space was "sensuous," and therefore aggregate and *finite* – Ancients were interested in visible objects rather than space that separated them (Panofsky 1991, 41). Aleksey Losev (Losev 2000, 3:177) defined the ancient perspective as "harmonious combination of depicted bodily objects, which did not take into account space that separated bodies in conceptualizing the unity of an entire image". This “naive”, according to Losev, realism considered only those bodies that were touching one another, while ignoring the space enclosed in-between. Losev characterized the 'depth' parameter in Hellenic and Roman pictorial images in the following way: "the presence of intervals in space can be perceived, but these intervals cannot be expressed by a single and general coefficient" (ibid.). Obviously, such perspective was not strictly linear. The overall proportions looked correct only when the depicted bodies were disposed of, one by one, going into the supposed 'depth', by filling up the space between the vantage point and the horizon. But as soon as there was a sizeable gap between the bodies, the size of these bodies was not adjusted according to the distance that was supposed to separate them.

In contrast, Renaissance artists applied perspective to the *infinite* space, carefully constructing distances between the pictorial objects. The same applies to music: Renaissance composers kept lower parts spaced wider apart than the upper parts in multi-part textures and conceptualized a semitone as a standard unit of measuring the intervals between musical tones, both in harmonic and melodic settings. They also observed the cadential plan for a music work and were aware of the changes of chords at least in some genres (e.g., frottola). Hellenic musicians did not account for anything equivalent to the disposition of parts and anything even remotely resembling “tonal plan” that would have regulated the succession of specific keys or cadences in a particular composition.

Hellenic theorists did attempt to define a semitone as a uniform measuring unit for the intervallic relations in pitch (Crickmore 2009). However, these attempts were complicated by the discrepancies in measuring the chromatic and enharmonic alterations (Hagel 2009). Ancient Greek musicians were certainly sensitive to changes in a pitch set (aka, “modulation”) and in an interval set (aka, chromatic or enharmonic “alteration”), but did not care to track one change to another for the entirety of a musical

composition. They did not appreciate “arching” of the opening of a musical piece with its ending by means of ensuring that the anchor tone would remain the same. Their compositional practice seems to have been designed for changing one mode with another, while taking into consideration no more than two modes at a time (West 1992, 195).

The Hellenic non-linear perspective corresponded to *non-linear tonal plan*. Just like Hellenic artists ordered only the depicted bodies, ignoring empty space between them, Hellenic musicians paid attention only to the "departure" tetrachord and to the "arrival" tetrachord, ignoring which exact pitch classes were used in the transition and how one transition related to another transition within the same music work. The ability to track pitch changes over a longer span of time appears to be a product of enculturation and optimization of hierarchic processing of frequency (both, in bottom-up and top-down directions), characteristic of our perception of tonality (Kumar et al. 2011).

Regarding the spacing of parts in musical textures, Ancient Greek music theory was simply not equipped with any means to organize the disposition of parts. Many experts do not believe that Ancient Greeks used multi-part music at all. All arguments for the existence of such music were collected and listed by Andrew Barker (Barker 1995), but even his attempt to squeeze the most evidence leaves no doubt that ancient music theorists did not consider multi-part arrangement important for music practice of their day and left no mentioning of the organization of music texture. It is possible that Ancient Greeks knew harmonic (vertical) intervals and used heterophonic textures (we are going to review the evidence for this later). But the prevailing method for conceptualizing music was definitely monodic back then – i.e., based on tonal organization of a *single* melodic line that carried all the expression to be concerned about.

So, all in all, we can find solid correspondences between Hellenic perspective and Hellenic music composition only in respect to the centrality principle and just partially in relation to the tendency to somehow standardize the comparison of intervallic differences between various entities (tones, pitch classes, tetrachords, etc.). Different theorists diverged in their methodology of measuring microchromatic shades (Hagel 2009), creating the general impression that ancient music theorists diverted a lot from the music practice of their time in attempt to figure out the most rational and clear way to classify things that they observed in practice (Wulstan 1971).

What we can safely conclude from our comparison of the compositional theory of the Renaissance and the Classic Antiquity is that similarities between the tonal organization in music and spatial organization in fine arts are limited to methods of implementation of the centrality principle and intervallic scaling. The principle of the uniformity of vectorization (directionality) seem to constitute the post-Hellenic developments. Let us sum up the compositional features of interest in a retrograde order by moving from the 18th century (Table-1) back in time through the basic periods that are most commonly featured in textbooks on art history (Table-2 below).

Table-2. The outline of similar traits of spatial and tonal organizations in 6 periods of history and prehistory of art.

Period	Features of Spatial Organization	Features of Tonal Organization
Age of Enlightenment (17 th -18 th century)	Artists of the Age of Enlightenment conceptualized perspective into “perspectival space” -i.e., the ideation of a particular place, pre-conceived by the artist who then populated that space with objects that best complimented that space (Elkins 1996, 14). The overall composition was usually compact, clear, and balanced.	The 17 th -18 th century composers began to typecast music texture - i.e., they reserved specific textures for specific genres: chorale, minuet, march, etc., (Kholopova 1979) and filled up these standard textures with idiosyncratic melodic and harmonic material. Textures were usually relatively compact (polyphonic or homophonic), in design.

	<p>Yet another development in perspectival organization, starting from Baroque on, was the engagement of shading effects and tonal gradations that eventually became more important than proportions in defining the depth aspect of a work (Bouleau 2014, 112).</p>	<p>Compositions explored chromatic shading, often opposing diatonic and chromatic harmony in the manner of light/dark, promoting frequent modulations and applied functions. Harmonic functionality started taking lead in determining music form.</p>
<p>Renaissance and Early Baroque (15th-17th century)</p>	<p>The rule of a single viewpoint was exempted wherever a great scope required greater space and multiple gazes. In such cases, 2-3 vanishing points and/or horizon lines were employed. The rule of a single scale was observed unless the composition required the emphasis on a particular aspect of a figure or a room, in which case the application of two scales was permitted as an exception. Late 16th-17th century compositions were frequently monumental, featuring the enormous variety of objects that often contrasted one another, characterized by great elaboration in detail (e.g., frescoes by Veronese and Titian). “Close view” genres (portrait and still life) became popular – offsetting the monumental art.</p>	<p>The rules of thematic composition (according to the theory of rhetoric, voice-leading, and non-chordal tones) were codified in treatises and observed rather strictly. The rules of alteration, modulation, and cadential plan were more flexible, reserving exceptions whenever strong contrast or expression of abnormal tension were needed. Renaissance texture was usually heavily polyphonic, up to 60 parts (e.g., in compositions by Tallis and Striggio) – except virtuosic instrumental pieces and a transparent <i>stile moderno</i> that conveyed intimate feelings. Baroque polyphony reduced the average number of parts, but complicated and elaborated the melodic and harmonic structures.</p>
<p>Hellenic, Hellenistic, and Medieval Near Eastern Art (5th century BC – 15th century AD)</p>	<p>Pre-Renaissance perspective accounted only for proportionality of objects, ordering them in the depth parameter without specifying any vantage and vanishing points (Richter 1970). Artists intuitively observed “aerial” perspective, not single-point, but flexible “multiscan,” affording oblique viewing (Arnheim 1977) – which generally corresponded to what Panofsky termed “curvilinear” perspective (Panofsky 1991, 22), although, strictly speaking, from an optical standpoint, this perspective was not “curved” (Kubovy 1988, 107). Ancient perspective, formulated by Euclid, followed the principle of <i>angular</i> distance, based on the “common sense” understanding of distance between the observer and objects positioned at different angles – in contrast to the “<i>level</i> distance,” based on straight optic appearance of distant objects, discovered during Renaissance (Veltman 1980).</p>	<p>Music-makers considered only the modal aspect (pitch set and modal rules) and the tonal aspect (stability) in tonal organization of a currently sounding structural unit and its immediate precursor – but not in the scope of the entire work. Mode could sustain throughout a composition, or modulate for a few times. The texture must have been heterophonic, featuring intricate non-formulaic melody and possible variants in accompanying parts, instrumental or vocal, with a probable drone tone and inclusion of instrumental variations and/or interludes. Heterophonic voices might be thought of as equivalents to discrepant angle views, where the viewpoint shifts vertically or laterally – such shifts introduce curvature-like distortions (Veltman 1980), producing melodic variants similar to optic variants. In both cases, the perceptual whole must be assembled from summing up the variants.</p>
<p>Egyptian, Sumerian, Babylonian and Assyrian Art</p>	<p>Near East “paratactic” or “ideoplastic” organization (Groenewegen-Frankfort 1951, 7) followed lines of what can be termed as “abstract rationalism” (Hauser 1999a, 1:23), based on axonometric principles of orthogonal projections. “All objects were depicted in direct frontal view,” while</p>	<p>Music-makers did not observe the uniformity of intervallic increment in defining the scales: Babylonian music system employed three types of different-sized semitones, whereas Classical Greeks had only one (Crickmore 2009). Absence of reliable transcriptions does not allow to discuss the</p>

<p>(30th-7th century BC)</p>	<p>shifting the point of observation from one detail to another in order to “keep the viewing angle strictly perpendicular” (thereby producing a sum of orthogonal shots along the observation path), and “reducing all horizontal surfaces to a basic straight line” (Rauschenbach 1980, 32). The depth parameter was indicated by the overlap of a “closer” object. The object’s size was independent of the depth parameter – marking the distant view by addition of indexical signs to the images depicted from the bird’s-eye view projection (Rauschenbach 2002, 188).</p>	<p>details in tonal organization of music compositions. However, the texture of Mesopotamian music was most likely strict monody, because of close supervision by priests and palace administrators (Ziegler 2011), with clear standards of performance rationally defined by notation-based professional training (Michalowski 2010), and great religious importance placed on “correctness” in tonal organization – determined by its adherence to mathematical models. All music was reduced to a single melodic line, perceived by summing up familiar melodic intonations.</p>
<p>Neolithic Art (ca. 8,000-3,200 BC)</p>	<p>Prehistoric Egyptian art contrasted the canonic depiction of the first dynasties: the perpendicular viewing angle was not observed, leaving the continuity of the figures’ contours the main means of spatial organization (Davis 1992, 5). Such mechanistic approach to integration reincarnated the naturalistic method of using pictorial contours to replicate visual contours after a long period of “narrowly geometric stylization” (Hauser 1999a, 1:5), brought by the Neolithic transition from food-gathering and hunting to cattle-breeding and planting. Increased demand for accounting promoted the “diagrammatic” abstractization of the earlier Paleolithic naturalistic depiction method. The later recovery of realistic principles probably had to do with the emerging tradition of scripting in pre-literal cultures – delegated to ideographic signs, which separated the realistic pictographs from abstract symbols reserved for household accounting or calendar tracking (Huyghe 1966, 38). “Diagrammatic” artists considered only figures adjacent in horizontal and/or vertical dimensions in spatial organization of their pictorial works. Depicted figures remote from each other were not coordinated.</p>	<p>Hypothetical prehistoric music must have followed the course of development from ekmelic to emmelic organization (Nikolsky 2015a) – through the process of abstraction of pitch parameter from the entire spectral content. The task of distinguishing pitch modulation from timbral modulation resembles the distinction between the ideographic sign and the graphic image. Timbral music is much more naturalistic (“graphic”) in imitating environmental sounds (Nikolsky et al. 2020). Discretization of pitch presents a strongly cultural (“ideographic”) approach to sound production, based on the consensus between all music users. The establishment of rules for such production requires extensive cultivation of monophony, with focus on consecutive connections between different pitches – akin to figurative continuity in spatial organization. The polyphonic implementations of emmelic music were also likely to be inherently “consecutive”: each singer had to hear his partner in order to come up with his own part (Arom 2004, 220). Such performance is tonally “short-sighted”: i.e. Buganda players only consider 2-3 neighboring steps in joined music-making (Kubik 2010, 116).</p>
<p>Paleolithic Art (ca. 40,000-10,000 BC)</p>	<p>Amazing realism of drawing the animal outlines (as challenging as the task of capturing animals in motion) characterizes murals of the entire Paleolithic period across a wide geographic area in Europe – until the late Magdalenian period, when stylized figurative style started appearing side by side with a realistic style (Huyghe 1966, 34). However, even in stylizations, realistic connotations usually stayed strong,</p>	<p>The naturalism in representation of visual reality corresponds to what Sheikin (2002, 30) called “echolaliac instincts” that brought to life at first the psychophysiological, and then the organophonic intonations of (respectively) the pre-modal and khasmatonal methods of tonal organization (Nikolsky 2015a). Surviving indigenous ethnic traditions that implement these methods usually employ what can be termed “<i>jumbled</i>”</p>

	<p>implemented to exaggerate a known important trait of the depicted object (Eastham 2005). Spatial disconnectivity in representation of real life objects appears to be a general marker of the Paleolithic art (Okladnikov 1967, 117): no two figures comprise an ensemble – although the depicted objects might altogether represent a single scene. Depictions were often made over older depictions, as though each of them was immanent and undisturbed by overlapping (Uspensky 1995, 178).</p>	<p><i>texture</i>” that I call “isophony” (Nikolsky 2018): i.e., collective music-making of the same signal without any coordination of parts – mere intuitive following of the same model by every participant with accidental discrepancies in pitch, rhythm, and timbre. No part is consciously tuned to any other part, yet all parts adhere to the same model, defined by the same goal of musical performance (and mutual lyrics). No clashing in pitch or rhythm is perceived as disrupting this model.</p>
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Table-2 reveals that the spatial/tonal correspondences in compositional arrangement are the most pronounced in the 17-18th century, become weaker in the 15-17th century Western culture, even more limited in the Hellenic/Hellenistic/Islamic Mediterranean art, and retain only general traits of similarity for the earlier periods of art history/prehistory. With this in mind, we can proceed now to the closer examination of the earliest methods of spatial organization in pictorial reproduction of natural models in Paleolithic rock art – in attempt to identify those traits that are also present in tonal organization of music that characterizes the lifestyle of surviving hunter/gatherer societies that live in environmental conditions similar to that of creators of the Paleolithic art.

The Origins of Compositional Arrangement

If one tries to draw parallels between the beginnings of pictorial art and pre-mode in prehistoric music (Nikolsky 2015a), the mutual feature will definitely be the notion of *contour*. The ability to carve or depict a geometrically shaped line most likely corresponded to the ability to track a melodic contour. The earliest known depictive images are the Quneitra artifact from the Levant, 55,000 BP, and the Bacho Kiro bone from Bulgaria, ca. 44,000 BP (Marshack 1996).

Image 1. A bone fragment with zigzag incision, Bacho Kiro, Bulgaria, 44,000 BP. The two rows of zigzag lines indicate the carver’s awareness of changing directions, of points marked in this way, and similarity of certain lines.

The closest musical analog to this would be vocalization of a few people following the same pitch contour with observable cross-relation between the rhythmic, timbral, and directional attributes of the contour envelop, so that the mutual resemblance could be recognized by ear.

1. **Audio:** Drinking chant, Campa Indians, Upper Amazon. Female choir keeps vocalizing the same “call” made by the intonation of the descending 3rd – in celebration of the making of manioc beer (Tschopik 1954). [\[See Supplementary Audio File 1\]](#)

There is no term in music theory to refer to this method of generating a clearly multipart texture. The most appropriate term would then be *isophony* (Nikolsky 2018) – production of parts approximately equal in melodic, rhythmic, and timbral characteristics, where no particular part is salient, and the texture appears interwoven by juxtaposition of the same brief melodic contour model.

The most probable source for the emergence of isophony is sociobiological: those animals that live in groups, depend on mutual cooperation and mutual control of a territory, and therefore, are prone to demonstrate from time to time the unanimity in their psycho-physiological state in certain situations. For example, a pack of wolves howls, reproducing the same pitch contour as set by their pack leader, to consolidate a pack after sunset for nocturnal hunting, to reveal the location of pack members and to warn stranger-wolves of their territorial claim (Lopez and Baugess 1979).

2. Audio: Wolf pack howling. [See Supplementary Audio File 2]

It is reasonable to expect that the first hominid tribes were utilizing vocal signals in a similar way while hunting or gathering. Because of higher intelligence, the contribution of a single human to the outcome of a collective activity is much higher than for any other animal, and therefore, there is a greater need for every human to “register” his presence and readiness for some mutual action, be it hunting, gathering or some important ritual rite. Then the timbre and other idiosyncratic features in isophonic reproduction of the same signal would serve as identifiers for a particular member of a social group.

Yet another possible way for the emergence of isophony is collective cultivation of instrumental music where each participant produces only one pitch at a time. Below is the example of such music:

3. Audio: Horn ensemble, Banda Linda, Central African Republic. The ensemble of sixteen *ongo* horns, each tuned to a particular pitch, perform the music, arranged from highest to lowest sound, in succession. [[See Supplementary Audio File 3](#)]

Each of the participants produces only one tone fixed in a particular pitch value throughout the session of music, arranged in a succession according to a social convention.³ Such manner of sound production is likely to have been available to hominids at the very early stages of cultural evolution. Whistles constitute one of the oldest types of musical instruments discovered by archaeologists, whose simplistic construction must have preceded multi-pitch pipes (Morley 2013).

Ethnomusicological accounts of possible chronology in the evolution of prehistoric forms of music, based on similarity of a lifestyle, also hold that the simpler organological morphology of a whistle makes it a most likely predecessor of a wind instrument (Sheikin 2017). Then, members of a Paleolithic tribe could have had his/her personal whistle and use it to represent themselves in a collective session of musicking that had an important ritual meaning for the entire tribe. Personalized use of pitches is quite widespread amongst indigenous ethnicities of northeastern Eurasia (Nikolsky et al. 2020) and was reported in societies whose traditional music bears isophonic traits, such as Audio Examples Nos.4-5 below (see Seeger 2004 for the description).

The practice of instrumental fixation of pitch values, demonstrated in Example No.2, might have followed a spontaneous discovery of the isophonic texture in collective reproduction of the same signal by a group of hominids (in a wolf howling style). In this scenario, the sound of a whistle or some other single-pitch musical instrument - e.g., a pebble used as a portable rock-gong (Blake 2011) – came to substitute a personalized vocal signal.

Isophonic music cannot be strictly qualified as “polyphonic,” since polyphony usually implies continuity and certain level of accomplishment of a part: a part is supposed to make sense on its own. Isophony, on the other hand, is characterized by fragmentary sound of music distributed to each of the participants,

³ Such music raises the question of how short a melodic phrase of each of the performers can be in order to produce segregation into parts? Limiting a phrase to a single tone produces not melodic lines but “melodic points” in a peculiar pointillistic texture.

where taken separately, a part does not make any sense without the other parts. This criterion is indispensable for correct identification of polyphony (Jordania 2006, 103).

An isophonic texture can be elaborated by applying variations in pitch, rhythm, timbre, and length of each of the renditions of a model, assigning a particular variant to a particular member of the tribe. Then, such a variant can serve as a “personal song” (Nikolsky et al. 2020) for this individual to be identified in the entire uncoordinated “choir” of a tribe. The whole texture of such collective vocalization would emerge stochastically, by chance, without a deliberate planning – even though each of the participants might deliberately control the tonal organization in his/her personal call or song (similar to how orchestral musicians collectively warm up before the recital starts – each of them deliberately chooses what to play and listens to himself/herself, however the entire sound of the orchestra in this case remains uncoordinated, “aleatoric”).

4. **Audio:** Akia tribe singing, Suyá Amazon Indians. A collective shout song that represents individual members of the tribe, based on their age and importance in the tribe. The lower the status, the shorter the musical phrase. The syllables “te-te-te” are used to integrate the singing between all the participants (Seeger 2004, 40). A single melodic formula integrates all the parts. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 4\]](#)

Isophonic texture can be characterized as *jumbled texture*, because it involves an ongoing rotation of the same set of closely related melodic elements, where they unpredictably realign with one another in time. The landmark of such tonal organization is integration of a strictly defined array of disjointed elements by means of sharing the same or very similar musical material. The visual equivalent to this would be the juxtaposition of similar images, where each image retains its autonomy by comprising a “frame” by its contours: the contour line separates such image from the “outside.”

Image 2. *Spotted horses*, Grotte de Peche Merle, France, ca. 25,000 BP. The contour of one horse is painted over that of another, leaving it “see-through.” Both images remain disjointed, each existing in its own right. There are more examples like this in the same cave.

Image 3. Right wall of the *Sanctuary* at the Trois-Frères Cave, ca. 13,000 BC. Juxtaposition of many images, as found in quite a number of caves, creates an impression very much similar to “jumbled texture” in music.

Primordial Paleolithic isophony most likely presented a repertoire of tonally disjointed melodic contours joined by gliding indefinite pitch, resembling the chorus of a pack of wolves howling. Primordial vocalizations were initially stochastic in pitch values. Collective activities, such as hunting or flinting stone tools, performed alongside isophonic vocalizations were likely to homogenize the *rhythmic* organization via the entrainment mechanism (Becker 2012), and enable participants to align their “parts” vertically, in time. Rhythmic entrainment is known to induce a musical affect (Troost et al. 2017), thereby turning a specific contour into a semiotic sign, physically distinguished by the contour shape and semantically distinguished by the associated affect.

Consistent collective use of rhythmically synchronized contours must have turned on the averaging mechanisms – both, motorically, while singing, and mentally, while evaluating the contour produced by others. Negotiation of the average values between all the participants had power to set the conventional model of a contour suitable for a particular application for which vocalization was used.

Something similar we can observe in the repertory of cries of a prelingual human infant: different contours (that vary in their temporal, timbral and pitch properties) characterize different applications (calling for attention, complaining about hunger, etc.) so that caretakers can effectively interpret most of infant’s cries (Golub & Corwin, 1985). Such contour-based semantic specialization that sets a particular cry into a discrete sign is likely to constitute a universal ontogenetic phenomenon (Wermke et al., 2007). Therefore, it is reasonable to expect the same semiotic genesis to take place in phylogenetic domain and impact the cultural evolution.

Some ethnomusicologists believe that the earliest form of music was polyphonic and collective singing by a tribe somehow resolved the dissonant clashes between multiple participants due to their lack of coordination in frequency and in time, resulting in the institution of conventions of tuning specific harmonic intervals (Jordania 2006). Such a view appears to present an anachronistic attempt of retroactive reconstruction of the past based on what we know today. There was no way for Paleolithic

hominids to know harmonic intervals, their sound and expression, and to possess skills necessary for recognition and reproduction of specific harmonies.

The proof for this is that it takes at least 2-3 years for even the most precocious infants to develop the ability to distinguish one harmonic interval from another and an extra year to learn to produce them by voice. For majority of normal infants, this time frame doubles (Hargreaves & Lamond 2017). And this is the situation where infants have an opportunity to observe and imitate the tonal organization in music that sounds in their environment. Paleolithic infants were deprived of such opportunity, and therefore, their changes of figuring everything out on their own were close to nil. There are no babies that learn to cry in-tune and in sync by crying together with other babies. And since any cultural tradition requires cultural transmission from one generation to the next generation in order to survive, Paleolithic people would not have been able to establish the tradition of musicking to trigger the cross-cultural evolutionary development of music.

Jordania claims that collective musicking of Central African Pygmies presents the model of the primordial tonal organization in music. It is true that all music of adult pygmies is collective, multi-part and based on discrete intervals of anhemitonic pentatonic music system (Arom 2004). But this music presents an advanced form of tonal organization. Although pygmies are one of very few ethnicities that have retained the hunter/gatherer lifestyle, a very important issue that distinguishes them from Paleolithic population is their group size. The closest match to the scarcely populated area where the earliest musical instruments, capable of producing multiple pitches, have been retrieved (Morley 2013) – Southern and Central Europe – would be not Equatorial Africa but Northeastern Eurasia (Nikolsky et al. 2020). And the notorious absence of collective forms of musicking amongst the indigenous ethnicities that inhabit the Extreme North (ibid.) suggests that *collective musicking is not a requirement for the existence of music*.

In order for the knowledge of tonal organization to be passed between generations, music has to be transmitted from mother to her child – hence, there is a requirement of *solo singing*: a child has to be able to generate musical tones by voice (since acquisition of vocal coordination precedes motoric coordination necessary for playing a musical instrument), clearly hear the acoustic attributes of the resulting sound and estimate how close it is to the acoustic model set by the mother. Since there is no human model for the very first musical vocalization to occur, the model either has to come from some natural sources (e.g., a pitched sound of a stalactite generated by hitting it with something solid or of a hollow body like an aeolian harp sound generated by wind) or it has to evolve gradually from timbre-based signaling that seems to be much more common across the animal world than pitch-based signaling (Nikolsky 2020a).

In both cases, the genesis of the ability to control sounds in pitch and generate music-like tonal organization necessarily demands *personal* (and not collective) experimentation with (re)production of sounds. Only after a number of individuals gain the basic skills of fine-tuning a musical tone can they jointly make music together. And only once their skills are passed to the substantial number of people can a cultural convention be formed. Since discrimination of intervals of pitch and duration that are required for tonal organization to emerge rely on standards of cultural conventions, the very first music system has no other way to emerge but through extensive period of personal use.

And this is what a closer look at the musical tradition of Central African Pygmies tells. Indeed, adult pygmies engage only in collective multi-part music. But their young children and their mothers practice strictly monophonic vocal music, in the course of years, gradually introducing at first duets, then trios and thereafter more complex forms of multi-part singing (Rouget 2011). The same course of development constitutes the most likely scenario for the evolution of music: *strict monophony as a starting point* and gradual thickening and complication of a music texture thereafter.

5. **Audio:** Akia boy singing, Amazon. This rare example, kindly provided by Anthony Seeger, complements the audio example above, by demonstrating how the complex isophonic texture

heard in that example (No.4) was, in fact, constructed of the component songs at least some of which (like this one) were initially practiced solo. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 5\]](#)

Once again, I have to underline that the isophony of the primordial “pack-vocalizations” of the earliest hominids (possibly, *Homo erectus*, but more likely *Homo Heidelbergensis*), similar to wolves’ howling, simply could not contain tonal organization (Nikolsky 2018). Strictly speaking, it should not even be considered “music”, since the definition of music requires the presence of entrainment in temporal arrangement of the physical properties of sounds and the presence of emotional contagion in semantic content ascribed to these sounds (Nikolsky 2020). The most accurate approach would be to consider pure isophony “proto-music”.

However, the isophonic texture that becomes partially coordinated in pitch and/or rhythm through the personal use, as in our Audio Examples Nos.3-4, presents a transitional form of tonal organization between “proto-music” and “music”, and can be evaluated as a peculiar form of music – under a cap of *emmelic* (see a chapter below) isophony.

- 6. Audio:** Osuokhai, Vilyuy River region, Yakutia. The rare example of an indigenous Siberian collective song-dance that is performed only once a year, during the festival of sun, utilizes variation of the same formula on every repetition by every participant, where only a single anchor tone is “tuned in,” while other tones keep “floating” in pitch (Tatarinova 2013). Such texture presents a metrically synchronized version of isophony. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 6\]](#)

In such a case, uncoordinated use of pitch, rhythm and timbre is on the way of obtaining certain pitch, rhythm and timbre values, “fine-tuned” by means of extended practice of solo exercising as well as responsorial-style duetting. The most likely activities that promoted such training were grooming vocalizations, through which humming- or grunting-like sounds could have acquired pitch and rhythm values, and motherese, where mother’s lulling or playing vocalizations became attuned to the instinctive cries of an infant, as a result acquiring distinct structural features for more effective two-part communication. Once established and habituated to, these structural features could be utilized in performance by two or more participants.

The Earliest Forms of Functional Differentiation within the Composition

Acquisition of pitch coordination skills demands reduction of a number of simultaneously sounding parts in order to focus one’s attention on just two pitch contours: the auditioned source and the produced target – in order to match them. Only after the algorithms of matching are established is it possible to proceed to chunking information and increasing the number of simultaneously coordinated parts. This requirement relates to both situations:

- an attempt to sing together with someone, in which case, one singer has to hear another singer and match that singer in specific acoustic properties (e.g., pitch, rhythm, timbre),
- an attempt to sing solo and to match one’s own previous instance of performance to the current one, in which case the same person listens to his/her own voice and adjusts his/her sound production accordingly.

In the process of that, *ekmelic* (aka, indefinite in pitch and, therefore, based on stretchable interval classes and registral zonal pitch classes) tonal organization becomes transformed into *emmelic* (aka, definite in pitch and, therefore, based on fixed interval and “pointillistic” pitch classes) (see Nikolsky 2015 for the discussion).

The most important feature of ekmelic (e.g., recitative-like epic tales and animal spells of Siberian indigenous peoples) and timbral (e.g., deep throat singing of Mongols and Tuvans) forms of music is that they do not allow collective performance. The details in sliding from one pitch level to another, in rendition of a pitch contour, in connecting two contrasting registers and in engaging this or that timbral effect – all these modifications can effectively convey information only if a voice of the performer is not masked by some other performer (Nikolsky et al., 2020). Juxtaposition of multiple performers will inevitably make it hard to detect what exactly comes from the mouth of each of them – very much like the sound of 3 persons simultaneously talking on top of each other turns their words that might make perfect sense if heard one by one into a meaningless noise. Only the emmelic forms of tonal organization strengthen music and allow multiple performers to deliver a clear message to a listener.

For this reason, ekmelic and timbral forms of music as a rule engage monophonic textures. Furthermore, ekmelic and timbral music traditions possess remarkable longevity – exclusively monophonic performance in solitary settings or for a narrow circle of closest relatives or friends effectively conserves the means of musical expression. Innovations in music usually originate from the rhetoric use of music in order to convince the audience in the authenticity of the transmitted information.

The highest rate of innovation is observed in those music cultures that contain musical theater or some form of program music, designed to impersonate a certain character, suggest a certain feeling or represent a certain situation in a manner of enactment. The necessity to impact the listener in a certain way, move him/her towards specific reaction and convince that the musical expression is “for real,” and not pretension, encourages performers to look for ways to increase the suggestive power of music. Hence the modernization of expressive means (Alekseyev 1976).

Singing an ekmelic or timbral song to oneself, one’s child or a parent does not pose rhetoric goals of convincing anyone in anything. Singing here occurs as a matter of fact, usually as an accompaniment of daily routines (e.g., walking, riding, fishing, knitting, etc.), and therefore, acquires an existential status – “I sing, therefore, I am” (Sheikin 2002, 304). In such applications, exceedingly common in societies of hunter/gatherers that live in hard climatic conditions and whose population is scarce, the expressive means of music usually becomes well conserved.

Subsequently, whenever a musical culture passes through the transition from ekmelic to emmelic tonal organization, it usually triggers an intense development of expressive means and the evolution of musical texture. An example of this is Yakut traditional music. Compare the Audio Example No.6 of collective Yakut singing above with this example of a Yakut ekmelic solo singing (monophony):

7. **Audio:** *Tuul Yryata*. Song in sleep, involuntary and therefore unintended to influence listeners. The ekmelic traits feature many gliding intonations, frequent fluctuations in pitch and timbral recolorations. They are not designed to convince anyone in anything and therefore represent stereotypical features of Yakut traditional music. All in all, this song can hardly be performed by multiple performers. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 7\]](#)

In other ekmelic cultures, the tradition of singing-for-oneself can preserve the monophonic song – as in the Hopi Indian culture that contains both, ekmelic melody-making (List 1985) and emmelic tradition of individual and kinship songs (List 1997).

Once emmelic culture of vocal production is put in place, it enables collective performance of music and creation of choral songs. Their cultivation, in turn, further increases the homogeneity in tuning, especially for the harmonic intervals that possess the highest roughness (seconds and sevenths). As a result, a music system becomes rasterized in steps of specific size (e.g., semitones, whole tones or minor thirds, as in pentatonic music).

Collective singing usually introduces changes in the performance settings in order to generate diversity or to support specific genres: singing “tutti” (everyone) can contrast singing “a duo” (duet), “a trio” or

solo, which can be arranged as echoing repetitions, as question and answer, or as contrasting musical material. The extensive use of any of such settings is likely to cause slight discrepancies in pitch and rhythm between all the participants. The greater discrepancies, the thicker the musical texture.

That is why the evolution of tonal organization of music transpires in the evolution of the typologies of musical textures – they tend to become more complex, which might involve their relative “thickness,” salience of specific layers, greater diversity in functionality of layers and in the type of musical material employed for this or that layer (e.g., a leaping primary melody, a stepwise secondary melody, a melodic ostinato figuration, a pedal tone, a double-tone drone, chords, etc..).

The responsorial setting especially is prone to intensify the pitch correction mechanisms in new forms of emmelic singing and bring performers to some agreement in their pitch values, thereby generating pitch classes and pitch sets. This leads to the emergence of emmelic modes and enables a singer to share his/her tuning style with the community, while negotiating the average tuning, attractive to everyone. In densely populated communities, any remnants of the indefinite monophonic tradition tend to quickly give way to harmonically attuned collective monophonic singing. As a result, a music system receives not only a repertory of most popular musical modes but also a typology of interval classes.

The next step is the emergence of emmelic *heterophonic* and *diphonic* textures – distinguished by the extent of continuity and autonomy of performer’s parts:

- ***heterophonic*** arrangement is based on a single melody that is carried with little minute variations by each (or some) of the participating performers so that the entire musical texture appears to temporarily “bifurcate” or “trifurcate” (etc.) after which the “outbranches” join again into a perfect unison (Nikolsky 2018),
- ***diphonic*** arrangement contains a second part that is different in its melodic material from the primary part and demonstrates a greater extent of continuity of its textural arrangement throughout a music work as compared to the nexus of momentary “outbranching” and reunification of the heterophonic arrangement; therefore, diphony constitutes a *polyphonic* rather than heterophonic texture.

This difference might not be well defined, in which case the deciding criterion is whether the entire music work is designed to simultaneously present one melodic idea (a single type of thematic material that conveys a single semantic value), or two. In other words, we have to figure out if the texture consists of just one part that is somehow distributed between multiple performers or of two different parts. The latter usually sounds like some sort of disagreement between two components, in contrast to the former.

8. **Audio:** *Lapp song* in memory of a deceased father-in-law, Kola Peninsula. Husband and wife sing a personal song of their father-in-law to commemorate his kindness. The lyrics are mostly meaningless vocables. The son starts his father’s song, and his wife joins in an octave higher, however she delivers her own version of the same tune, at times substantially deviating from her husband (e.g., repeating a motif, while her husband carries on to a new motif – thereby generating a very brief polyphonic counterpoint). [\[See Supplementary Audio File 8\]](#)

This most basic implementation of heterophony engages just 2 parts each of which presents its own autonomous rendition of a mutual melodic model – the second performer does not try to perfectly merge with the first one, but merely sings along sharing the same tempo and pitch classes. There is a certain disconnection between both singers: each as though “speaks for himself/herself” on the same topic and sharing the same sentiment (hence the same melody) yet with slight difference in attitudes (the male singer leads and exposes a greater emotional intensity).

We can call this primordial form of heterophony “*oligotonal*” – from the Greek “oligo” that means “few” – because it uses very few pitch classes, and some of them remain not completely fixed in pitch value,

wandering up and down, depending on their proximity to the fixed anchor-tones (see Nikolsky 2015a). Oligotonal heterophony usually engages very few performers, 2-3, who exhibit considerable differences in their rendition of the same tune, treating it more like concurrent singing of “solo + solo” rather than perfectly matching “duet”. Nevertheless, even this highly autonomous form of heterophony still comes out as a concordant expression of the same musical idea charged with the same emotional state – unlike diphony.

The evolutionary first forms of diphony were likely to follow the discovery of “step equivalence” (see Nikolsky 2015a) and therefore featured the interval of a 2nd as a formative vertical interval.

9. **Audio:** *Harvest Song*, Shope Country, Bulgaria. 2-part polyphonic sections, based on 2^{nds} and unisons, contrast the collective *otglas* (i.e., the ascending glissando slide that terminates phrases). This music contains the disagreement between two melodies that tonally challenge each other, despite being quite similar in their expressions. This is like a struggle of two fighters that share much in common in their appearance. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 9\]](#)

The *diphonic* texture resembles oligotonal heterophony by being fragmentary, albeit for longer runs, but still differing from the full-featured polyphony that as a rule sustains its texture for the most of a music work. Diphonic phrases and sentences usually do not keep overlapping in their cadences. Instead, their polyphonic exposure is terminated by monophonic or heterophonic (contemporaneous) cadences. Therefore, diphony is not a fully-fledged form of polyphony. Nevertheless, diphony shares with polyphony the underlying property of “colliding” parts, so that one part becomes excited while another part relaxes. This discrepancy is responsible for the propensity of polyphonic texture to carry some kind of disagreement: parts either argue, compete for attention, cannot come to agreement, or interrupt each other to add something new – all in all, as though presenting multiple angles on the same topic.

A 2nd-based diphony must have set the model for a clustered *triphony* (3-part texture) that sounds even more messy and disagreeing.

10. **Audio:** *Odkad seke nismo zapjevale*, ganga, Bosnia. 3-part polyphony of “clustered” style, with common motion in parallel 2^{nds}. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 10\]](#)

Diphonic texture upgrades to triphonic texture by means of step equivalence through a mechanical addition of equidistant steps according to the number of available participants. If the number exceeds three and becomes too great for an ear to recognize parts and participants in the hotch-potch of melodies, the textural arrangement will break performers into groups, each assigned to carry out a single dedicated part in the texture. The criterion of what constitutes an excessive number of parts is, of course, cultural, however, it relies on the cognitive constraint in sharing attention between no more than 3-4 simultaneously running parts (Stoter et al. 2013). Greater polyphonic density requires hierarchic organization of texture, with some parts carrying important musical material, while other parts – less important – so that the listener would use diagonal shifts of attention, skipping from one part to another, following some musical cues (Huron 1989). In Western classical tradition this method is exemplified in imitative polyphonic techniques that characterize such genres as *ricercar*.

Folk music can also employ “part-compressing” compositional devices (i.e. imitation, ostinato, responsorial) to distribute thematically important musical material across different parts by permanently assigning an important melodic line to a specific part in the texture. In doing so, it can follow a numerical order from the top or bottom of the texture, and define the other parts in terms of their functionality in regard to the principal part (Jordania 2006, 28).

The visual equivalent of simple diphonic texture would be an ensemble of two depicted objects, united by the subject of depiction, their interaction and the continuity of a depicted scene.

Image 4. *Two fighting rhinos*, Chauvet, 30,000 BC. The ensemble of two images is created by the joint action of “fighting,” known from real life.

But before we proceed to discussing the place of heterophonic, diphonic and triphonic textures in the timeline of the evolution of tonal development in music along with the timeline of the corresponding compositional devices in evolution of fine art, let us touch on another extremely important trait that characterizes the earliest forms of rock art uncovered by archaeologists.

Naturalist vs. Schematic Methods of Representation

Another important trait of Paleolithic spatial organization and, as we shall see in this chapter, of the hypothetical Stone Age music, is *naturalism*. The oldest discovered cave art is strikingly realistic: the unknown painter accurately converted visible contours of real objects into the contours of a pictorial image (Hauser 1999a). Following the compositional analogies that we have so far established, such method of representation can be related to *psychophysiological* intonation in singing (Sheikhin 2002, 30), which is characterized by imitation of sounds of nature (i.e. wind) and human/animal-produced sounds (i.e. flint-knapping, horse steps or animal calls).

11. Audio: *Geese Katajjait*, Canada. Vocal imitation of geese cries in a timbre-oriented Inuit music culture. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 11\]](#)

Both, indigenous forms of naturalistic music and depiction, have their roots in animistic ideology and shamanism, the premise of which is that the real-life object represented in arts and its representation itself are inherently connected by supernatural forces and, therefore, can influence each other (Hubbard 2003). Thus, in shamanic traditions of many Northern Siberian ethnicities, melodic and pictorial contours are believed to have power to affect the corresponding real objects (Novik 2004, 67–85).

Great precaution characterizes use of figurative art in numerous hunter/gatherer societies of Siberia, Northern America, and South Asia: drawings that depict ritual images on tambourines are washed out upon completion of a rite, drawings on snow that accompany Eskimo story-telling are destroyed at the end of the story, faces drawn on masks are burned after their use, etc. (V.V.Ivanov 2014, 4:357). Similar precautions and taboos are found in relation to musical instruments, e.g., many different native Siberian ethnicities believe that shaman’s tambourines are under the spell, so that touching it can inflict trouble on anyone else other than the owner (Sheikin 2002, 69-86).

In accordance with such belief system, indigenous Siberians have been conducting rites to seek a favorable outcome for their important activities from supernatural entities, like spirits, deities, dead ancestors, etc.. Such rites involve both, music and depiction (Nikolsky et al. 2020). Thus, Siberian hunters imitate the sound typically made by a prey prior to hunting or draw an image that graphically represents that prey on a piece of bark of a tree. Often such representations are realistic in trying to capture characteristic details in the prey's calls or its visible contour.

However, the similarity is not imperative for the belief that the magic will work. Once the supernatural connection is set in a mind of an indigenous hunter, keeping the sensory resemblance between natural objects and their reproduction is optional. Naturalism of representation is required only in the emerging phase of shamanic tradition: once the connection between an image and its real prototype is established, the depiction can become significantly simplified and stylized – and over time it can lose any resemblance to its original prototype. In fact, the object that secures a supernatural connection usually obtains the status of a fetish, which is often accompanied by taboos on mentioning this object's name or and/or other means of reference (Novik 1998).

Visual and musical representation also can be tabooed, in which case indigenous people usually invent some form of symbolic representation by a deliberately dissimilar sign. Often, such decidedly schematic sign (visual as well as auditory) can be combined with realistic renditions of other entities that accompany the tabooed entity but are not believed to possess supernatural power. In such a case, a composition becomes collage-like: a schematically represented sacred entity as though becomes cut off from all surrounding realistic objects, and the compositional unity is broken. A famous example of such collage effect is the “bird on stick” image at Lascaux cave.

Image 5. *Animals and Bird on Stick with Human and Bison, Lascaux cave at Dordogne, France, c.17,000 BCE. The abstraction of the human image and of some shamanic accessory is collaged with a realistic animal picture.*

Collage-like bordering of realistic and schematic images in a single picture finds a counterpart in shamanic deep throat singing tradition, widespread across Siberia and Far East. Its sound-production technique is designed to imitate “voices of nature” simultaneously with shaman’s natural “human” voice. This can be achieved in a variety of ways. The most obvious method is production of two distinct pitches by the same singer, either by generating subharmonic tones with the help of false vocal chords, or using resonance of the upper face to generate overtones (Lindestad et al. 2001). In both cases, a single singer manages to emit a heterophonic or diphonic texture, where the melodic line proceeds from one tone to another on a sustained fundamental drone (Kyrgyz 2002).

- 12. Audio:** Cave Spirits, Tuva. The *kargyraa* deep throat singing style, characterized by simultaneous engagement of the vocal and vestibular folds, creating a growling impression. The collage of “natural” and “artificial” parts by a single vocalist. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 12\]](#)

Less obvious is the “collage of parts” achieved by an ongoing breaking of the voice. Thus, the Yakut *kylysakh* technique (Alekseyev 2016) presents a peculiar bi-timbral “diphony solo” (quasi 2-part singing by a single performer) (Alekseyev 1976, 7–8), produced by quick “grace-note”-like leaps from the “overtone voice” to the normal voice – such peculiar breaking probably was initially reserved for communication with “dangerous” spirits (Novik 2004, 67–85) akin to an “auditory mask” for the shaman’s voice.

- 13. Audio:** Song of the heaven shaman woman, Aiyy Umsuur, from olonkho “*Niurgun Bohotur*,” Sakha. The *kylysakh* style characterizes positive supernatural characters. Thus, in this epic chant, the shaman turns into a stark to bless Niurgun Bohotur before his battle with the underground bohotur (Alekseyev and Nikolayeva 1981, 25). [\[See Supplementary Audio File 13\]](#)

As you can hear in this example, frequent “grace-notes” of *kylysakh* make the impression of getting in the way of pitch classes generated by a “normal” singing voice, causing tension and clash of singing techniques. This is what can be qualified as a technique of vocal “collage”, characterized by pronounced lack of compositional integrity.

Reproductions whose entire composition is supposed to be sacred are likely to be rendered entirely in a schematic manner. This must be the case with the depiction of a shamanic rite at La Valltorta:

Image 6. *Shamanic rite*, from La Valltorta, Spain, ca. 6,000 BP. A stylized drawing of two human figures and some animal.

The equivalent of such deliberately artificial (musically “schematic”) vocal representation can be found in the music works that are entirely based on “false voice” production – “falsetto”.

- 14. Audio:** Chant of Tukuna boys and girls, Amazon Indians. A rare occasion of choral singing at a feast celebrating initiation of girls, where all the guests reproduce the same intonation falsetto to assure strength and protection from the evil forest spirits (Schultz and Chiara 1962). [\[See Supplementary Audio File 14\]](#)

The growing share of schematization of pictorial contours towards the end of the Paleolithic, in place of previously dominated naturalism, had nothing to do with the decline of technical skills on the part of a

painter. French caves retained schematic art side by side with realistic 3D sculptures, reliefs, and carvings of animals, such as L'Abri-du-Cap-Blanc, ca. 15,000 BP, or Roc aux Sorciers, ca. 14,000 BP (Hauser 1999a). Thus, the cave located at La Marche contained many realistic depictions of human heads and figures, dated 15,000 BC – time when schematic style became popular in the same region.

- Schematization should be regarded as a deliberate method of representing not what artist's senses detect in real world but what that artist knows about entities that he/she is trying to represent by means of his/her art.

For the purpose of our overview, the importance of this method is that it deliberately damages composition by making it partially or completely unrealistic. However, one of the consequences of cultivation of such traditions is that schematic representation helps art-users realize the conventionality of physical attributes of the expressive means of arts.

Visual contours can be ascribed semantic values followed not the iconic similarity between the signifier and the signified by following an arbitrarily adopted convention. Initially sacred, tabooed and secretive, such arbitrary connection of the physical appearance of a sign to a dissimilar-looking semantic content tends to put in place purely symbolic means of signification.

As a result, both fine art and music, open doors to quick advance in elaboration of new expressive means – very much in line with the development of language in indigenous societies. They also start with languages where onomatopoeia and phonetic symbolism occupy a prominent place but end up with the bulk of new words that bear no similarity in their sound to features of entities that these words denote (Nuckolls 2004). The same development marks the ontogenetic acquisition of verbal skills throughout childhood (Monaghan et al., 2014).

The Emergence of Compositional Grouping

The next advance in pictorial composition was the discovery of a continuity of objects designed to indicate an event by means of grouping together schematic pictorial representation of different objects.

Image 7. *Man gathering honey*, from the Cuevas de la Araña en Bicorp, Valencia, Spain, ca. 8,000 BP. A schematic representation of a human figure with a vessel, tree with a hive, and bees. All of them look disproportionately to each other, united only by common knowledge of what the task of gathering honey actually involves.

Just like pictorial images can be joined by proximity and knowledge of the depicted happening, musical objects can be grouped by their immediate succession in music and by knowledge of what is going on. Contrasting “schematic” melodic motifs can be grouped together into a single melodic stream by the device of a responsorial, where two parties of performers keep continuously responding to each other, so that each party retains its own character and disposition, yet each following reply is

influenced by the previous entry. Obviously, the lyrics often take the role of informing the audience about what is actually represented.

15. Audio: *Ahir Birha*, Northern India and Nepal. This holler-style responsorial song represents an argument between two milkmen about the extent of sacredness of cow and river Gang (Junius 1972), illustrated in a progressive escalation of tension. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 15\]](#)

The horizontally harmonized melodic line produces *heterophony* – which can be defined as series of short bifurcations and trifurcations from the principal melodic formula, designed to complement singing preferences of each of the participants, and/or provide variety in multiple repetitions. Such texture differs from isophony by keeping all parts basically in-sync and limiting the discrepancies to the pitch domain rather than the rhythm domain. Technically speaking, the heterophonic typology is based on *stratification of a single part into multiple voices*. Here, it would be useful to point out the principal difference between “part” and “voice” in the theory of music texture (Skrebkova-Filatova 1985).

- **“Part”** is a coherent layer in a music texture that possesses certain continuity within the entire music work, is designed for the performance by the same type of a musical instrument or of a vocal, and differs from other parts by its textural function (e.g., principal melody, secondary contrasting melody, bass line, figure of an accompaniment, etc.). Its function and instrumentation usually determine what kind of pattern the musical material of a part employs (e.g., a guitar accompaniment often uses strumming chords, a harp accompaniment - an ostinato figuration, whereas horns – pedal tones). The differences of patterns enable listeners to recognize specific parts as constituents of a particular type of texture. Yet another aspect of tonal organization for a part is its relative “thickness”: part can be implemented as a solo, a “combo” (small group of soloists), or a “tutti” (a large group about 8 or more performers).
- **“Voice”** is a sublayer within a part that does not have to possess continuity (e.g., a part can temporarily break into voices, when a group of saxophones repeatedly play a pattern of the accompaniment that consists of a “lick” in unison followed by a single chord). Division of a part into voices can be continuous within a dedicated section of music (in the practice of orchestration, this is usually marked as “divisi”, whereas its cancellation – as “unison”). The onset of sublayering usually appears as “washing off,” smudging, or shading of a clear contour of a part, similar to “sfumato” in painting. Different voices, like parts, can be distinguished by their textural functions: e.g., in a chord, the upper voice is usually marked out by heightened expressivity as melodically important, the bottom voice is usually marked dynamically to emphasize the root of a chord, and the middle voice is the weakest.

In the example below, the texture consists of a single melodic part that is layered between a great number of performers, where some parts become more salient than others.

16. Audio: *Gaelic psalm*, Hebrides, Isle of Lewis. This is one of the most complex implementations of the heterophony: a single melodic line is “smudged” by consistent delays between different parts (Knudsen 1968)—presenting a rare style of melodic variation by means of a deliberate “reverberation” effect induced by the continuous sub-beat lagging between parts (Cooke 2001). Yet, despite this complexity, the music clearly expresses a single idea conveyed by a single melodic stream. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 16\]](#)

This type of heterophony constitutes its “classic” model (Nikolsky 2018), characteristic for folk traditions. It differs from the primordial oligotonal heterophony (Audio Example 8) by featuring greater number of performers (3 and more), their subdivision into soloists and groups (can feature a few soloists and a few choral groups, interacting in a responsorial format), sometimes with some basic instrumental accompaniment (although most of the time this texture is vocal), and by its orientation towards forming a deliberate “tutti”. Unlike the disjointed combination of 2 or 3 simultaneous variants of the same melody in oligotonal heterophony, here we have a clear harmonic integration between all participants – they all actively seek an opportunity to merge into a single melodic stream. Subsequently, individual deviations become much less pronounced than in the oligotonal heterophony.

The “choral” orientation, most evident in the increase of the number of performers, finds its counterpart in the expansion of the ambitus of music and the number of pitch classes in a musical mode. Therefore, this heterophony cannot operate in an oligotonal mode. It requires at least a mesotonal mode. For this reason, the best way of distinguishing this type of heterophony from oligotonal type is by calling it *mesotonal* (if it uses 5-6 pitch classes) or *multitonal* (7 or more pitch classes).

On the other hand, comparing to strict monophony, mesotonal heterophony presents a thicker texture due to out-branching of voices. In this respect, heterophony functionally opposes monophony – the relation that is often overlooked by musicologists but is compositionally very important.

1. The pragmatic idea behind collective **heterophony** is *individualizing* a known melody in a collective performance, so that each of the performers can render that melody to his liking while remaining “on topic”.
2. The pragmatic idea behind collective **monophony** is *sacrificing individual taste* in favor of adhering to a single standard as shared by the group of performers.
3. The pragmatic idea behind collective **polyphony** is *opposing* one melodic material with another, so that performers as though “collide” two topics (their relation could range from anything between “conflicting,” on the one pole, and “presenting an alternative view” on the same topic, on the other pole).

The opposing nature of polyphonic texture is evident in the ethnomusicological definition of polyphony: “a mode of expression based on simultaneous combination of *separate parts*, perceived and produced *intentionally* in their *mutual differentiation*, in a given *formal order*” (Agamennone 1996). My italics mark those criteria in the definition that contribute to the tendency of polyphonic parts to clash and compete for attention.

The pragmatic distinction between heterophony, monophony and polyphony comes handy whenever the tonal organization within a texture is unclear. Heterophony, monophony, and polyphony each presents a **class** of types rather than an elementary type (as we shall see from further examination of the historic development of texture). There is a range of continuity within each of these 3 classes, where number, functions and typology of musical material that constitutes each of the constituent parts and voices within a part can vary in the extent of their autonomy. Subsequently, one type of a texture can resemble another type. Thus, the Hebrides psalm (Example 16) can be mistaken for polyphony (Knudsen 1968). The entry on heterophony in the Grove dictionary contains a notation example of a Hebrides psalm that looks like a “jumbled texture,” which is comprised of scattered asynchronous entries of 5 singers:

Ex.2 Opening of 'Martyrdom', Isle of Lewis, Hebrides (Knudsen)

voice 1
Tha cui d-gea ta bs'

(after preceding the text)
voice 2
Tha cui ui d-gea ta a bs'

voice 3
Tha cui d-gea ta bs'

voice 4
Tha cui uid ta bs'

voice 5
Tha cui d-gea ta bs'

But in reality such music does not sound “jumbled” at all. Its asynchronicities remain tiny - in the order of a fraction of a beat (usually less than half a beat). Polyphonic imitations usually occur over the periods of 2-8 beats. Sub-beat discrepancies of the Hebrides chant fall short of evoking the perception of a new polyphonic entry. Instead, they create an unusual “sfumato” effect by slightly smudging the melodic line. Musical textures should always be evaluated based on the arrangement of the thematic material.

Now that we understand the distinctions between three principal classes in the typology of music textures, we can discuss what would be a perceptual equivalent of layering a heterophonic part into fragmentary voices.

Spatial equivalent of heterophony is such a pictorial composition, where one object in the ensemble occasionally masks another, thereby indicating which of them is closer to the observer – while, at the same time, presenting the overlapping objects as a single compound entity. Akin to heterophony, which is morphologically the easiest (and therefore, likely the earliest) form of consistent *harmonization* of multiple constituents within the same texture, “masking” is the earliest indicator of spatial harmonization – i.e., rendition of 3D data onto 2D plane.

Just like the presence of harmonization distinguishes heterophony from isophony, the presence of masking distinguishes spatial grouping from flat “jumbled” juxtaposition of disconnected images in a pictorial composition. Masking demonstrates that two depicted objects each occupy its own slot of space despite the superficial impression they give in sharing the same space. Just as heterophony was possible at earlier stage of ekmelic music (Audio Example No. 6), masking can be found in earliest forms of art – at first, in a form of a *bas-relief*, in Solutrean Fourneau du Diable, Bourdeilles, and later, in murals.

Image 8. *Font-de-Gaume bison and deer*, 14,000 BC. The image of a deer is superimposed over that of a bison, queuing the depth parameter – perhaps, its earliest occurrence.

The transition from ekmelic to emmelic organization refreshes the isophonic texture by providing definite pitch for vertical coordination of parts. Interaction of isophony and heterophony is likely to have produced the simplest form of harmonization of the constituent tones within a music texture, namely - *non-functional homophony*.

- **Homophony** – is such organization of music texture where all parts move together at more or less the same pace, forming harmonic relations that are expressed in chords (Hyer 2001). Chord is a unit of harmonic fusion of numerous complex tones, perceived holistically as a single percept – which imposes a very high requirement for multi-part synchrony for homophony, higher than for other types of texture (Huron 2001). Tones in a chord must have their onsets in the order of no more than 30-50 msec (Rasch 1988).

Many scholars assume that homophony occurs only in genres and styles of music that are part of Western classical music tradition or are its derivatives (such as Western popular music or musical traditions of former Western colonies). Indeed, Western homophony is an advanced form of tonal organization that emerged no earlier than in the 17th century, after Vincenzo Galilei, Giulio Caccini, and Claudio Monteverdi succeeded in launching *Seconda pratica* (aka, *Stile moderno*) in opposition to *Prima pratica* of Renaissance polyphony, and made its philosophy of monodic exposition of musical ideas win the international acclaim (Selfridge-Field 1990). However, chords and homophony by no means are limited to Western musical traditions. Below is the example of a chord-based music genre from a music culture that is very distant from Western classical music.

17. **Audio:** *Ompeh music*, Akan people from the Efufu area of Ghana. The example of popular in West Africa the call-and-response form between soloist and chorus, where the chorus performs a multi-part dubbing of the soloist's melody – what appears as the chain reproduction of the same “chord.” [\[See Supplementary Audio File 17\]](#)

A monophonic music can be expanded into a simple homogenous homophonic texture that can resemble Western homophony by following the principle of dubbing a monophonic melody in a fixed vertical interval (usually, a 3rd, but sometimes a 4th, 5th and even major 2nd). Western classical music also passed through this stage, embodied in the genre of parallel organum of the 9th – 12th centuries (aka, *diaphonia*). Its music theory, documented in the treatise “*Musica enchiriadis*” (c.895) and other treatises, explained its texture in a non-polyphonic way – as a result of the idea to reinforce and harmonically enhance one of the sacred melodies from the canonic collections of Gregorian chant, implemented in a simple way, by ear, through consistent dubbing of a melody in 4th, 5th and octave (Tallmadge 1984).

Technically, this is the same method that is often employed in traditional music of different African countries, where a melody can be presented as a chain of parallel triads (Kubik 1998) and even 7th-chords, performed in a 4-parts arrangement, such as the ongoing alternations between C-E-G-B and Db-F-Ab-C, recorded at Bigene village, Nola District, Central African Republic (Kubik 2005).

- The principal pragmatic idea of such “**parallel homophony**” is perfect melodic agreement between multiple parts, where each part is disciplined to avoid any individualized embellishments in order to express a single melodic idea: in a way, a powerful collective statement of “plurality in unity.” All participants start and end at the same point, always keep a perfect rhythmic sync, and sing the same text. Such texture appears consistently thicker and more forceful than heterophony, and more homogenous and orderly compared to isophony.

Parallel homophony can be considered “**natural**” in a sense that its design seems to be rooted in the idea of emphasizing formants of human speech or overtone singing – i.e., reinforcing one of the lower harmonics in a harmonic series (Kubik 2005). Strictly speaking, we should not speak of “chords” in such music but rather of “a chord” – the entirety of music texture constitutes a coordinated reproduction of the same natural “chord” rather than succession of chords, where certain chords are subordinated to others. Creators of such music report that they conceive the progression of triads and 7th-chords as a reproduction of the same model, where each chordal structure has equal status – in contrast to the functional homophony of Western music that is based on fluctuations of tonal tension in such formulaic progressions as Tonic-Subdominant-Dominant (Kubik 1999, 105).

Once established in a music culture, parallel homophony can evolve into more complex texture that features contrasts between various chords. An example of such texture can be found in Georgian traditional music:

- 18. Audio:** *Kakhuri nana*, Georgian lullaby. The 3-part harmony of the chorus contains diversity of chords while remaining homophonic. Perfectly synced chords color the principal melody initiated by the soloist by the succession of chords varying in the extent of their harmonic tension and relaxation. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 18\]](#)

Although, Georgian music is often capped under the title of “polyphony,” many of its genres feature homophonic organization: all parts move simultaneously, follow the same pattern of syllabification and are called to harmonically recolor a single principal melody that carries the main expression. The complexity of harmonic structures here can challenge Western classical music. However, the foundation of Georgian tradition of multi-part singing is dated by most experts earlier than 4th century AD (Javakhishvili 2010) and, therefore, cannot be attributed to the Western influence. Western culture of “thinking in chords” (Nutting 1974) seems to find its counterpart in Georgian folk traditions.

- Western chords differ from Georgian chords by their standardization and their functional reduction to just 4 types of triads and 8 types of 7th-chords. All other chordal structures are viewed as inversion of the basic ones or as featuring non-chordal tones. Furthermore, chordal structures are distinguished by their harmonic functionality – intervallic structure of chords possible in a key is determined by chord’s harmonic function (tonic, subdominant or dominant) (Sposobin 1951). That is why the best way to distinguish this type of homophony from folk ones is by calling it “**functional homophony**”.
- Georgian homophony, like African parallel homophony, is **non-functional**, because its folk manner of distribution prevents uniform standardization and classification of chordal and intervallic typology, without which it is impossible to reduce the entire variety of possible chords to a single principle. For this reason, a homophony that is based on a variety of chords is bound to be far from simple rational. And this is what we find in Georgian music system: e.g., Megrelian multi-part textures engage 18 types of chords on the VI degree, 14 - on the V, and 13 – on the IV degrees (Arom 2010). This is in sharp contrast to Western music theory that codifies only 3 triads and 3 7th-chords on these degrees of a key. The best way of characterizing Georgian homophony is by calling it “**multi-chordal**”.

In this capacity, Georgian homophony resembles Western genre of pre-tonal (modal) chorale, as implemented by the early Baroque composers of the 17th century. Their chorales, like Georgian homophony, were also based on a rich assortment of non-classified chords.

So, what would be the visual equivalent to non-functional homophonic organization? - The main homophonic trait is the reinforcement of a single part that carries a very expressive melody by other parts in strict *équiritmique* manner while spacing the parts according to some euphonic harmonic interval. In visual domain, a similar compositional arrangement would be the use of multiple reproductions of the same expressive image, with minimal variations, organized into a proportional, rhythmically pleasant ensemble within a contiguous pictorial space. Such pictorial device was commonly used in prehistoric art to express the idea of abundance of natural resources or greatness of manpower of a tribe.

Image 9. *Antelopes and hands*, Altamira, ca. 16,000-12,000 BC. Multiple images of clone-like antelopes probably signify abundance of food supply.

Image 10. *Warriors*, La Valltorta cave, Spain 6,000 BP. Multiple schematic images of running humans with spears likely illustrate the power of a tribe.

Image No. 9 suits the parallel homophony, because the multiple occurrences of antelopes look too similar and produce more ornamental impression. Their arrangement is rather schematic, complementing the schematic rendition of hands. In contrast, Image No.10 suits the multi-chordal homophony, because the

reproductions of a “running man” are quite diverse in little details, looking more like a scenery. Greater differentiation in replicas of the same figure contributes to a more realistic impression.

The Emergence of the Parameter of Depth

Once the methods of compositional grouping were established, the composition received a potential for representing the parameter of depth. For visual arts, the combination of visual continuity and the device of masking one contour with another is known to lead to the intuitive discovery of a so-called *bird's-eye view perspective* [aka, aerial view] – i.e., the idea of representing the parameter of depth by rising the vantage point so that it would be possible to look as though “over” the object in the foreground closest to the observer (Donger 2018). The germ of such a perspective can be found in prehistoric cultures.

Image 11. Rock art at [Balho](#), Djibouti, near Ethiopian border, Neolithic culture (Gutherz, Cros, and Lesur 2003). An elevated view of a herd of antelopes and 2 giraffes reflects the experience of looking down from a mountain top.

Image 12. *San bushman* rock art, Ukahlamba Drakensberg Park, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa, near Lesotho, ca. 1000 BP (Herbert 1998). An elevated view of a scene depicting the capturing of a “Rain-bull”.

Notably, both examples above originate from the geographic areas where traditional polyphonic music is still in use. Especially across South Africa, polyphonic textures are exceedingly common amongst almost all native ethnicities.

19. Audio: *Gamo* dance song music, female and male choir, Ethiopia. Functional polyphony.

[\[See Supplementary Audio File 19\]](#)

20. Audio: *Dorze* dance song music, female choir, Ethiopia. Functional polyphony. [\[See](#)

[Supplementary Audio File 20\]](#)

21. Audio: *Ntoa hae e loana ke mosebetsi*, a pea threshing song, Lesotho. Functional polyphony.

[\[See Supplementary Audio File 21\]](#)

Sustained repetition of short melodic patterns, meshed across different voices, and tiered at different fixed pitches within a predetermined scale characterizes polyphony of cultures of African Horn as well as of South Africa (Arom 2004, 307). The necessity to represent a number of objects compositionally grouped along the imaginary depth axis requires the use of a polyphonic texture, since the view has to project the impression of being “distant” while covering a variety of objects. Monophony, heterophony and homophony are too flat and homogenous to support such an impression.

- **Functional polyphony** is such a texture that conjoins a few contrasting parts each of which carries its own melodic function (e.g., the most expressive and diverse melody, the secondary supporting smooth melody, a leaping bass, a pedal tone, an ostinato figuration, etc.).

At the point of formation of functional emmelic polyphony, the development of musical texture reaches its limit within a folk culture that is unsupported by notation, codified math-based music theory, institutionalized music teaching, and professionalized music performance. The next round of development occurs within the urban civilizations, documented by history. The entire succession of types of textures is presented in Table-3 below.

Table 3. Evolution of the typology of texture in compositional organization of music and realistic pictorial fine art. This table presents a hypothetical chronological order of development of the typology of musical textures (15 types total) plotted against the typology of music systems (see Nikolsky 2015a and 2016a), highlighting the most important corresponding features between the tonal organization in those musical textures and the spatial organization in pictorial arts.

Texture	System	Tonal Features	Spatial Features
1. Ekmelic Isophony (Audio Examples 1, 4)	Timbral	Brief call, continuously reproduced by multiple performers with irrational deviations in timing and pitch, where each participant retains idiosyncrasy of the rhythmic, timbral, and directional attributes of the pitch contour – altogether producing a “jumbled” effect.	Disconnectedness of images, governed by reproduction of visual contours of a real prototype – with frequent cluttering and overlapping of newly made and earlier made images on the cave wall.
2. Ekmelic Monophony (Ex. 7)	Ekmelic (Nikolsky 2015)	Brief formula, continuously repeated by a solo performer, with distinct timbral and pitch characteristics that keep modulating within a certain narrow range of values – representing an	Avoidance of clutter by reserving a dedicated pictorial space for each image; priority of naturalistic representation of a single object – single image per

		individual style of a singer in a manner similar to the unique sound of his voice.	single prototype, emphasizing their “sameness”.
3. Oligotonal Heterophony (Ex. 8)	Oligotonal (Nikoslky 2015)	Similar to the above, but performed collectively, more or less in-sync, with fragmentary deviations in pitch, so that overall the parts comprise a single tune recognizable by virtue of observing a close similarity of pitch, rhythm, and timbre between all the participants – while featuring quite autonomous variants of that tune brought to a single melodic denominator.	Indication of pictorial depth by means of one contour masking another, in imitation of a closer visual object blocking more distant objects – thereby representing not an object but a scene, where each object receives its own spatial spot while constituting an organic part of a whole image.
4. Emmelic Isophony (Ex. 6)	Oligotonal and Mesotonal (Nikoslky 2015)	Similar to the ekmelic isophony above, but with greater spread-out distribution in time, so that overlapping of parts provides greater fluidity and continuity by masking the breaks between the end of a tune and the beginning of its reproduction in some other part. In contrast, pitch values become discrete, fixed and coordinated.	Similar to the ekmelic isophony above, but with the grouping of a greater number of similar images altogether, producing greater continuity and more of the impression of a frontal view. Constituent objects display the presence of some basic arrangement in their spacing.
5. Mesotonal Heterophony (Ex. 16)	Mesotonal (Nikoslky 2015)	Similar to the oligotonal heterophony above, but performed collectively and in greater sync, often with subdivisions into a solo leader and a chorus, with only minute deviations in pitch, so that the tune is recognizable as the same melodic entity by virtue of observing what exactly is shared between all the participants – integrating all multiple melodic variants into a single melodic stream of constantly varying thickness.	Similar to the oligotonal heterophony above, but featuring more pictorial objects of the same kind, yet at the same time, some of these objects can become more salient due to differentiation in regard to a particular aspect or feature. The overall impression from the composition here is more massive and powerful.
6. Diphony (Ex. 9)	Mesotonal	Similar to the oligotonal heterophony above, but with greater spread-out distribution in pitch, so that the vertical intervals between the concurrent tones keep varying, while maintaining melodic continuity for each of the parts - presenting two autonomous melodic ideas at the same time on a more or less continuous basis, as though struggling for attention.	Similar to the oligotonal heterophony, but with more obvious ensemble relations that are formed between two autonomous images, where each image is assigned a particular function that is different from that of another image. At the same time, images are united by the subject and their interaction.
7. Triphony (Ex. 10)	Multitonal (Nikoslky 2015)	Same as the above, but involving three autonomous parts, concurrently producing two different vertical intervals, and presenting three autonomous ideas clustered together.	Same as the above, but with the ensemble of three different images, each executing its own function in the depicted scene while looking cluttered.
8. Parallel homophony (Ex. 17)	Multitonal, Pentatonic and Heptatonic	Perfectly synchronized rendition of all parts, comprised by dubbing a principal melodic line in a vertical interval, where dubbing is retained throughout most of	Multiplication of the same object, with minimal variations, organized into an ensemble within a contiguous space; each

		the musical work – representing a single melodic idea and expression.	of multiple occurrences executes the same function.
9. Functional Polyphony (Ex. 19-21)	Heptatonic (Nikolsky 2015)	Contrast of functions of parts within the texture: i.e. one part melodically leading, another supporting, offsetting, complimenting or interfering, etc. – thereby generating multiple melodies, related to one another by such means that are sustained within a music work.	Implementation of the elevated panoramic view, as though looking from the “bird’s eye view,” to display the objects positioned behind the frontal images, so that images execute different functions in a scene.
10. Monody (Ex. 23)	Extended diatonic family of modes (Nikolsky 2016a)	Similar to the monophony above, but performed by multiple vocals and/or musical instruments in a mathematically verified tuning that is defined by reference of all the tones to a single principal tone and interval, featuring the octave equivalent pentachord-tetrachord division, and the dominance of a single melodic line.	The same elevated panoramic view as above, but with mathematically verified canonic iconography: division of space in registers, alignment of images by the baseline, and general prevalence of frontal view in integrating all the pictorial objects within an entire work.
11. Functional Heterophony (Ex. 22)	Extended diatonic family of modes with chromatic alterations (Nikolsky 2016a)	Similar to the multitonal heterophony, but in a mathematically verified tuning applied to continuously expanding non-formulaic melody (rather than ongoing repetitions of the same “tune”), where the parts display functionality and autonomy: carrying a drone tone (possibly alternating between a few drone tones) or/and melodic dubs; marking the principal melody by more generous alterations. Listener usually appreciates such texture as an external observer of an aesthetic object (rather than as a participant in a show).	Similar to the multitonal heterophony, but following geometrically verifiable projections in marking the foreground and background of the picture, often engaging architecture; employing shading to indicate the depth aspect, and positioning the vantage point decidedly outside of the picture, conceiving the latter as an aesthetic object designed for appreciation from an unfixed external vantage point.
12. Modal Multi-chordal Homophony (Ex. 18)	Hypermode (Nikolsky 2016b)	Similar to the parallel homophony above, but featuring multiple chords that form various relations, generating chordal progressions and increases or decreases in harmonic tension. Introduction of interval classes.	Similar to the parallel homophony above, but featuring greater differentiation between the replicated objects so that the entire picture appears more like a sketch of a scenery.
13. Modal Polyphony (Ex. 27)	Hypermode (Nikolsky 2016b) and Hemiolic Chromatic (Nikolsky 2016c)	Mathematically verified tuning optimally defines the horizontal melodic as well as the vertical harmonic aspects of the musical texture, providing all parts with equal opportunities for chromatic shading and textural functionality; listener becomes included in the texture by the task of ongoing orientation in very complex structures – when he has to keep tracking a certain thematic material amongst the parts.	Geometrically verifiable projections are used to mark the foreground and background of the picture and connect them by defining a specific vantage point that fixes the position of the viewer, thereby integrating him into the depicted image in a manner of a window; all pictorial objects are defined in relation to this fixed point.

14. Triadic (aka, "Strict") Polyphony (Ex. 28)	"Monality" (Wienpahl 1971)	Mathematically verified tuning that mediates chords in vertical harmony, and melodies in horizontal harmony, favoring certain vertical and horizontal combinations of tones, while excluding others (restricting the use of dissonant intervals); governed by the idea of harmonious distribution of musical material in the virtual music space.	Mathematically verified single-point linear perspective, relatively strictly observing the unity of the scale, singularity of the vantage point, and a little more flexible in the implementation of convergence points; governed by the idea of clarity of composition.
15. Functional Homophony-Polyphony (Ex. 34)	Tonality (Nikolsky 2016a)	Mathematically verified tuning that mediates chords and melodies, allowing for unprecedented variety of functions and configurations of elements and components of texture; appreciation of originality in tonal organization; functionality of parts in texture and functionality of tones in horizontal harmony.	Mathematically verified linear perspective and shadow projection, allowing for deviations from the rules as well as spatial exaggerations; appreciation of originality in spatial organization; functionality of components in visual composition.

The Emergence of Math-based Theories of Rendition

The barrier that separates prehistoric music cultures from historic ones is the emergence of math-based theories of tuning and the codification of prescriptive music theory by the state officials who were put in charge of public performances and music teaching, - which standardized music practice and theory and professionalized music occupations (Nikolsky 2016d). Institution of the culture of literacy, specifically, popularization of verbal scripts and their use to record instructions and requirements of music theory, as well as the use of musical notation for documenting tunes and their tonal arrangement played crucial role in promoting and conserving new forms of music.

Their wide adoption was accomplished through the set of energetic reforms, mandated by kings who adopted the power of chief priests and used it to delegate the tasks of dissemination of new music and supervision over its usage to the casts of priests and scribes. The earliest description of such a reform comes from Mesopotamia, 3rd millennium BC.

Once put in place in one state, such new model of the official music administration spread into adjacent states, viewed as an embodiment of the power of the state and a great value in the regional competition for political dominance. The socio-political reorganization of diverse multi-ethnic population in the newly emerged urban states of the Bronze Age seems to have fueled the trend of turning music performance into the exhibition of prestige. States and cities competed for having the most technically advanced and educated musicians who had to display their skills regularly in mass-scale celebration events.

This trend was most obvious in the rapid boom of orchestral music (Marcetteau 2008), not known prior to the Bronze Age (Krispijn 2010). Standardization of pitch supported playing and singing in perfect unison across different types of voices and musical instruments. Similar contemporaneous developments characterized other regions in the world, including those very remote from Mesopotamia, such as China and India, suggesting that the rise of new standards was not an isolated cultural achievement but a generic evolutionary stage in the global development of music (Nikolsky 2016a).

New music stood in opposition to the previous forms of music that were based on folk transmission of local ethnic traditions. The overview of the huge stock of the available ancient sources leaves no doubt

that for absolute majority of writers the older folk forms of music appeared insignificant and unworthy of attention – even those forms that were practiced by their own people and were popular amongst commoners, e.g., Homeric tradition of rhapsode’s epic singing (West 1981). Music that did not meet the standards of rational harmony was usually viewed as uncivilized, “barbaric” and “raw”, calling for “correction” and cultivation according to the rules of “legitimate” music theory (Nikolsky 2016d).

- In a word, this was the opposition of a new universal fixed music system endorsed by the *state* to the old unfixed *ethnic* music systems, where the former tried to reorganize the latter in order to bring them in agreement with the new official rules. Technically speaking, the *modal* melodic principles of tonal organization were over-ruled by the newly postulated harmonic principles of tuning, leading to the cross-cultural adoption of a new form of tonal organization – *diatony*, based on the mathematically verified “circle of 5ths” (Crickmore 2014). Eventually, this reform resulted in the institution of the diatonic heptatonic 8-mode music system across most of Western and Central Eurasia (Werner 1948) and the invention of musical *keys* and *tonality* (Dahlhaus 2014). This is the reason why earlier folk modal forms of music were viewed as a raw material to be “properly” arranged and cultivated (Nikolsky 2016d).
- Similar process took place in the domain of fine arts, where the rise of first Bronze Age civilizations was marked by the emergence of prescriptive canons of representation of perceptual reality, administered within temple and palace cultures by priests and state officials, and rendered by professional craftsmen (Winter 2010). Similar to music, earlier ethnic traditions of fine art were discarded, and all attention went towards appreciation and adoration of new canonic forms of depiction. The latter became synonymous with the authority of the state, inspiring the interstate competition in the realism of pictorial representations, since such realism supported cross-cultural comparison of art objects across linguistic and cultural borders (Hauser 1999).

In structural terms, new music differed from the earlier folk ethnic models by avoiding formulaic repetitions of the same tune in favor of diversity of motifs and their improvisatorial development. Nearly all survived notations of Ancient Greek music feature non-formulaic and non-repetitive “unveiling” chain of motifs – even the survived notation of choirs – with frequent modulations and chromatic alterations (Pohlman and West 2001). Ancient Greeks, starting from the Classic period, clearly appreciated originality in artistic expression, most evident in the abundant musical competitions and the practice of paying (sometimes, hefty sums of money) for listening to what was considered a masterpiece back then (Nikolsky 2016c). In contrast, folk traditions of Eurasia are characterized by formulaic structure, appreciation of traditionality and disrespect for commercialism (Zemtsovsky 1987).

Here we come to a very important distinction that separates the prehistoric and historic periods, as well as the folk and math-based traditions. The cultural transmission in folk forms of music that are based on modality is set in such a way that promotes the “beauty-in-averageness effect”. Thus, morphing of photographic mug-shots is known to generate the most likeable facial images by cancelling out idiosyncratic features and emphasizing the average ones (Langlois and Roggman 1990).

The underlying reason for liking is the ease of processing the information – we tend to like that which we can do fluently and dislike that which demands cognitive effort (Winkielman et al. 2006). Attractiveness of averaging is not limited to faces (Halberstadt 2006). Morphing of pitch and timbre seems to follow suit (Bruckert et al. 2010). So, a folk song becomes “averaged” through multiple acts of oral transmission from person to person, when each receiver relies on his attention and memory to capture the melody. Inevitably, he notices and remembers those traits that he already knows. As a result, every new round of transmission adapts the melody to better suit conventional popular models.

There is experimental evidence that a multiple chain of transmissions has power to dramatically alter the tonal organization in a melody – to the extent that the chromatic original becomes diatonic at the end of a chain (Lumaca and Baggio 2017). Similar radical transformations are reported by ethnomusicologists, especially noticeable when a song, created in a music culture with one intervallic typology, becomes

imported by another culture with different intervallic typology: e.g., Russian diatonic song in a minor key becomes anhemitonic pentatonic after its distribution amongst the indigenous population of Buryatia (Alekseyev, 1986, p. 148–55). In essence, orally transmitted songs behave very similar to genes – multiple rounds of transmission generate random mutations, of which the variants that match a given cultural environment and human needs the most survive, whereas other variants go extinct (Jan 2018).

This situation becomes radically changed in a music culture that values originality and where music is distributed through notation. Likeability here is traded for originality. Notation preserves the intervallic structure, while aesthetic appreciation encourages production and reproduction of the idiosyncratic musical traits that secure the conservation of authorship. Both tendencies are very pronounced in Ancient Greek music and can be traced back to earlier Mesopotamian cultures (Nikolsky 2016c). However, the authored melodies, composed in quest for originality and demonstration of craftsmanship, are deprived of the beauty-in-averageness effect.

Practice of performance under supervision of a musical administrator in a Mesopotamian temple or palace (Michalowski 2006a) limited performer's creativity too much for the averaging effect to occur. Hence, the idiosyncratic traits were likely to make palace and temple music more manneristic and artificial than popular folk melodies. Adherence to canonic rules, royal tastes and new ideology replaced the likeability. Music turned into a political tool to serve the state in consolidating its citizens against external enemies, implanting the germs of nationalism and triggering the international competition for prestige and power.

The quest for originality had a pronounced influence on music texture. Modal foundation of folk music made its texture fundamentally melodic, i.e., “linear” or *horizontal*: folk monophony, heterophony, polyphony, and homophony all tend to engage melodically fluid parts that would “dress” a principal melody in a way that would enhance its appearance the most. Math-based music systems introduced the explicit *vertical* aspect of tonal organization by putting in place harmonic rules that offset and even subordinated the melodic organization – melodies were to be conceived in terms of the axiomatic rational interval classes.

Music theory postulated rules for arrangement of music based on extra-musical concerns for religious (e.g., Apollonian versus Dionysian music), cosmological (the Pythagorean concept of “music of the spheres”), social (the concept of ethos) and political reasons (nationalism, e.g., advocacy of Dorian mode as a genuine “Greek” mode by Greek authorities). As a result, music textures increased their complexity and diversity to the extent of surpassing the ability of an average layperson to perceive and interpret changes in the organization of the parts.

One of the first manifestations of growing complexity was the differentiation of parts based on their textural functions. The increase in stereotypicity of tonal organization due to standardization of intervals was compensated by the specialization of parts, discovered through the experimentation with *orchestral* music. The latter was invented at Mesopotamian courts in the 3rd millennium BC and became quickly adopted by neighboring states (Nikolsky 2016d). This music radically must have transformed the heterophonic texture that is most typical for folk music by making heterophony *functional*. The discrepancies between vocal and instrumental techniques of sound production, as well as the differences between instrumental families caused timbral, dynamic and textural differentiation between parts.

Thus, blowing in a wind instrument and singing both sustain a pitch level, whereas plucking a string does not, instead requiring a performer to keep repeating a tone in short rhythms in order to match a simultaneous long-sustained tone by a vocalist or a flute. Another point of difference is that the textural parts of wind instruments are more salient than string instruments due to the greater intensity of pneumatic sound production. Reed instruments (e.g., oboe) are generally more salient than edge-blown instruments (e.g., flute), because their nasal timbre appears sharper and more “pointed” than “fluffy” edge-blowing sound. Low wind players have to take breath more frequently than high wind players,

which makes the phrasing of the former more salient. Similar differences are produced by contrasts in numerosity: e.g., a good soloist stands out against a choir, even when they sing in unison.

The larger the ensemble, the greater the accumulation of differences. And although we cannot reconstruct the sound of Ancient Sumerian or Egyptian orchestras, we can get an idea of their heterophony by listening to the sound of orchestras in the Arabo-Andalusian tradition that inherited the music theory from Ancient Greeks.

22. Audio: A fragment of an *Andalusian Nouba*. This is the advanced “orchestral” implementation of the heterophonic texture by a large ensemble of singers and instrumentalists who all play the same melody in slightly different ways that happen to be more comfortable for their musical instruments or voices. The rhythmic accompaniment presents a pitchless counterpoint. The entire texture sounds by far thicker and richer than mesotonal or multitonal heterophony in the Ex.16. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 22\]](#)

Of course, the *Nouba* above represents much later historical development and more advanced tonal organization than music of Ancient Greeks (Davis 2004). The latter was more modest, based on the model of simple *monody* – i.e., originally, an ode in Greek tragedy sung by a solo singer to his own accompaniment on a string instrument, later conceptualized as a special type of music texture, where an expressive melody is supported by some basic figurative accompaniment (Palisca 1960).

The principal difference between homophony and monody is that homophonic parts are usually integrated into a homogenized whole (e.g., singing in “barbershop harmony”), where the succession of chords (actual or implied) constitutes the primary means of unveiling a music form. Monody, in contrast, is based on the semantic and structural opposition between the “expressive” melody and the “unexpressive” accompaniment, and usually engages melodically fluent material rather than strict chordal “strums.” Hellenic monody was characterized by simple figurative accompaniment (West 1992).

Hellenic monody significantly differed from traditional forms of folk monophony, heterophony and polyphony. The earliest notation of an entire Greek composition is the diatonic “*Epitaph of Seikilos*”, probably composed in observation of the rules of music theory of the day (Mathiesen, 1999, p. 150).

23. Audio: *Epitaph of Seikilos*, 1st century AD. Ancient Greek Phrygian diatonic tonos (the intervallic structure coincides with our modern Dorian E Minor). The entire melody possesses a single pattern of a single motif repetition (“rhyming” endings of lines Nos. 3-4). The rest of the melody consists of a string of ongoing unveiling of new thematic material (i.e., the motifs are arranged as “a->b->c->d... etc.”). Combined with the abundance of leaps and changes in direction, the composition testifies of high esteem for originality by Ancient Greeks (Solomon 1986). The texture in this audio features at first a 2-part aulos, and thereafter a vocal part supported by the plucked repetitions of anchor tones. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 23\]](#)

The fine art’s counterpart for the emergence of theory of vertical harmony in music and functional layering of parts was the canonization of pictorial compositional rules, most famous in Ancient Egyptian art. Let us review its principal innovations.

Image 13. *Ostrich Palette*, Hierakonpolis, Egypt c.3100 BC, pre-canonic art. Pictographic representation iconically imitates the appearance of real-life objects while referring to what was known about them - in a rather free and disorganized manner of filling up the available pictorial space with the constituent images (Rauschenbach 1980, 30).

Image 14. *Narmer Palette*, Hierakonpolis, Egypt c.3000 BC. Canonic art. Just a century later after Image 13, these palettes demonstrate clear hierarchic organization by breaking the entire pictorial space into 3-4 registers and differentiating between the constituent images in each register by making more important images larger in size.

It took about a century for the canonic iconography to elaborate a uniform code that governed Egyptian art for over 2,000 years until the Hellenic times. The canon was based on 3 main principles:

- 1) division of space into registers according to a hierarchic scale to indicate relative importance of the constituent images (more important registers are larger),
- 2) alignment of the constituent images in each register by their baseline, and
- 3) prevalence of frontal view for each of the constituent images (Davis 1992, 1).

All three come amazingly close to tonal organization of musical texture. A musical work also occupies a range of “tonal space”: the totality of musical tones that a work engages form a so-called “ambitus” – the compass from the lowest to the highest tones. This ambitus is broken into registers, distinguished by timbral coloration and contrasts. For monophonic music, the acoustic properties of sound generation on a particular musical instrument or a type of vocals determine the registers. Thus, clarinet has 4 registers: somber “chalumeau” (E4-E5), dull “transition” (E5-B5), bright “clarino” (B5-C7), and piercing “altissimo” (C7-A7), all timbrally contrasting each other (Miller 2014). Different types of vocals, as a rule, contain 3-4 registers (Titze 1988). For multi-part music, registers are usually associated with specific musical instruments and types of vocals, still distinguished primarily by timbral differences (Nazaikinsky 1972).

In the ensemble music, parts are aligned by their registral ranges, forming groups: treble, medium and bass - most obvious in the layout of an orchestral score (Banshchikov 1997). The breaking points between these orchestral registers can easily be envisaged as a division executed in reference to the “baseline” – the lowest tone performable by an orchestral group.

Finally, the imperative frontal view in pictorial images can be equated to the prevalence of melodic organization, aka, the “linear” manner of exposure of the musical material for each of the constituent parts in a musical texture. The frontal orientation in pictures exposes an image in its “face value” – all expressive idiosyncratic traits are visible to a viewer like an act of witnessing in real life. The linear exposure of a melody in music achieves a similar task by exposing all expressive idiosyncratic traits in a succession of tones of that melody. After all, a melody in music works much like a face in a picture in conveying the characteristic semantic features of a chosen protagonist (Woloszyn and Ewert 2012).

Egyptian pictorial canon can be compared to the Babylonian music system that was based on Sumerian music theory, contemporaneous to Egyptian Old Dynasty. The documents, uncovered by archaeologists and deciphered by cuneiform specialists, provide enough insight into Mesopotamian music systems to generalize their basic principles of tonal organization (Dumbrill 2005). The first documented evidence of tonal organization comes from the cuneiform notation of the Hurrian Hymns, and the related texts, uncovered at Ugarit in Syria ca. 1,400 BC.

It should be noted that, unlike the verbal scripts, the deciphering of Hurrian notation is currently not fully agreed upon by the specialists. Kilmer's dyadic method of interpretation (Kilmer 1974) has earned much media attention but was rejected by most specialists.⁴ A number of newer reconstructions of the Hurrian Hymn No.6 – the only notation of Babylonian music that survived in its entirety – have been published

⁴ In the context of what we know of the surviving Mediterranean music systems, Kilmer's model of strict 2-part syllabic counterpoint without a single monophonic tone looks highly improbable (West 1994). Furthermore, following her interpretation of notation rules, vocal melody cannot possess a compass wider than a 5th, which appears to be an obvious misnomer for a *heptatony* (ibid.), which Hurrian music system was definitely based upon (Dumbrill 2007). Finally, Kilmer's transcription of a Hurrian hymn contains a tritone that is supposed to have been avoided, according to the music treatises of the time (Dumbrill 2005).

(Duchesne-Guillemin 1984, West 1994, Dumbrill 1998, Mirelman and Krispijn 2009). Below are the YouTube links for 3 transcriptions:

- Transcription by Kilmer (1974), criticized by West (1994). [\[See Supplementary Audio Files\]](#)
- Transcription by West (1993), criticized by Crocker (1997), but convincingly rebutted by Gurney and West (1998). [\[See Supplementary Audio Files\]](#)
- Transcription by Dumbrill (1998). [\[See Supplementary Audio Files\]](#)

Although these transcriptions differ substantially in their melodic structures, what remains in common between all of them is the use of octave-equivalent diatonic heptatonic modes⁵ whose mathematically inferred tuning provides standards for all forms of vocal and instrumental music - plus the practice of fixing an entire musical composition in a notation format. Hymn No.6 and the survived fragments of the other hymns demonstrate that Babylonians did fine-tune a musical instrument to accompany the vocal part, which confirms the existence of the monodic music texture, and that they observed harmonic unity to the extent of conceptualizing modulation to a relative key (Hagel 2005). Babylonians also knew the circle of 5^{ths} and named their 7 modes after a particular series of 5^{ths} that were used to generate each of these modes (Kilmer & Tinney 1996).

So, returning to the issue of 3 rules of the first Egyptian depiction canon, we indeed can draw some parallels with the rules of Babylonian tonal organization. It is unfortunate that we neither know nearly as much about the Mesopotamian pictorial canons contemporaneous to the Egyptian one, nor about the music theory of Ancient Egypt. However, comparing Egypt to Mesopotamia does make sense, because there is abundant historic evidence of intensive cultural borrowing by Mesopotamian artists from their Egyptian colleagues (Winter 2010) and by Egyptian musicians borrowing from Mesopotamia (Duchesne-Guillemin 1981), especially in the realm of orchestral music, in particular, string instruments (Emerit 2013).

- 1) **Division of pictorial space into registers according to a hierarchic proportional scale** finds analogy in division of the entire ambitus of performable “legitimate” music tones into two symmetrical registers with the axis of symmetry falling on the pitch class that corresponded to our “D”. According to the UET-VII-126 tablet, the tuning of the open strings (pitum) was G-A-B-C-D-E-F-G-A, where the same interval set (tone+tone+semitone+tone+tone+semitone) was reproduced from “D” both, up and down (Crickmore 2009).⁶ This tuning, traceable to the 18th century BC (Friberg 2011), likely descended from earlier times, perhaps from the tuning of the legendary Lyre of Ur, c. 26th century BC (Rowan 2013), concurrent with the Old Kingdom. The accurate reproduction of the same interval set, as well as with the positioning of the undesirable interval of tritone B-F symmetrically around the central “D” act similar to pictorial scaling. The resultant scale is equivalent to our Mixolydian major (Rahn 2011) that is known for the best camouflaging of the tritone of all “classic” diatonic modes (Kushnaryov 1958, 314).
- 2) **Alignment of the pictorial images in each register by their baseline** finds analogy in referencing each pitch class to the “D” and in the technical procedure of tuning prior to performance, where one pitch class is inferred from another pitch class by building a perfect 5th

⁵ I have to mention that the term “musical mode” is a modern-day concept applied backwards in time to address the tonal coherence of a set of tones (pitch classes) selected as the formative basis for music-making. Mesopotamian texts do not contain terms translatable as “mode”, instead speaking of “tuning” – which, however, implies “re-tuning” from one pitch set to another in order to perform a new piece of music (Mirelman & Krispijn 2009). The underlying idea of a set of pitch classes united around some focal class and associated with a certain expression justifies the application of the modern term “mode (West 1994).

⁶ It does not matter for drawing these conclusions that we do not have a reliable transcription of Babylonian music. Melodies, created in the UET-VII-126 tonal system, were likely to inherit its hierarchic and registral organization, since they were observed and followed by music-makers.

up and then inverting it an octave lower in order to build the next 5th. Although Babylonians did not have a word for “octave,” they had words for all smaller intervals – which suggests that octave did not bear any melodic or harmonic function, and was reserved for the tuning procedure alone. So, octave equivalence must have been regularly used before every performance (Kilmer 1984). The deciding role in mode formation was given to tritone – it had to be avoided at all costs between the adjacent tones in a composition. Just as sexagesimal division was adopted internationally for measurements of degrees and time, Babylonian tuning cycle came to serve as an international standard for tonal organization in many music systems – akin to the Ancient form of “equal temperament” (Franklin 2007).

- 3) **Prevalence of frontal view for each of the pictorial images** finds analogy in the unchallenged dominance of monodic melodic texture in nearly all known traditions of the Middle East, which has become its trademark. All Ancient sources point at the monodic melody as the foundation for the musical thinking of this entire region. Just like the frontal orientation of a pictorial image secured the recognition of semantic properties of facial features and posture of depicted figures, melodic orientation of Ancient music secured the recognition of semantic properties of melodic intervals, motifs, phrases and musical modes – exemplified in the Ancient doctrine of “ethos” that matched specific modal structures of music to specific affective states (Nikolsky 2016c).

Both canons, pictorial and musical, apply a coherent set of rational rules to the repertory of compositional elements, in effect establishing a “mega-form” for expression of every type of culturally important content. Convenience of reserving a single universal scheme for every new composition of art and music explains amazing longevity of ancient canons. Egyptian canon represented a default method of *orthogonal projection* of 3D objects onto a 2D plane – it was still preferred to more advanced forms of perspectival representation, despite the latter being known to Egyptian artists at least from the 15th century BC (Arnheim 1954, 75).

Such stability had to do with the persistent adherence to the “abstract rationalism” of thinking (Hauser 1999a, 1:23): i.e., aprioristic orthogonal projection provided stricter and more stereotypical manner of ordering in comparison to empirical angular projections. The former imposes a single objective criterion, producing the same result for every artist, whereas the latter must comply to multiple variable conditions, peculiar to different artists. The Ancients definitely preferred uniformity of expression, which most likely stemmed from their love for planning and pre-planning.

Egyptian canonic art was the first school of pictorial representation that operated by means of *geometric drafting*: an artist planned his composition in advance by securing the “correct” proportions and angles between the drawn figures (Lawlor 1982, 54). Mathematically verified pictorial composition served the same purpose as mathematically verified musical composition: both were seen as obtaining a supernatural power through expression of divinized numerical proportions.

In Egyptian iconography, gnomon (a sundial) and square were attributes of the chief deity, Osiris (ibid, p.72). In Sumerian iconography, the very symbol of royal authority was a measuring rod and a line, often depicted in a canonic scene of a god handing rod and line to a king (Robson 2007). Ruling subjects in a state was deemed equivalent to employing a “ruler” for correct measurements.

Pre-dynastic Egyptian culture split pictographic representation into two different styles: hieroglyphic and fine art. Hieroglyphic pictographs were reserved for transmission of knowledge about objects, whereas artistic pictograms specialized in capturing the characteristic appearance of real-life objects, where details in appearance had greater importance than the conceptual information about them. This new artistic iconography that set the foundation for the first canon was distinguished by its geometrically rationalized composition.

Image 15. *Two humans with a plow*, Middle Kingdom Egyptian wall painting. This picture is more of a demonstration of how the agricultural work looks like and less of informing about the procedure of plowing. The geometric features of pictorial organization stand out: a 2-tier arrangement, where the upper figures are distributed in strict rhythm of nearly equal spatial intervals and figure width, aligned by an implied straight line of animal legs that runs in parallel to the ground-line of the lower tier.

This brings us to the next crucial issue – the pronounced realistic revolution in the aesthetics of Ancient Egypt and Mesopotamia of the 2nd millennium BC.

Illusionism in Arts and Music

The transition from hieroglyphic to purely pictorial representation occurred in a hierarchic fashion determined by semantic factors. Unimportant objects were stripped off of their informative layer more readily than the important objects: both, Egyptian and Babylonian art, at their earlier stages represented humans schematically in contrast to animal depiction (Hauser 1999a, 1:23). Assyrian art was the first to become interested in realistic depiction of humans: presenting entire battle-scenes as snapshots at a climactic point, with figures captured in motion - unlike the Egyptian schematic “reports” of the Pharaoh’s victory (Groenewegen-Frankfort 1951, 172).

The goal of capturing the appearance eventually led to the emergence of *illusionism* – i.e., such approach to art that aims to represent visual physical traits precisely, based on the mimetic capacities of the expressive means of a particular kind of art. One of the earliest documented artifacts that manifested the novel illusionistic approach were the naturalistic erotic Babylonian reliefs in lead inlays from the decorative insets in the Assyrian elite’s furniture during the Tukulti-Ninurta I reign, the 18th century BC (Assante 2007).

Image 16. *Erotic scene with a couple*, Babylonian terracotta relief, 18th-17th century BC. One of the earliest naturalistic depiction of humans.

This is very close to the time of Hurrian hymns. And the timeframe is not the only commonality that justifies the drawing of parallels between the emerging illusionistic visual art and illusionistic music. Here we have to specify how exactly music can possibly be “illusionistic”.

It is quite common to understand illusionism in visual arts as accurate reproduction of shapes and colors of visible objects as though in an attempt to fool a spectator into mistaking a reproduction for the original. However, such understanding would be rather superficial, since it would not draw a line between photographic and artistic reproductions of reality.

A camera generates much more consistent and detailed reproductions than even the most skillful painter could possibly capture, yet photographic images are generally not considered “illusionistic” by art historians and aestheticians. A crucial point that distinguishes illusionism is its *sensualist* orientation – illusionistic art engages realistic reproduction in order to draw emotional reactions from spectators as though they are witnessing a real-life original rather than its mimetic copy (Florensky 1996). Without this underlying pragmatic goal, an art object would not constitute a sign.

A pictorial image can function as a sign only under the condition that its physical body (aka, “signifier”) is connected to some piece of information (aka, “meaning”, or “signified”) by means of a social convention – mere mechanical reproduction of visible attributes of a real-life object does not constitute a conventional “piece of information”, since mimetic similarity here is obvious and requires neither prior knowledge of a convention, nor interpretation on the part of the spectator (Uspensky 1996). Semantic connotations of sadness, happiness, fear, etc., associated with a certain type of an image – this is what makes a mimetic work by an artist meaningful.

The same affiliation between the “signified” and the “signifier” characterizes music which relies on emotional communication to a greater extent than any other forms of art. Throughout most of music history and across the globe, with very few exceptions, the art of music has been viewed as “a language of feelings”, where musical emotion serves as the primary tool for effective emotional communication (Nikolsky 2015b). Hence, “illusionism” in music is a *deliberate attempt of music-makers to convince the audience that music emotions are “real-life” emotions that are experienced by some fictional protagonists in an imaginary space of music*. The brightest demonstration of such “illusionism” can be found in the genres of musical theater, such as Western opera or ballet, but is not limited to the Western tradition of classical music. Vital indigenous traditions of music theater exist in India, China, Indochina, Korea, Japan and Indonesia – with very ancient roots.

The best documented theatrical tradition of Antiquity is Hellenic tragedy, and it served as a cradle for numerous forms of artistic “illusionism”: Aeschylus established the rules of constructing the dramatic plot, the framework of two actors impersonating the opposing protagonists and the chorus commenting on the circumstances of the action; Aristotle forged the doctrines of mimesis and catharsis that underlay theatrical impersonation; Euclid elaborated the rules of geometry through the art of scenic design called to convince the audience in the reality of a stage action; Euripides wrote highly emotional music to emphasize the affective states experienced by protagonists on stage; yet another innovation was the use of masks to conceal the identity of an actor and allow him to project the psychological state of his

fictional character on the audience (McDonald & Walton 2007). All of these developments contributed to the creation of a theatrical virtual reality, experienced as an alternative to the real life by majority of theatergoers. And once they developed a taste for theatrical shows, Hellenic music supplied them with the “budget” shows (not as expensive as going to a theater) through the institution of new forms of instrumental program music and representational lyric songs that also followed theatrical principles of emotional impersonation of plots and/or fictional characters – the entire development of chromatic and enharmonic genera of tonal organization of Ancient Greek music fulfilled the public demand for dramatic characterization (Nikolsky 2016c).

Certainly, there is a long historic distance from Ancient Greece to Ancient Babylon. However, the ties between Hellenic and Babylonian cultures are quite strong - through Pythagoras (Riedweg 2005) and Plato (Crickmore 2009b) - and include music theory (Hagel 2005, Crickmore 2009a, Friberg 2011), as well as mathematics (Struik 1987). It would be useful to remind that Babylonian proportions were perpetuated in the construction of Parthenon – an object of national pride for Ancient Greeks (Kappraff, 2006). In light of the arguments above, the direct comparison of the first samples of illusionistic Babylonian visual art and Babylonian “realistic” music should not come across as unfounded.

The idea of evoking arousal by accurate topographic reproduction of naked human figures (Image No.16) is not that far from the idea of evoking a state of joy by generating a melody in a musical mode whose ethos was considered joyful. The classic implementation of ethos in Ancient Greek civilization has its roots in Mesopotamia, traceable at least back to Sumerian times (Nikolsky 2016c). Sumerian king Shulgi, 21st c. BC, famous for his musical reforms, was credited with knowing how to instill emotions by means of music: “not only that he knew how to play musical instruments, but he also knew how to cause joy with his music to those around him” (Klein 1981, 16).

The task of generating a particular emotional state in the participants of a religious rite in order to “convince” a particular god in the necessity to act in a way that would be beneficial to them, must have caused some radical reshaping of the pre-existing folk traditions. The extent of this transformation can be seen in the development of the genre of lamentation that occupied the central position in Sumerian culture: from kings to slaves, all casts of society subscribed to the ritual of gaining a favor from deities by complaining of their sufferings (Löhnert 2011). Initially, closely related to the archaic folkloric funeral laments, lamentation quickly acquired its own syntactic and semantic typology, elaborating its own easily recognizable “language” of expression (Cooper 2006). Similar developments must have characterized other genres as well.

In this sense, “composing” a song according to the rules of a legitimized “official” music theory such as Shulgi’s, and conventions of an existing genre, would create the “illusion” of a specific musical emotion. Notably, such illusionism is possible only in the framework of a production cycle of a professional composer (West 1994, 171), hired to convey a certain emotional message – which we know to have taken place already in Sumer. Sumerian culture marks the turning point for the emergence of the market for professionally produced music.

Once in place, the marketplace nurtured competition, branding and name recognition. From the Uruk period onward, Sumerians had 3 words to refer to musicians: generic 'nar,' specific 'šud' for the singer of prayers, and 'šir' for the singer of songs – which was also used to indicate authorship, in the meaning of "a composer" (Krispijn 2010). The best composers were remembered by names: Tapsihuni, Urhiya, Puhiya, and Ammiya (West 1994, 171).

Specialization required expertise from the musicians - to prepare music for a given occasion ahead of time - and their performance could score varying degrees of success, reflected by differences in wages (Ziegler, 2011). By the 18th century BC, there was already an internationally recognized system of accreditation of musicians across the network of courts (*nar*) and temples (*gala*) of the Middle East - with clearly defined promotional ranking from Junior, Senior, to Chief Singer, regular invitation of visiting artists, and frequent relocation and integration of musicians through conquest and interstate gift-

exchange (Franklin 2007). Educated musicians were highly valued across Mesopotamia and neighboring countries, and could easily find employment at palaces and temples, receiving rations, stipends, and land in reward for their service (Ziegler 2011). The surviving accounting records demonstrate that some courts maintained over two hundred professional musicians, temples employed a few dozen musicians on a permanent basis and involved about few hundred performers at specific celebrations.

A big role in estimates of musician's qualifications was played by his knowledge of formal music theory, music genres and musical modes – the combination of which prepared the ground for the emergence of musical ethos. It might have already existed in the 2nd millennium BC. Middle Assyrian tablet VAT 10101 (West, 1994, p. 170) presents a census of Akkadian love-songs, classified by modes (tunings), 3 of which turned out to be by far more common for expression of love. Each of the 7 existing musical modes seems to have been associated with certain affective states through the system of genres, and the job of a professional musician was to turn his audience in the emotional state requested by the palace or temple authorities. His success determined his promotion and salary. So, a professional Sumerian musician found himself in a business of making illusions of real-life emotions. This was not how a folk musician in a village culture carried out his musical occupations.

Folk musicians usually “speak for themselves”, expressing what they actually experience at the moment of performance rather than trying to convince their audiences in the realism of this or that musical emotion – hence, they create the “real thing” and not an “illusion” (Nikolsky 2016c).

The task of musically evoking the state of joy by exposing the listener of Hurrian Hymn 6 to the intervals of the *qablite* mode (D-E-F-G-A-B-C-D-E) (Dumbrill 1998, 142), associated with the *qablite* ethos (Dumbrill 1998, 131) can be regarded as a form of “illusionism” (listen to Ex.24 below), not that different from Babylonian terracotta reliefs. In both cases, emotional reactions are primed by conventional signifiers: a configuration of contour lines on a 2D surface, and the interval set of a melodic line.

24. Audio: Hurrian Hymn No.6, the reconstruction by West (1994). [[See Supplementary Audio File 24](#)]

3D Representation and Functional Differentiation within the Parameter of Depth

Babylonian pictorial illusionism still was far from the linear perspective. An artist reproduced a scenery not from a single fixed vantage point but through the series of glances in a point-by-point manner while moving along the frontal baseline, adding some “finishing touches” to integrate the pictorial objects at the end of sketching. Such method of depiction, conceptualized as “portraiture” – i.e., the image that highlights the most representative features of some real object and is supposed to be judged in relation to its faithfulness to the original – was already in place in the early 1st millennium BC, in Assyria (Winter 2009, 1:83).

The principal method of pictorial composition was the realistic reproduction of a frontal close-up view that encompassed all the important neighboring objects in the foreground (Rauschenbach 2002, 187). This integration contrasted the earlier methods of naturalistic depiction that characterized Paleolithic cave art. There, different figures were rarely united in an ensemble, instead, artists pursued the goal to capture a single object in motion that was most characteristic to it (Okladnikov 1967, 117). Throughout the Stone Age, naturalistic treatment was applied to animals rather than humans, probably because animals were more important for human survival than other humans (ibid., p.105). It took about 5,000 years between the end of the Paleolithic and the origin of a science-driven agricultural civilizations to depart from the emblematic principles of representation of humans and develop an interest in capturing the depth aspect (Frolov 1992, 69).

Image 17. *Sennacherib receiving the submission of Jews.* Sennacherib's Court 6 at Nineveh. Canonic implementation of bird's eye perspective.

The seeds of 3D representation were forged during the 1st dynasty of the New Kingdom in Egypt (1550-1292 BC) and highlighted in later Assyrian art (900-700 BC). We can list the following new traits of compositional organization:

- 1) animal and human figures were spread out across the entirety of the available space, not standing on the same baseline, but still often arranged by registers (Aruz, et al. 2014, 55);
- 2) distant objects were masked by the closer ones; or
- 3) placed in higher registers - to form "ranks" in a bird's-eye view (Russell 1987).
- 4) the difference in scaling between close and distant figures is present in the reliefs at Ashurnasirpal Palace, anticipating later *aerial perspective* (Flittner 1958, 249).

Image 18. *Siege of the city.* Palace of King Ashurnasirpal II. Rough scaling, suggestive of aerial perspective.

The musical analogs of these 4 traits would be:

- 1) uniformed diatonic distribution of pitch classes, degrees and interval classes in a musical mode, verified mathematically rather than being defined linearly “by ear” per each melodic motif (as in earlier forms of folk music, according to the taste of a music-maker);
- 2) differentiation within the music texture between a melody in the foreground and the supporting instrumental parts in the background, where melody generally masked the accompaniment;
- 3) the arrangement of the accompanying parts to fill up the available orchestral ambitus more-or-less evenly by assigning a dedicated register to each instrument, to keep it audible;
- 4) the expressive enhancement of the leading melody (e.g., chromatic alteration, embellishments, portamento, etc.) was reserved for the melodic part(s) and not for the accompanying part(s).

Although we can only fantasize the sound of Babylonian and Assyrian music textures, the presence of 1) is confirmed by the survived documents on music theory. The validity of 2)-4) is supported by the common cross-cultural practices of ensemble music, reported by ethnomusicologists and historians of Western classical music, and by the psychoacoustic requirements for successful collective performance in an instrumental ensemble.

We know that playing the same melody together “in tune”, in agreement with the cosmological rules (Nikolsky 2016c), was the preferable manner of performance in Antiquity. The sacral status of music, closely supervised by professional administrators (Ziegler 2011), together with the existence of notated references for the core music repertoire (Michalowski 2010) must have effectively reduced the share of discrepancies, flattening the melody close to perfect monophony.

In such conditions, each instrument would have to be necessarily placed into a different register in order for a performer to be able to hear his own part (Patterson et al. 2010) and make sure that no mistakes were made. This was super-important, since mistakes in perfect intervallic ratios were viewed as a potential threat to undermine the “harmony of the spheres”, and thereby, compromise the world order (Nikolsky 2016c).

Finally, the practice of making a foreground melody more salient by injecting slight variations in timbre and pitch where melodic motifs allow – in contrast to the meagerness of the supporting background parts - is widespread across different music cultures. The underlying reason for such treatment must be the instinct to emphasize the familiar expressive elements in a part that is viewed as a primary carrier of expression in a music work (e.g., sharpen the ascending intonation, flatten the descending one, place an embellishment on the climactic tone in a melodic phrase, connect both tones in a climactic intonation by a glide, etc.).

Ancient Greek music texture probably was initially similar to the Assyrian texture – so as the spatial organization in the very first samples of the Greek landscapes looked about as flat as the Assyrian ones.

But by time, Greek art developed hierarchic representation of depth, and Greek music became most certainly more heterophonic because of the wide spread of public music education and the growing popularity of music competitions – which promoted the technical advance in woodwind, string, and vocal performances. At some point, masters of musical instruments must have felt the urge to take advantage of their expressive skills and started enhancing their accompanying parts in a way analogous to the performer of a principal melody yet complementary to their musical instrument. Eventually, all parts in a texture were likely to accumulate enough discrepancies to thicken the texture.

Image 19. Mural in the *Tomb of the Diver*, Paestum, Italy, 5th century BC (Holloway 2006). Very flat landscape, reduced to bare visual contours.

There is evidence that harmonic (vertical) intervals were familiar to Ancient Greeks. The “*Book of Problems*” by pseudo-Aristotle contains eleven references to vertical intervals in discussion of various “problems” in harmony (Spiess 1959) – a sure indication of at least the occasional use of vertical harmony in musical practice. The absence of guidelines in treatises of contemporaneous music theory must have left a practitioner clueless as to how to regulate vertical intervals, hence, prompting pseudo-Aristotle to address this issue as a “problem”.

Two other popular ancient treatises contained references to the use of harmonic intervals in music: Plutarch’s “On Music” and Plato’s “Athenian Stranger.” Both references suggested that patterns of instrumental accompaniment to vocal singing was initially simple monophonic (during the Archaic period and earlier), but gradually became complex, possibly including the usage of 2 simultaneous tones of instrumental accompaniment on lyre or harp per 1 vocal tone, plus occasional insertion of instrumental passages in the accompaniment (Mathiesen 1999, 361–2).

Andrew Barker (1995) sums up all the available evidence to build a case for multipart heterophonic accompaniment in Greek musical practice from its earliest times throughout its history. According to his conclusions, it seems that the heterophonic variants of the principal melody were regarded by Greeks not as random deviations but as executing a particular function towards the principal melody.

The practice of dubbing of vocal melody was regarded as a peculiar expressive device in its own right. Thus, Diogenes of Babylon, 2nd century BC, reported that “the hymns sung in Ephesus and by the choruses in Sparta were more impressive because accompaniment was added and so showed the power of music to move us” (Ferguson 2003, 399). Larger ensembles could have included a drone tone (known as “ison” in later Byzantine music theory) as a point of modal reference for all participants (Daniélou 1995, 15). And we know that the tradition of Byzantine plainchant had Ancient Greek roots, descending from Greek-speaking monastic communities in Palestine (Jeffery 2001).

The invention of a drone pedal might have been prompted not by cultural but by psycho-acoustic factors. Greek choral festivals often reached monumental scale of up to 600 singers (West 1992, 41). Ensembles

of this size would have failed to deliver well-tuned melodic intervals (especially for melodic leaps) without providing a harmonic reference for every participant in form of a drone. On the other hand, the placement of a drone in the bass part would have made it easier for the audience to habituate to a non-melodic tone and, therefore, ignore its presence, focusing instead on the melodically important parts (Ahmedaja 2011).

The ison in Orthodox plainchants of Eastern Europe comprised an organic part in the performance ensemble, determined by the modal structure of the chant, and therefore not notated. However, according to modern practitioners of Byzantine chant, “ison” is more than a single “tone” that underlines a tonic of a musical mode: often, ison changes its position in pitch and moves within a music work, being regarded by performers as a discrete melodic entity, *added* to the principal melody of the chant (Koço 2013). The same applies to heterophonic textures of folk cultures in the Balkan region, probably influenced by the ecclesiastic music (Koço 2015).

25. Audio: St. John Chrysostom - *Axion Esti*, Marian hymn of praise, 4th c. AD. The melodic line receives support of a drone tone that is occasionally moved in pitch to “tune in” for singing in a new tetrachord – such practice, found in today’s Greek and Syriac churches, is likely to have originated much earlier, conserved by some sacral tradition. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 25\]](#)

There is no reason why heterophonic structures similar to ison could not have evolved in the practice of instrumental ensemble accompaniment of Ancient Greeks and Ancient Romans. After all, there is evidence of usage of purely instrumental bands (without vocals) in military Ancient Greek music (Franklin 2008) and in public funeral rites (Bogdanov 2007).⁷

The largest festive choir settings (West 1992, 41) were likely to have produced organum-like dubs in parallel 4ths and 5ths. Such dubs are known to occur spontaneously in choral performance whenever the high- and low-range vocals of musically untrained singers are used along each other (Tallmadge 1984). Once discovered in vocal music, such organum-like arrangement could have earned its place in instrumental music. Organum-like textures are still observed today in folk instrumental music of Pontiac Greeks who most frequently use progressions of parallel 4ths and drone tones in playing lira (Ahrens 1973). Parts in such textures are usually differentiated enough to carry one of 4 functions:

1. **Carrying** the melody – featuring the richest share of expressive details (e.g., embellishments, slides, timbral recolorations, etc.);
2. **Grounding** the melody – emphasizing the anchor tones while skipping some passing tones;
3. **Thickening** the melody – dubbing the melody in unison, octave or some other parallel intervals;
4. Providing the **harmonic reference** for parts – sustaining the drone tone(s).

If a comparatively similar number of performers would play a typical Western classical homophonic texture (e.g., a chorale) versus a heterophonic texture differentiated in 4 abovementioned layers, the latter would sound substantially thinner than the former. However, such *functional heterophony* would produce a richer texture than the non-functional folk heterophony (compare Audio Examples 8 and 25).

In the same vein, the first survived samples of Classic Greek murals demonstrate significantly more detailed “functional” representation of a group of 3D objects onto the 2D surface, executed in a realistic

⁷ The 4th century BC fresco was discovered in 1842 in Kerch catacombs (Ashik 1845) and subsequently destroyed. Ashik provided a thorough verbal description of this fresco. It depicted a funeral procession accompanied by a joined performance of two separate groups of musicians: 1) two trumpets with a pan flute and 2) four trumpets. It is highly unlikely for these seven instruments to have played in perfect unison at all times. The division into two groups strongly suggests a textural differentiation of some kind (e.g., in a form of a responsorial or a simultaneous dubbing in different registers).

style, as compared to the Assyrian art. What is responsible for greater realistic impression is the arrangement of constituent images within a composition according to the function of their prototypes in real life – i.e., functions of “parts” here closely correspond to functions of their real-life models.

For this reason, Greek “illusionism” surpassed Assyrian by a margin. Pre-Greek artists merely “reported” on certain notable events in their works, caring to choose such compositional arrangement and such attributes of compositional objects that would characterize their prototypes in real life in general, at all times rather than at the current moment of depiction (e.g., plowing in Image 15). This caused a great deal of schematization in pictorial representation. Artists documented the totality of what they knew about an event, including its causes and consequences.

Image 20. *Hades abducting Persephone*, Vergina Tombs, a royal Macedonian burial complex, 4th c. BC. Realistic organization of all 4 objects in an ensemble with the pronounced depth parameter in the center, stressing the most dramatic part of the composition. The depiction of a wheel reflects the capacity of a wheel in a cart to propel its motion – in contrast to the figure of Persephone who tries to resist the motion.

Greek artists, from Hellenic times on, sought to represent a particular person or a particular event “as is” at the moment of happening – to capture its “momentum” in order to stir the viewer emotionally. This posed the task that Assyrian artists did not have to face: to choose the right moment in the unveiling of an event, a moment that would serve the best to represent the essence of what was depicted. Hence, Greek illusionism obtained a strong theatrical flavor. In Hellenistic theater, it was paramount to convince the audience in “reality” of the enactment to make it respond to the stage action emotionally as though it was a real-life event rather than its reproduction.

Hellenistic musicians had a similar task at their hands, having to make the listeners “feel” the song’s lyrics or the stories suggested by the title of the instrumental music (Power 2013). To be able to tell stories through music they had to introduce an arsenal of chromatic shades (Nikolsky 2016c) – very much like their fellow-artists who discovered the expressive use of a shadow.

Advances in enharmonic and chromatic music around the 5th century BC coincided with the invention of “architectural painting” that employed perspectival images for home interior decorations and for theatrical scenography. Thus, Apollodorus was nicknamed by Plutarch “the shadow painter” for his invention of a shading technique (Little 1971, 1–10). Foreshortening of closer objects by means of placing extra shades in the foreground works quite similarly to the addition of chromatic “shades” to the pitch values of the *pyknon* degrees in tetrachords of a leading vocal melody to make it more expressive (Franklin 2005). *Pyknon* [literally, “close-packed” or “condensed”] was the term in Ancient Greek music theory for 2 smaller intervals formed between the “pinch” of 3 closely spaced degrees at the bottom of a tetrachord whose sum of the intervallic values was less than the size of an interval at the top of that tetrachord (Solomon 1984).

The notion of *pyknon* was crucial for distinguishing between the diatonic genera (that did not have *pyknon*) and the chromatic and enharmonic genera of the same tetrachord. Yet another important distinction was that the *pyknon* degrees were “movable” – i.e., altered whenever a genus of the tetrachord was changed – whereas the upper degree in a tetrachord was “standing” – i.e., it provided a stable anchor tone for a musical mode (Mathiesen 1999). In a word, alteration of the *pyknon* degrees in a principal vocal part while keeping the accompanying parts diatonic (or altered in a way that was different from the melody) would have thickened a musical texture by exposing the discrepancies in tonal organization of its parts.

Image 21. *Seated woman playing a kithara*, from Room H of the Villa of Fannius Synistor at Boscoreale, ca. 40 BC. Use of shading for 3D effect. [\[See Supplementary Audio Files\]](#)

This “foreshortening” effect constitutes something different from perspectival organization, as evident in the example above: the legs of a chair do not match the angle suggested by the shading of a sitting figure. Shadows, cast by the sun, form orthogonal projections - in contrast to a central projection required by representation of 3D objects on a 2D plane. In Greek tradition, these two projections were never integrated, each possessing its own axis. Foreshortening of one object had little bearing on the foreshortening of another proximal object in pictorial composition (Ivins 1964, 32–33). By contrast, scaling of pictorial objects, adjacent in their depth parameter, was usually quite consistent in preserving the principle of reduction in size by increase of depicted distance.

Image 22. *Laestrygonians preparing for the battle*, The Odyssey Landscapes, from the Esquiline Hill in Rome, 1st c. BC. The composition features not entirely consistent shadow casting and shading, while quite consistent scaling.

Similarly, chromatic alteration in music should be thought of as an expressive device that is autonomous from the expression of a musical texture. Multiple parts create a sense of relative “thickness” in music, whereas use of chromatic shades evokes an effect related to lighting – in a way, highlighting the intervallic makeup of a melodic line. Numerosity of parts is not the same as intervallic structuring.

- Differentiation of parts in heterophony reflects the *vertical* aspect of harmonization and corresponds to *scaling* in pictorial composition.
- Chromatic shading of diatonic degrees reflects the *horizontal* aspect of harmonization and corresponds to *shading* in pictorial composition.

Ancient Greek culture was the first to combine techniques of horizontal and vertical tonal harmony in music with techniques of 3D representation in pictorial composition. All three techniques shared a

common origin in *scenography* (Andersen 2008, 728–730). The sole purpose of scenography was to provide convincing emulation of known real objects in stage design of theatrical plays.

In theater, visual illusions accompanied auditory “illusions” in “aestheticized” reproduction of emotional states familiar to people through everyday life. Stage design “faked” the visual attributes of stimuli primed to trigger certain emotion, while tonal design “faked” their experiential attributes through complex mechanism of priming a particular emotional state by means of a tonal signal, such as a specific intervallic progression (Lippman 1964, 160) whose *harmonia* referenced a particular ethos (Mathiesen 1984). Pseudo-Aristotle lists a number of such “tonal signals”: i.e. Hypodorian mode refers to a magnificent and steadfast character, most suited for kithara song; whereas Hypophrygian mode refers to action, such as military marching, that is appropriate for an actor on stage – however, both modes are inappropriate for the chorus, which generally requires quiet and mournful music (Aristotle and Mayhew 2011, 1:577).

Musical emotions came to provide a histrionic analog to real life emotions. Both scenic representations, visual and auditory, supported each other side by side in a single act-out event, such as an episode of theatrical play.

Although shades of chromaticism and shading in pictures originated in the same civilization, once the pictorial shading technique received life of its own, it followed its own course of development. Thus, Roman architectural painting kept elaborating the shading techniques until they gradually evolved into a perspective system based on a single vanishing point (Little 1971). In contrast, the chromatic and enharmonic genera in Roman music went into near oblivion by the 5th century AD (West, 1992, p. 165).

The Concept of Framing a Composition

Yet another important perceptual concomitant of perspectival organization in fine arts that received its analog in Ancient Greek music theory is the concept of the *frame*: i.e., the presence of some kind of delineation of the virtual 3D space of a picture from the real-life 3D space that surrounds a picture. This is where the semiotic approach of Ancient Greek artists came to differ from that of the earlier civilizations. Greco-Roman tradition of architectural painting pioneered the same principle that later prevailed in Western civilization, from the Renaissance onward – the painter adopted an *exterior position towards the depicted space*. In contrast, the earlier artists, as a rule, favored an *interior* position, as though placing themselves *inside* the depicted virtual reality (Uspensky 1995, 173–181).

Noteworthy are those cases where painters depicted new images superimposed on the pre-existing images (quite common in cave art), as though believing that each of the layered entities enjoyed its immanent existence – disregarding whether or not they blocked each other in relation to the viewer. The reason for such disregard must have been the *equal status assigned to the images and to the viewer*.

The use of the inserted vantage point, evident in Ancient Egyptian and Assyrian landscapes, must have been the remnant of this older tradition. Such landscapes feature clear “*centrifugal*” orientation, where hills and trees on one side of the river are directed up, whereas on the other side – directed down, as if unleashing the energy from the center (Flittner 1958, 260). In effect, such arrangement as though frames an important constituent image within an artwork “from the inside.”

We can infer the meaning of such orientation from its explanation in surviving medieval sources on the Orthodox iconography, which most probably reflects the earlier Byzantine and, possibly, Roman Christian traditions. Something very similar to the centrifugal principle of orientation is described in medieval instructional treatises as the “*in reverse*” principle: the right side of the picture is referred to as “left,” and vice versa, defining each side as a mirror image - from the position opposite to the actual viewer who becomes identified with the “virtual observer” *inside* the virtual depicted space (Uspensky

1995, 254). Reference to the “depth” dimension is treated in the same way: from the point of view of a person placed in the middle of the depicted space (p.299).

Image 23. *Brick making*, from the Rekhmire's Tomb at Thebes, 18th Dynasty (New Kingdom). The pond is depicted from the point of view of a person in the middle of it: with trees on each side of the pond bent away from the center.

This “*interior*” method of orientation by no means is limited to Russian and Byzantine Orthodox canons of iconography: the inverted left/right orientation is found in iconography of the *Final Judgment* of the Catholic Church (saints at the “right” versus sinners at the “left” sides), as well as in the reliefs of Gothic tombs and in Romanesque sculpture (Aleshkovsky 1972, 106, ff15).

The pathway of left/right inversion is traceable to the oldest forms of cartography (Uspensky 1995, 255), and must be related to the same conventions that determined the symbolic use of handprints in the prehistoric rock paintings. The left handprints constitute the overwhelming majority of handprints in Paleolithic cave murals as well as in the modern cave paintings by the Aboriginal population of Australia and by native Indian population of Americas – which are usually interpreted by scholars as a form of signing an artwork by its author whose right hand is busy painting. However, this interpretation is highly doubtful and anachronistic, because indigenous pre-industrial cultures are characterized by syncretic art and by social organization that leaves little space for social hierarchy. Such societies are fundamentally heterarchic, unfamiliar with the notions of individualism and authorship altogether.

A more probable explanation is the usage of the left hand as an orientation cue, called to unlock the entry access from the “dirty” earthly world (left=evil) to the “pure” heavenly world (right=virtuous) (V.V.Ivanov 2014, 4:262–268). Associating the imprint of a painter with that of a virtuous person could have marked a magical connotation, “activating” a supernatural connection to a mythological hero, some deity, or a spirit of the dead (Uspensky 1995, 303). Egyptian canon also related the visual compositional device of *inversion* to the ritual transfer of the newly deceased from the “world of the living” to the “world of the dead,” aka, the *Dwat* (inverted world), expressed in progressions of reciprocal elements (Lawlor 1982, 21).

Iconographic framing also deals with the opposition of two “worlds”: esoteric but austere sacred truth versus common but fictitious pleasant appearance (Florensky 1996). In cases of interior vantage point, the function of framing is to generate contrast between the center (“inside”) and the sides (“outside”),

e.g., by using concave forms in the center and convex forms at the margins of icons (Uspensky 1995, 180), or by depicting the same building from the interior angle at the center of the picture and from the exterior angle at both sides (ibid., p.181).

Image 24. *The Robe of Christ*, from the Kremlin Cathedral of the Dormition, 17th century. The interior at the center is combined with the exterior at the margins of the picture.

The reverse orientation might be interpreted as the product of the inclusive mindset of the pre-perspective artist, eager to tell us what was going on inside the depicted building (contrary to the attitude of an external observer who did not enter the interior space of that building, satisfied by what was visible from the outside).

The *interior* orientation, as a matter of fact, requires a *continuous mediation* between the virtual and the real worlds: the viewer has to mentally keep switching from the view available at his actual observation point and the position of the virtual observer that is implied inside the depicted space (Uspensky 1976, 231).

The ongoing integration of both impressions, experienced through the series of glances from inside and outside, comprises a peculiar “self-contained” concept of space in archaic icons.

The ongoing alternation between two vantage positions also explains why the ancient architectural paintings were often not framed at

all: the peripheral objects in the composition as though prevented a virtual interior observer from “looking out” from the pictorial space in which he was enclosed, so that he could not see the “real world” beyond the “frame-walls” of virtual pictorial space.

The perceptual equivalent for the interior orientation for music would be the ensemble performance setting that is exceedingly typical for folk music, where the singer wraps his melody into the heterophonic or polyphonic texture of his own self-accompaniment, as though *placing himself inside the composition* in the most direct sense of the word.

In contrast, “*exterior*” orientation would engage performance of one’s part in a polyphonic or homophonic composition created by someone else (as in a cover song), where the performer must speak not for himself but for some fictional protagonist according to someone else’s script, while pretending as though the pronounced lines are his own. In such situation, a performer is aware that his part constitutes an autonomous entity *added* by the composer (or arranger) to the rest of the composition. Awareness of such juxtaposition stands in the way of intuitive appropriation and causes the performer to think of mechanical summation rather than qualitative integration of parts into a whole.

The borderline between the interior and exterior design here is not always clear, since folk music might also reproduce pre-existing “cover songs.” However, such covers focus not on *faithfulness* to the original but on *authenticity* in rendition. In this case, a folk performer enjoys a substantial leeway in modifying the pitch, rhythm, and metric characteristics of the preexisting music, thereby assimilating its musical

material to the extent that allows him to completely identify himself with the protagonist of the song and to present the work as genuinely “his own” rather than as a reproduction of someone else’s work.

Exterior orientation does not allow a performer to achieve a perfect enmeshment: the audience is usually aware of how the composition ought to sound and expects more of an expressive “reading” of the familiar text, where the performer is aware that his identity is different from the identity of an author of the text. Hence, *the performer’s execution of some composer’s music does not really constitute the “music work”* – it only makes the already fixed music work readily perceptible for the public, manifesting a composition that exists *externally* to the performer in a form of music score.

A music expert can experience a particular musical composition without any involvement of performers: he can read the music score and hear internally the sounds of music. In such a scheme, the performer himself occupies the position *outside* the composer’s creation – unlike the typical folk performer who effectively recomposes the existing composition, placing himself *inside* the musical content that is (re)arranged by himself and tailored to his individual performing skills.

Exterior orientation is not bound to Western classical music alone. It can be found in many music cultures that possess the tradition of notation, the fixed code of music theory, the notion of mistake in making music, and the institute of supervising the correctness of execution. The Babylonian music culture already fits the bill. In Mesopotamia, genre classification was the business of scribes, and proceeded according to the intended manner of performance, fixed in notation and classified through the standardized system of subscripts and rubrics (Rubio 2009, 23).

Rubrics specified such structural features as format setting (i.e., call-and-response), types of cadence, and tuning (mode). Subscripts denoted a musical instrument/vocal required for performance, the goal of music performance (e.g., to soothe or glorify a god), or to accompany a certain action (e.g., feast or procession).

Although Sumerian scribes classified their music differently than modern scholars, the very fact that Sumerians came up with a taxonomy to define every piece of music goes to prove an important upgrade from folk music practice. Unlike the latter, Sumerian theory of genre resembled more of accounting and cataloging – designed to facilitate the selection and reproduction of a particular piece of music for a given occasion. Performance practice of Babylonian musicians was supervised by temple and court officials, usually scribes (Ziegler 2011).

The importance of a scribe’s contribution to the musical composition was reflected not only in the higher social status of scribes in comparison to regular musicians (Michalowski 2010), but also in the tradition to identify the names of those scribes who were responsible for the choice of source materials for notation: e.g., Ammurabi and Ipsali (West 1994, 171). Apparently, notation required not only expertise, but also responsibility in attaining the accuracy of information. This should be taken as an indication of the importance of correct execution of a musical composition in those Bronze Age civilizations that observed the doctrine of “harmony of spheres”.

The interior/exterior opposition also manifests itself in the tonal organization of a musical mode. The very same pitch classes can belong to this or that sister mode within the same family of modes.⁸ Understanding of this necessarily involves distancing oneself from the experience of listening: one has to relate not only to what he hears now, but to what he has heard before and learned about music, retrieving in his mind the sound of familiar modes and their corresponding ethos. Not only that, but also each mode must be distanced (externalized) from other modes. Such task invites the attitude of a

⁸ Thus, in Western music theory, a single pitch class “C” can belong to the Ionian (C-D-E-F-G-A-B), Dorian (D-E-F-G-A-B-C), Phrygian (E-F-G-A-B-C-D), Lydian (F-G-A-B-C-D-E), Mixolydian (G-A-B-C-D-E-F), and Aeolian (A-B-C-D-E-F-G) modes – which all share the same pitch classes, and therefore, constitute a family.

spectator in a theatrical show rather than that of a direct participant in the musical action – which characterizes folk cultures.

Folk musician does not usually think in technical terms as to which mode to choose and how one mode differs from another. He intuitively picks those modal formulas that correspond to his emotional state from the repertory of known modes according to the public convention of associating a specific genre to a specific mode. His music-making typically occurs “in the present,” and completely *within* the framework of a particular mode – thus, *inside* a designated tonal space. Music-making in the math-based music system that encompasses a family of modes rarely fits an entire music work in a single mode.

More often than not, a piece of music involves a few modes, thereby, setting boundaries between modes and requiring transition points. For this reason, a *framework of one mode necessarily makes another mode appear “external” and foreign*, requiring a theory of modulation. Archaic forms of folk music do not have such rigid formal framing in its tonal organization, affording “*inclusive*” treatment of sonic material by means of “modal inflections” (see Nikolsky 2016c). “*Exclusive*” treatment becomes the prerogative of a musical key that accompanies the emergence of perspectival organization of pictorial images.

It can also be said that angular projection, utilized by Euclidian perspective (Veltman 1980), provides a cognitive advantage over earlier orthogonal systems of Mesopotamia and Egypt in encoding the depth parameter by making the depicted image less ambiguous. By showing an object slightly from aside, the lines that are supposed to depict the depth aspect become angled (rather than parallel) to the lines that depict the vertical aspect.

This distinction significantly facilitates processing of the 3D spatial encoding in a 2D picture. Jan Deregowski rightfully calls attention to this important transition in the cognitive approach to viewing a pictorial artwork, distinguishing between the *outline per se* and the *typical contour* of an object (Deregowski 2009). Ancient Greek artist preferred to arrange the projection to optimally represent the typical contour (rather than outline) as a more stable entity. That which earlier artists were grasping intuitively only at some occasions became rationalized by Euclidian geometry and turned into a compositional rule.

In a similar vein, the Ancient Greek musician must have started distinguishing between the melodic contour of a leading melody (as in vocals) and the melodic contour of an accompanying part (vocal or instrumental), optimizing his performance not in reference to the principal melody alone, but to the *entirety* of the texture.

Once in place, notions of geometric perspective (formulated by Euclid) and musical key (formulated by Aristoxenus) maintained their connection throughout Western history.

New Synthesis: The Emergence of Holistic Integration

The early Christian culture broke the Greco-Roman tradition by radically flattening both, texture in music, and depth in depiction, forming a new universal canon to illuminate the idea of equality of all objects in the face of God and illusiveness of things mundane.

26. Audio: *Tecum principium in die virtutis tue*, Ambrosian chant, 5-6th century AD. Strict monody with alternation of solo and choir became the principal type of texture in Christian music. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 26\]](#)

Image 25. *Great Novgorod* icon. Post-Constantinian canon put in place a new iconographic style after legalization of Christianity (Finney 1997, 225). Its compositional method is often referred to as the “reverse perspective” (Deregowski 1993).

The term “reverse” refers to the peculiar features that appear to be in polar opposition to the rules of “linear perspective”: objects that are more remote from the vantage point are drawn larger, lines that are supposed to be parallel diverge against the horizon, and the vanishing point is placed outside the painting. “Reverse perspective” as though inverts the basics of linear perspective.

This inversion was completely deliberate on the part of artists and Christian authorities who found deep theological meaning in each of its rules: thus, the increase of size in reverse to the increase of distance was understood as the symbolic representation of smaller importance of things that are the closest to human whereabouts, part of “earthly” life, readily visible to anyone – as opposed to “heavenly” things of great magnitude yet visible to only the ordained (Florensky 1996).

Although the theory of “reverse perspective” was faceted within the Byzantine iconography and thereafter elaborated in Russian

iconography, a number of scholars consider this form of perspective cross-cultural and find its implementation in earlier cultures, explaining its rules by instinctive psychological strategies of spatial representation that are different and alternative to linear perspective (Howard and Allison 2011).

Early Christian iconography focused on commemorating spiritual values by means of sanctified abstract conventions – decidedly hostile to the illusionistic methods of Antiquity (Florensky 2006, 197–272). As hostile was the attitude of the Fathers of the Church to the musical “illusionism” and especially the music for aulos (McKinnon 1989, 34, 61, 72, 78), historically associated with Dionysian theatricality in Hellenic tradition (Franklin 2013). Plainchant canon was abstracted from the diatonic music of Platonic times, prior to Aristoxenus.

Subsequently, plainchant inherited the prescriptive ethos-based music theory associated with Pythagoras, favoring it over the sensualist descriptive theory of Aristoxenus who sought to reflect the common practices of his time rather than “nomothetic” principles: Aristoxenus reasoned that it was people (and not “celestial spheres”) who created music, and therefore the task of music theory was to identify ways and methods of human perception (Cazden 1958). Early Christian theorists highly valued Pythagoras and his diatonic theory and looked down at humanistic and materialistic tendencies of ancient cultures. Christian authorities generally kept the core Pythagorean concepts while purging out the traces of “heathen” ideology (Bower 2002).

Over centuries, Christian plainchant forged its own pool of intonations in the tunes approved by the Church authorities. The codices of tunes were canonized and eventually fixed by notation – which, in sharp contrast to the overwhelmingly hemitonic tradition of Antiquity, strongly relied on the pentatonic trichords (Hansen 1979). The Ancient Greek heritage was not the only source of influence undesirable by Christian music theorists. The Arabic, Persian and Gypsy influence were also targeted - most pronounced in Spain, where we have records of prosecution of the musicians using *cante jondo* and *cante flamenco*. In relation to Jewish music, however, the attitude was mixed: part of the ecclesiastical music found its way to a pool of permissible *Cantus Firmus* tunes, but this related only to the diatonic chants,

especially the pentatonic based tunes. Bence Szabolcsi discovered this highly interesting topic. He considered the Hebraic chants to have originally been pentatonic, and later influenced by the neighboring Babylonian culture (Szabolcsi 1965).

The evidence of the Jewish pentatonic influence is the notation of the Ashkenazi Pentateuchal chant published by a number of Christian authorities, such as Caspar Amman, Sebastian Munster, Johannes Vallensis and Johannes Reuchlin (Avenary 1975). Their primary motivation was the concern to derive the most “authentic” interpretation of the Bible from the indigenous Jewish sources (Kalib 2002, 15). And pentatonic mode occupied an important place in Biblical cantillation (Avenary 1978). Pentatony still retains its importance in Judaic liturgy till this day (Rosowsky 1957).

An example of the theologically driven influence of pentatony on Western music modes can be found in John Merbecke’s Creed, 1550 (Kim 2008, 191). Throughout the late Middle Ages, there were attempts of Catholic clerics to update the translation of the Bible and revise the repertory of the tunes. Such purist clerics saw freeing the melodies from chromatic modulations as getting rid of emotional impurities added by human interference in the “holy” melodies. Imports from the Jewish chants were seen exactly as restoration of the original authenticity.

Psychoacoustically, the Christian shift towards pentatony probably had to do with the intuitive discovery of the inherent property of anhemitonic intonations to reduce tonal tension (see Nikolsky 2015a) – a very important issue for early Christian aesthetics.

A word of caution must be mentioned here: just like rejection of Hellenic chromatic and enharmonic music did not prevent the adoption of Hellenic diatonic theory across the Christendom, the Church’s stance against illusionistic depiction did not completely eliminate the ancient tradition of realism.

Image 26. *The Three Magi*, The Basilica di Sant'Apollinare Nuovo, Ravenna, 6th c. AD. Christian

art sometimes imitated the perspective of pagan Roman art.

In Western Europe, Roman legacy in fine arts remained very much alive even prior to the Renaissance revival of Greco-Roman traditions – supported by the eagerness of Frankish royalty to elevate their cultural status to the levels of prestigious contemporaneous Byzantine art (Hauser 1999a). In Eastern Europe, the older realistic tradition suffered the backlash during the brief period of Iconoclasm in the 8-9th centuries, surviving chiefly amongst wealthier ethnic Greeks and at the Balkan and Italian provinces of Byzantium (Mango 2002).

For Christian music, the legacy of Hellenic music texture fared less well than for arts – even in the West. Performance practice was largely reformed and pushed in totally new direction. Fragments of the canonic melodies, collected in tonaries, have served as a source material for most of the music composed for ecclesiastic purposes throughout Medieval West. The legacy of reducing the melodic content to sanctified plainchant tunes extended far into the Renaissance and Baroque through the prevalent compositional technique of *cantus prius factus* – i.e., laying out parts of the multi-part composition in counterpoint to the pre-existing plainchant melody delegated to a lower part (Yevdokimova 1983).

Initially, canonic rules kept a firm grip on both, Christian iconography and monody, throughout the early Middle Ages. Then, the rebirth of dipphony and triphony out of monodic plainchant pushed Western music towards polyphony. The multitude of examples of polyphony were documented in *Musica enchiriadis* (9th century AD) testifying that 2-part polyphonic textures were already common back then. About the same time, came the first experiments of liberating depiction from canonic rules, away from scholastic stylishness, and toward a more naturalistic and individualized manner (Schapiro 1952).

Image 27. *Journey to Bethlehem, Santa Maria foris portas*. Castelseprio, 9th century AD. Carolingian reincarnation of the Roman compositional technique, refreshed by the amalgamation of Byzantine and Carolingian styles (Leveto 1990).

Late Carolingian art eased up the negative attitude of Christian authorities on Greco-Roman legacy, even occasionally featuring shading in iconographic works – despite the obvious association of “shadow” with darkness, ignorance, and evil in contrast to “light” associated with truth and God. Following the same path, the 12th century *musica ficta* legalized the occasional use of chromatic “shading”, making it aesthetically appealing and usable despite the earlier disapproval of ancient and contemporaneous non-European chromatic music by the Church (Brothers 1997).

New Analysis: The Differentiation of the Integrated Whole

The growing interest to imitative and contrasting polyphony led to the emancipation of the techniques of contrasting polyphony in the 12th century (Tischler 1956). The compositional idea of binding parts by making them contrast in tonal and rhythmic organization is untypical for folk indigenous traditions, since the task of optimizing a contrast (without which parts do not merge in a way that is convenient for perception) requires the experience of laying out the constituent parts - either in notation or in the form of oral teaching of the performers by a composer.

At this point, the qualifications of a choir singer in church or palace became deficient for handling the task of singing in counterpoint with other singers, requiring their coordination by a specialist, familiar with the existing compositional techniques and skilled in hearing polyphonic relations between all parts, as well as capable of trouble-shooting a mistake or imperfection and instructing performers to correct a problem (Yevdokimova 1983). To address this need, a new musical profession was established that later acquired a name of “Kapellmeister” [from medieval Latin “capella” and Germanic “meister” – “master of a chapel”], or “maestro di capella” [Italian].

First “masters of chapel” started writing treatises to share problems that they faced in their occupation and solutions they found, and these treatises became popular instructional literature across Europe – e.g., “*Scholia enchiridis*”⁹ was one of the first treatises (c. 10th century) to discuss the rules of generating a counterpoint part to a given plainsong (Strunk and Treitler 1998). The international spread of the public discourse on polyphonic music theory marked the radical divergence of Western music from earlier folk forms of “natural” polyphonic traditions.

27. Audio: Anon. – *Alleluia* from *Codex Calixtinus* (13th century), florid organum. The texture is based on the contrast between a lower part that carries a simple canonic plainsong, presented in very long rhythmic values and smooth stepwise melodic motion, set against a higher part that contains an alternative melody. This melody is designed to impress a listener with its sophistication and beauty - in contrast to solemn and stern plainsong below. The contrast is not limited to the semantic domain. The musical structure of the upper part contrasts the lower part by means of its florid melodic line and much shorter rhythmic values, as well as its performance setting: the upper part was usually delegated to a soloist or a group of soloists, whereas the lower part was performed by the choir in unison. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 27\]](#)

By the 14th century, a number of completely new polyphonic textures have been in use all over Western Europe, reaching the unprecedented complexity of music form. Especially complicated was the technique of hocket, which articulated phrases in such a manneristic style that even a 3-part polyphony was really hard to follow for a musically trained listener (Leech-Wilkinson 2003). Ultimately, Pope John XXII banned such polyphonic devices in 1324 (Wright 2008, 346).¹⁰ This ban stayed in effect until the

⁹ Noteworthy, this treatise contains numerous references to geometry, arithmetic, and astronomy in its explanation of the principles of tonal organization of the counterpoint (ibid., p.134-138).

¹⁰ Hocket [from Latin “hoquetus” – “hiccup”] is a technique of distribution of thematic material between a few adjacent parts in a polyphonic texture, where a single audio stream as though is divided between 2 (sometimes,

16th century (Blackburn 2007, 90). It took about a century for Western composers to resolve the manneristic crisis and earn back the approval of clerics.

Pivotal was the switch from the old Pythagorean doctrine of Tetractys that postulated the consonance of the interval of a 4th (Barbera 1977) to the new harmonic theory based on the consonance of the intervals of a 3rd and of a 5th (Barbour 2004). This new harmonic method was pioneered by John Dunstable and quickly caught attention of European composers (Bukofzer 1952). The new practice of generating contrapuntal parts that frequently formed the intervals of a 3rd and a 6th led to the general prevalence of triads in harmonic organization of the entire music texture (Wienpahl 1971), setting a novel method of conceptualizing tonal organization in music in terms of concordance of chords (Nutting 1974). Triadic foundation allowed composers to greatly increase the number of parts, and to standardize handling of intervals to support simultaneous movement of multiple melodies.

This upgrade in textural complexity concurred with the experiments of Masaccio in finding compositional schemes alternative to canonic iconography, capable to evoke a sense of lifelike movement – the goal that prompted him to seek ways how to imitate 3-dimensional disposition of figures in his paintings (Deimling 1995).

28. Audio: Dufay - *Ecclesie Militantis* (1540), motet for 5 parts, dedicated to the Papal approval of the Jesuit Order. The motet utilizes 3 melodies, each with its own lyrics (one about the militancy of Church, another about the value of peace, and the third about the omnipresence of God) and 2 supporting parts. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 28\]](#)

Image 28. Masaccio – *The Tribute Money* (1425). Use of linear and atmospheric perspective to emphasize Jesus' head in unification of 3 episodes of the story, joined in a single composition: 1) the tax collector demanding tax from Jesus and his disciples (center), 2) St. Peter removing money from the fish's mouth (left segment), 3) St. Peter paying the tax collector (right segment) – all sharing a naturalistic cityscape background that is rendered in the perspectival tradition of the Romans.

An important consequence of the integrative effect of “chunking” musical tones into chords and of grouping depicted objects into a realistic scenery was a marked increase in premeditation of the artistic

3) parts by means of creative use of rests (Sanders 2001). Christian clerics were highly hostile to hocket because of its disruption of lyrics, deemed inappropriate for liturgical music. Although the theory of hocket was developed within the period of Western Ars Antiqua, 12-13th centuries, similar devices are known in Western popular music and in some non-European folk polyphonic traditions (Tagg 2012, 465-467).

composition. The painter had to envisage the image prior to sketching his work. The composer had to commit to a certain scheme of registration of the ambitus, a certain style of rhythmic coordination of parts, a certain method in distributing thematic material between parts, and a certain principle of disposition of text through all vocal parts prior to the “compositional” phase of conception – such methodology of composition becomes a new norm in the 15th century, but the germs of it are noticeable even in earlier Ars Nova motets (Moll 1998), contemporaneous to Masaccio.

New Complexity: The Emergence of Pre-planning

Already in the 14th century, some composers decided the functionality of parts in a music texture pre-compositionally, based on the semantic attributes of pre-selected lyrics. Sometimes this entailed visualization of the musical composition. The most striking demonstration of this can be found in unconventional notations that became popular towards the end of the 14th century: usually, concentric circular, or in the shape of an object – such as a heart or a harp.

Image 29. Anonymous – “*En la maison Dedalus*” for 3 parts (c.1377), the earliest example of circular notation (Berkeley, University of California Music Library, 744).

29. Audio: Anonymous – Ballade “*En la maison Dedalus*,” voice solo with instrumental accompaniment of two polyphonic parts, where the upper part canonically imitates the lower part – circulating the same thematic material in defiance of the free-floating vocals. The circular look of the notation complemented the multi-part circularity of the music. [[See Supplementary Audio File 29](#)]

Such notation was much more than a mere “cosmetic” choice for the unusual expression of conventional musical structures determined by composer’s fancy. The author of “*En la maison Dedalus*” found a way to musically illustrate the

lyrics that referred to a maze, built by Dedalus for the Minotaur, by scoring his composition as an 11-course labyrinth, drawn with a pair of compasses (Leach 2011). The part closest to the center carries the “tune,” while the tenor and countertenor parts are notated as one part to be sung in canon, where the tenor keeps chasing the countertenor (in illustration of the moto “*Tenor faciens contratenorem alter alterum fugando*”).¹¹

The reference to the labyrinth here serves as a metaphor for the story of a courtly poem that describes the suffering of a suicidal Lover who strives to find his way to the “heart of his desire” (Wright 2004, 239). This Romantic idea is expressed graphically as well as musically through the path of the melodic motion yet to be found under the pressure of the chasing voices of the accompaniment.

¹¹ The transcription of this ballade in modern notation is made by Richard Crocker (Crocker 1967).

Matching visual and musical expressions to illuminate the text of a song maybe characterized as a stylistic trait discovered by artists of *Ars subtilior* (c.1360-1420): the quest for esoteric sophistication in appreciation of beauty of spatial arrangement of a given music texture (Smilansky 2011). Yet another famous example of expressive notation is “*La harpe de melodie.*”

Image 30. Senleches - *La harpe de melodie* for 2 parts (1395), Chicago, Newberry Library, 54.1. Notation in the form of a harp, where notes are placed on strings, against the inscriptions on the banner which are wrapped around the fore pillar of the harp. The accompanying text invites to discover and appreciate the notes of a beautiful harp, instructing a performer how to derive the second part from the picture of the strings (Leach 2013).

30. Audio: Senleches - *La harpe de melodie*, virelai. Typical for Western Medieval culture theme of courtly love is expressed here with the concern for privacy – suggesting that the pleasure from refined music and pleasure from refined company are both better off if concealed. Hence, the performer is tasked to strive hard in order to find that which is concealed in the unconventional notation.

[\[See Supplementary Audio File 30\]](#)

This tradition of emblematic notation survived for quite a long time: John Bull’s 6-part circular canon “*Sphera mundi*” in the 18th-century manuscript, and canons for the Chapel Royal by Juan del Vado (1679) testify to its longevity.

All in all, emblematic notation should be viewed as an original way of pre-conceiving the thematic material and the textural arrangement in a musical composition by engaging spatial connotations. Ever since Western music elaborated the array of standardized textures, associated with specific genres and styles of music, there was no longer a need to use weird notation, because spatial visualization of musical texture became as common in the process of fixing music in a multi-part score, as audiation of the notated harmonic intervals and chords constituted a chore in the practice of musical composition.

Composers started using conventional notation to capture unconventional “inventions” of texture. An example of this is a device of deliberate blurring of the pulse of harmonic progressions by means of committing to a layered texture based on the repetitions of a figuration of the accompaniment (rather than using regular chords). Candace Brower (2008) provides a glimpse into such textural creativity: an accompaniment in Brahms’ *Intermezzo*, which is treated like a Möbius strip in Escher’s lithographs.

31. Audio: Brahms – *Intermezzo in B minor*, op.119, No.1. Accumulation of the chain of 3^{rds} in the expressive legato figuration of the bass voice obscures the harmonic plan by making it unclear as to which exact chords are implied in a bar, and how exactly they are distributed between the beats (and downbeats). [\[See Supplementary Audio File 31\]](#)

Textures with such dispersed, lagging, or delayed harmonies in the melodic figurations of one or more voices of the accompaniment became the “favorite” of many late Romantic piano composers, such as Alexander Scriabin, who described his synesthetic vision of music compositions as a dynamic interaction of multiple objects of different size, mass, and color in a delimited area of space (Sabaneyev 2000).

Introduction of a new methodology of pre-composition in the 14-15th centuries eventually led to crystallization of a new listening style, characterized by appreciation of harmonic consonance and polyphonic complexity despite its occasional *incomprehensibility* (Wegman 2002).

32. Audio: Ducis – *Agnus Dei*, No.18 from *Cantiones Triginta Selectissimae* (1568). This motet for 8 parts features a quadruple retrograde canon: it makes parts Nos. 5-8 reproduce parts 1-4 in retrograde inversion (so that the first tone of part-1 is the last tone of part-5, etc.) – which is humanly impossible to perceive upon audition. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 32\]](#)

Image 31. Tintoretto – *The Origin of the Milky Way* (1580). Tintoretto assembled this composition by trying to find pictorial analogs to the cosmographic allegory through the complex system of curves, circles, and triangles, called to reflect the complexity of celestial spheres (Bouleau 2014, 475). It is highly doubtful if Tintoretto’s idea is perceptible by the viewer without reading some verbal explanation of the allegory.

A parallel to this can be drawn in the Renaissance fine arts. The rules of “linear perspective” quickly turned from the artist’s scholarly explorations into the standard for composition and consumption of

visual fine-art (Edgerton 2009), prompting artists to seek recognition by inventing unusual compositional arrangements and experimenting with various ways of breaking the rules (Bouleau 2014). The quest for originality often brought to life compositional schemes that were hard to comprehend even for fellow-artists, well versed in a variety of compositional techniques.

Sometimes, the complexity of a visual composition inspired the complexity of a musical composition. Thus, the tonal organization of the 4-part motet “*Plus nulz regretz*” by Josquin Desprez was probably modeled after Leon Battista Alberti's method for determining perspective in art as a way of implementing planned proportional compositional structures, which characterized the entire Renaissance approach to composition (Reynolds 1987).

33. Audio: Josquin - “*Plus nulz regretz*” (1511). The similarity between the principles of linear perspective as formulated by Alberti and this musical composition remains practically inaudible as compared to other motets by Josquin – testifying to the scholasticism of compositional thought in Medieval Western music. [[See Supplementary Audio File 33](#)]

The New Standard of Originality in Compositional Arrangement

Textural standards of post-Renaissance music come surprisingly close to perspectival standards of post-Renaissance art. Thus, tonal key is commonly realized through 3(4)-part polyphonic, 4-voice homophonic, and 3(4)-component polyphonic-homophonic texture - which altogether encompass absolute majority of the 18th - mid-20th century compositions (Kholopova 1979).

Often, composers approached textural design creatively, conceiving an original conglomerate of voices/parts prior to laying out the music. The range of available options was virtually unlimited: a composer could potentially hybridize a number of any pre-existing schemes of musical textures, even those that came from alternative methods of tonal organization, such as different types of homophony, polyphony and heterophony.

34. Audio: Haydn - “*Uns sprießet Überfluss*,” No.6, from *The Seasons* (1799) features a 4-part vocal fugue with the orchestral accompaniment that mostly consists of 2 parts (bass and melody). This is an example of a creative textural decision where the composer has engineered a unique functional combination of parts by combining the polyphonic and the homophonic methods of tonal organization. [[See Supplementary Audio File 34](#)]

Similarly, a number of 18th century artworks employ an unorthodox integration of the architectural interior on a wall with painted architectural ornaments, placed against a backdrop of a depicted scenery – with the addition of yet another architectural background (see Image 32, below). The idea of hybridization of a few autonomous systems in a single compositional compound unites the experiments of the 18th century artists and of the 18th century composers under the same umbrella.

The entire Baroque culture might be characterized as a complex interaction of multiple constituent parts, where each part is rendered as an autonomous expressive entity, competing with other entities, and therefore, producing contrast and conflict. Baroque polyphony differs from Renaissance polyphony by the overall smaller number of parts, yet greater individualization of the thematic material in each of the parts (Poultney 1996).

In amazing similarity, Baroque fine art is recognized for its individualization of each of the component images and the resultant cluttering (uncharacteristic for the Renaissance), usually compensated by intense, often striking, tonal contrast (Hauser 1999b, 2:106).

Image 32. Tiepolo – View of the east wall of *Palazzo Labia*, Venice (1750). The architectural interior here is incorporated into a spatial ensemble with a fresco “*The Banquet of Cleopatra*,” forming an original fantastic space. The perspective organization of this fresco is seamlessly embedded in the interior design of a room, creating a collage of 3D and 2D images.

“Invention” of an entirely original spatial composition that would deliver “illusionistic” impression despite its complexity and originality is a trademark of Baroque art – largely in line with “invention” of original textures and compositional schemes in music to convey musical affects. The commonality of

inventive implementation of a thematic idea was exemplified in the emergence of a dedicated musical genre of “invention,” in its evolution from Cesare Negri to J.S. Bach (Caldwell 2001). Introduced by the Renaissance composers, such as Johannes Tinctoris and Clement Janequin, “musical invention” was understood as the discovery through the process of composition.

Later Baroque development added yet another layer of meaning – in J.S. Bach’s words from the preface to his *Inventions*: “a clear method ... not only of arriving at good original ideas [*Inventiones*] but also of developing them satisfactorily” (1723). Hence, the genre of musical invention was designed to demonstrate compositional skills in developing original musical ideas.

Something similar to Baroque musical “invention” in the realm of fine art would be the genre of “ceiling painting,” which from Michelangelo to Le Brun has presented an arena for Baroque artists to exercise their inventiveness of fantastic visions. It would be useful to remind that the very term “Baroque”, in fact, literally meant “bizarre” in Italian. Ceiling painting became a genre, highly appreciated for its bizarreness in Italy (Wittkower 1958, 481), as well as in France (Blunt 1957, 196).

Image 33. Pietro da Cortona - *Triumph of the Barberini*, Palazzo Barberini, Rome (1639). The stucco ornamentation creates a frame of reference for apparent realness of some figures that as though share “our” space with a stucco behind them, whereas other figures are either leaning on the stucco, dangling their feet or are positioned farther away, as if “behind” the stucco. At least partially, the intention of a painter must have been to entertain spectators with an unusual task of contemplating the painting’s intricacy from the unconventional position of lying on one’s back:

Image 34. Visitors of Palazzo Barberini are appreciating Cortona's fresco.

The connection to musical “invention” in the Cortona’s example is limited to the pragmatic aspect of interpreting the harmonic organization of specific thematic material rather than music texture per se. Besides its association with inventiveness, the notion of “invention” was also renowned from Hellenic times as one of the five canons of rhetoric (Murphy 1981). “Inventio” constituted a method for discovery of arguments, implemented as the first section in the compositional plan for a speech, dedicated to an attempt to deliver a convincing and compelling argument. The same function characterized “inventio” in a music form (McCreless 2002). Thus, Johannes Mattheson and Johannes Heinichen in their highly influential treatises both regarded inventio as a rhetoric centerpiece in the use of the *loci topici* (i.e., categories that delineate the relationships between ideas) to inspire expressive melodic themes.

- 35.** Audio: Marini - *Sonata in ecco* for 3 violins and basso continuo from *Sonate, symphonie con altre curiose e moderne inventioni* op.8 (1629). Marini’s exploration of the genre of invention goes along the rhetoric lines of “convincing” and entertaining his listeners in presenting a subject, in this case, an idea to combine musical and histrionic aspects of expression in the acting out an echo. Two violins “echo” the first violin from a hidden location, consistently surprising the audience by the changing pattern of which thematic material of the 1st violin becomes echoed. Things are complicated by the everchanging thematic material and by the interplay of 2 violins “in disguise”: each of them is distinguished by its own pattern of echoing. The resulting “charade” stands as a pretense for role-playing throughout the musical composition by each of the actors – as an inventive theatrical implementation of the *stile rappresentativo* (Cypess 2008, 184-240). Marini aims to entertain his audience in a way quite like Cortona’s depiction of cherubs dangling their feet in Image 33. Both examples pick a theme and develop it with a grain of humor to amaze spectators. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 35\]](#)

Paradoxically, the quest for novel “engineering” of creative ideas led to consolidation of the “standards” of spatial and tonal composition into dedicated scholarly disciplines that started adopting progressively

more and more “scientific” appearance. The “science” of perspective became an attribute of professionalism in fine arts. Already, Leonardo was writing that those who ignored perspective were like “maritime pilots that maneuvered their ships without rudder or compass – never certain of their output” (Bell 1992). Likewise, towards the end of the 17th century, the theories of general bass and counterpoint (they both covered the issues of music texture and tonal organization) acquired the status of “bar exam” for the wish-to-be-composers. The discipline of counterpoint put the vertical and horizontal aspects of harmonic organization under the same umbrella of rendering parts in a polyphonic texture.

The switch of fashion from polyphonic to homophonic genres, which cut the careers of J.S. Bach and Vivaldi short, did not change the state of affairs in approaching music texture in a “scientific” manner. Neither harmonic, nor textural complexities ended, when contrapuntal compositional techniques went out of favor.

Most typical textures of common practice period - polyphonic-homophonic textures - combine homophonic principles of organization by subordinating all parts and voices to a one-at-a-time leading melodic line (with possible dubbing), where each of the textural components receives its own discrete function in accompanying the main melody. However, even purely “homophonic”, i.e., accompanying, parts still require from the composer a knowledge of counterpoint. That is why the treatise by Johann Fux on counterpoint, “*Gradus ad Parnassum*” (1725), remained the obligatory textbook in most conservatories of music until the end of the 19th century, when most Western countries adopted textbooks on counterpoint in their native tongues.

Throughout the 20th century and until the present, students of music composition and music theory have to pass exams on theory of counterpoint in most graduate schools of the world – despite the fact that polyphony went out of fashion during the first quarter of the 18th century. The primary reason for this is that counterpoint is instrumental in scoring any homophonic texture, including the most basic genres, such as a song or a dance.

The maximum number of components in an orchestral texture of a typical 18-19th century piece of music can easily reach seven (Kholopova 1979, 37):

- 1) principal melody;
- 2) its dub;
- 3) melodic counterpoint line (imitative or contrasting);
- 4) figuration of the accompaniment;
- 5) harmonic accompaniment (in chords or double-notes);
- 6) bass line;
- 7) pedal tones and pedal-like background layer.¹²

36. Audio: Rimsky-Korsakov - *Praise to Wilderness* from the opera “*The Legend of the Invisible City of Kitezh and the Maiden Fevroniya*”. The orchestral score features all 7 functional types of textural components. [[See Supplementary Audio File 36](#)]

¹² Not all of these components have to be engaged simultaneously at any given point in time – more common is the “diagonal” method, when only 3 parts (melody, bass, and one of the accompanying voices) run throughout the composition, while 1-2 extra parts/voices appear to be temporarily replacing each other, thereby, keeping the number of simultaneously active information streams to 4-5 (e.g., Beethoven – Adagio from *Sonata Pathetique*).

The Notion of Variation in Density along the Depth Parameter

The equivalent of “texture thickness” for linear perspective is the *number of vanishing points*. Albertian perspective linked together the viewer and the depicted space by adopting the strict tri-unity of scale, horizon, and viewpoint: vanishing point here anchored a system that “incarnated” the viewer, turning him into an organic part of the work as well as its “ruler.” The task of gazing at the vanishing point, in effect, installed the viewer as the *object* of the composition (Bryson 1983, 106).

Image 35. Raphael – *Marriage of the Virgin* (1504). “Frontal” one-point linear perspective integrates the viewer and the depicted objects in a manner of “looking through the window.”

Technically speaking, it is the vantage axis between the observer’s eye and the vanishing point, defined by the artist, that pierces the pictorial space and reveals the number of

objects placed along this axis. The “golden mean” of populating the available depth seemed to be about 4 ranks – provided that the painter did not shoot for the “crowd effect,” and supplied the interspatial objects with discrete characteristics.

The musical equivalent to such detailing would be the distinction between the texture that is based on a chordal accompaniment (“the crowd”) versus the texture based on melodic counterpoint (“a supporting character” or “characters”, if there are a few counterpoint parts). An average of 3-4 textural components (occasionally simplified to just 2 or complicated by adding parts up to 6) is common for the compositional arrangement of both, Western perspectival art and Western tonality in music.

“Mediterranean tonality” that forms an alternative to Western tonality (see Nikolsky 2016e) and corresponding to it Eastern traditions of pictorial spatial organization have never come close to the density of the depth parameter in artworks of Western painters and composers. There is a common belief that Islam followed early Christianity in prohibiting the realistic fine art and sensual music of Antiquity.

In reality, Islam neither cut ties with the Roman legacy nor banned drawing from nature – in fact, some religious authorities encouraged picture-making.¹³ The only pronounced detrimental effect was that early Islamic artists downgraded to a flatter rendition of figures than that in the Roman tradition.

Image 36. *Hare* from the Fustad fragments, 10-12th centuries. Hellenic influence is evident in Islamic Fatimid art, suggestive of depth and texture (Hoffman 2000).

37. Audio: St. John of Damascus – *Ya walidata-l-ilah* (Canon on the Nativity), Melkite chant. The Byzantine chant was assimilated in many Middle Eastern communities, with lyrics translated into Arabic. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 37\]](#)

It is true that Islam eventually denounced *illusionism*, instead introducing a special style of spatial representation based on frontal and oblique parallel

projection, without committing to a particular “point of view,” avoiding shades, relief, and minimizing scalar coordination (Raynaud 2009). However, Islamic artists were aware of the “open space,” and did not shun from its realistic depiction. But their method was decidedly non-illusionistic: devoid of horizon and vanishing points in an attempt to remove personal connection of the spectator to any anchor point in the horizon at the picture’s background – to make the picture look “impersonal” (Rauschenbach 1980, 196).

A picture often merged a few discrete projections in a manner of a blueprint – presenting information unavailable from a single viewpoint (e.g., combining bird’s-eye view and worm’s-eye view), while maintaining the continuity of the horizontal baseline (Orbay-Grignon 1996).

¹³ The Fatimid book of illustrations c. 11th century includes even realistic depiction of a nude holding a lute and a cup (probably with wine) in her hands (Hoffman 2000).

Image 37. Folio “Entertainment in a Garden,” from a *Khamsa of Amir Khusrau Dihlavi* (16th c.). Space here cannot be derived from a single glance at the picture, but requires continuous horizontal scanning. [[See Supplementary Audio Files](#)]

The frontage of the foreground took on a leading role in projecting a realistic impression, thereby limiting spatial representation to a largely 2D coordination of pictorial objects by homogenizing colors and sizes, so that the observer’s eye would be encouraged to move sequentially through the foreground without trying to “pierce” it, often suggesting a spiral observation curve (Papadopoulo 1979, 458). The strategy of such “superficial” scanning through the foreground of a pictorial composition resembles scanning through the texture of a music work performed on a solo string instrument, such as qanun, oud, or santur within a tradition

of maqam or dastgakh.

Yes, a musical texture does not demand multiple performers - *a single musical instrument* can generate music recognizable by its textural by ear even by a musically untrained listener. Even instruments capable of playing only one pitch at a time (e.g., flute solo), as well as a solo singer, do pattern a melodic line by means of changes in melodic contour, rhythm, and register (Skrebkov 1973, 136). This is how we immediately tell the difference between a guitar-like quick rolls of strummed chords and harp-like broken arpeggio figurations made of chordal notes – even when guitar-like strums are played by some

other instrument (e.g., cello pizzicato), or when harp-like figurations are played by a clarinet. In a similar way, the presence of a specific pattern in a single part can prompt listeners to recognize its musical material as being originally conceived for such instruments as violin (due to double stops a 5th apart), organ (consistent presence of a pedal part), trumpet (many loud broken arpeggios in the middle register), bagpipe (the drone of a 5th), timpani (a few loud pitches classes often repeated) etc.. The signifiers are:

- specific types of distribution of tones in regard to the prevalent intervallic sizes between them,
- changes in melodic direction combined with certain rhythmic patterns,
- number of rhythmic divisions consistently used in music,
- numerosity of grouped tones per phrase/motif of music,
- the average length of phrases and motifs,
- the prevalent manner of articulating tones, and
- the manner of registration of phrases and motifs.

The same principles of patterning apply to non-Western music. A strictly monophonic texture of a solo instrument that executes a melodic line in a specific maqam generates recognizable textural patterns, whenever a “busy” fluent melody “branches out” into the implied voices in the technique of “hidden polyphony” (Yanov-Yanovskaya 1984). Musicologists used to call it “hidden,” because a performer always produces only one note at a time (e.g., sonatas for flute solo by C.P.E. Bach), which denies genuine polyphonic texture (Fuller 1971).

Modern Western musicologists call such arrangement “implicit polyphony” and consider it a cross-cultural phenomenon (Klempe 2017). Psychoacousticians have demonstrated that the perceptory laws that govern perception of genuine polyphony are the same as those in charge of “implicit polyphony” (Huron 2001) – determined by the cognitive phenomenon of the segregation of an audio stream detected in an “auditory scene” (Bregman 1994) as a function of tempo and intervallic distances between the consecutive pitch levels (van Noorden 1975).

Yet another source of polyphonization of a single part by means of texturing it in a characteristic way is the inclusion of drones in a solo improvisation (instruments capable of playing only 1 tone at a time can keep producing the same drone tone sequentially). A typical device of tonal organization is sustaining the full time value of those treble tones that are dissonant in relation to a drone - in contrast to shortening the time values of the consonant tones while building up the climax (Vinogradov 1973).

- 38.** Audio: *Shur* on tar solo, Azerbaijanian mugam. Three textural devices: 1) Use of drone tone, 2) implied polyphony, and 3) registral contrast - induce the impression of rich texture with idiosyncratic patterning in a purely monodic music. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 38\]](#)

Techniques of polyphonizing a single part found in maqam-based music are not limited to the pedal devices like drones. According to the testimony of Muzaffer Sarisozen, a distinguished Turkish ethnomusicologist, lute performers in central Anatolia often employ progressions of parallel 5^{ths} (just as double-pipe players in various parts of Turkey do). Even Anatolian solo flute players occasionally engage a challenging technique of producing double-stop overtones.

The most sophisticated organum-like forms of 4th- and 5th-based parallel polyphony are found in folk Anatolian songs and violin/bagpipe duos in North-Eastern Turkey (Picken 1953). Some Central Asian offshoots of the maqam tradition (e.g., Azari *mugham* or Uzbeki *shashmaqam*) make use of polyphonic textures based on instrumental accompaniment that repeats an ostinato figure, while the vocals execute the primary melodic line.

- 39.** Audio: *Maddoh*, Pamir. The accompanying rubab (6-string lute) keeps repeating the melodic figure B-A#-B, with the drone tone E – in contrast to the freely unveiling vocal melody. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 39\]](#)

Overall, such textures are more sophisticated than those possible in the Ancient Greek tradition, but they still come nowhere close to even the simplest types of multi-part arrangement of Western Renaissance music. The same distance separates Western and Eastern spatial organization. Some of the manuscript illuminations from Persia and India feature big landscapes or many dozens of characters – but multiple objects never align along the vantage-to-vanishing points axis, and therefore do not produce hierarchic order, remaining all equally “superficial.”

In contrast, Renaissance artists and musicians were interested in “deep” content: confined to music’s middle parts/voices or the “interim” space of an artwork. Both media were vulnerable to saturation. Leonardo’s rule of 20-time reduction of the real object’s size (Kubovy 1988, 41) reflected a hard boundary beyond which the depicted detail would be too fine for the observer to see. Then, detail-rich compositions of smaller size would suffer from a strict one-point perspective that would be *compressing* the interior of a picture as the depth-distance increases, not only diminishing the “more distant” objects but also cramming them together (Arnheim 1983, 205).

The Typology of Complex Depth

The workaround for overcoming the Leonardo’s limit of the 20-time reduction was *multiplication of vanishing points*. Already Alberti’s pupils realized that strict tri-unity of perspective could produce a tilt in a vertical figure (Bouleau 2014, 25) or tension between the distant vanishing point and the foreground figures (Arnheim 1983). Then, rising or lowering of the horizon line, and placing a vanishing point on an important object to stress that object would enhance the composition (Elkins 1996, 147).

Image 38. Veronese – *The Wedding at Cana* (1563) uses 6 vanishing points to make the space appear airy despite a crowd of people populating it (Bouleau 2014, 26).

Multiple vanishing points allowed artists to employ a more economical distribution of objects, reserving more space for the foreground and compensating for this by flattening the background. Renaissance painters often employed up to 3 horizons and 4 vanishing points, making one of them dominant while subordinating the other ones to it (Rauschenbach 2002, 150). Some of the painters became famous for the complexity of their perspective that enabled them to put out monumental works that contained hundreds of pictorial objects – e.g., Veronese.

Horizons varying in height, as well as multiple left/right vanishing points, could be optimized to reserve space for placement of more objects between the foreground and the horizon. Musically, similar function was secured by the practice of *basso continuo* [“continuous bass line”]: improvisation of the accompaniment to a solo instrument on an instrument capable of playing multiple sounds at once or delegated to a group of 2-3 of such instruments, e.g., harpsichord and viola da gamba. Notably, musical instruments engaged in playing basso continuo (usually, 1-3 instruments) were completely ignored in the practice of naming of a composition (Cohen 2008). Thus, Sonatas for flute solo by J.S. Bach BWV 1030-39 were considered “monophonic” despite the fact that their performance usually engaged 3 people (a soloist and 2 players executing basso continuo).

The nomenclature of naming distinguished between the cases where an instrument, such as harpsichord or organ, was supposed to “realize” (i.e., decipher in an improvised creative manner) the series of “figures” (aka, numbers) placed under the bass line in a musical score (i.e., “figured bass”) and the cases where such musical instrument carried out a part that was spelled out as “notes”. Only the latter was considered in the specification of an instrumental setting in the title of a music composition. Obviously, the visual aspect of the look of a music score played a role in identifying and classifying music.

Technically speaking, basso continuo was a science of detecting implied harmony of the melody (or multiple melodies in a polyphonic work) and filling up the distance between the melody and the bass line with chords and figurations according to the context of music. The number of notes in a chord and their exact disposition across registers did not matter and was left at the discretion of a musician responsible for providing a basso continuo. This is what resembles the use of multiple vanishing points by artists who wanted to fit more figures into the available pictorial space.

By the end of the 17th century, the use of basso continuo was codified into the theoretic discipline of *figured bass* and was considered the backbone of professional composition in distinction from the amateur music-making. Figured bass was the first thing that a wish-to-be-a-composer had to study – pretty similar to how a wish-to-be-a-painter had to study perspective.

Many modern textbooks inaccurately describe basso continuo as a Baroque invention. As a matter of fact, the origin of basso continuo dates back to Veronese’s times. The practice of spontaneous invention of a chord-based counterpoint part to a leading melody had evolved within the development of *stile moderno* (defined by Giulio Caccini in *Le nuove musiche*, 1602), which, in turn, grew from the older practice of *basso seguente* of the earlier *stile antico* (Schulenberg 1984). *Bassi seguenti* were instrumental dubs of all the vocal parts arranged for the organ to support choral and madrigal music by reproducing all vocal tones in unison. *Bassi seguenti* were actually printed, starting at least from the 1590s, in “short” or “full” notation (Horsley 1977).¹⁴

Sometimes the vocal bass part had long rests (e.g., in the 1580s Ferrara madrigal style), in which cases a free non-dubbing instrumental bass was added in the score (ibid., p.476), constituting a discrete extra part. Cases like that exposed the contribution of *basso seguente* to the perceived thickness of a music texture. Thickening of a texture must have been one of the reasons for basso continuo to have become a

¹⁴ Thus, in 1609, in *Conclusioni nel suono dell'organo*, Op.20, Adriano Banchieri recommended that the organist played the bass part and added a kind of accompaniment suggested by *basso seguente*, above it.

standard of composition – music-makers and listeners developed a taste for thick textures and perceived strict monophony as too thin.

Just as deviations from Alberti's one-point perspective are already found in the works of his pupils, the roots of basso continuo are traceable to Palestrina – the staple of the Renaissance strict style of polyphony – as well as to the music of other reputable polyphonists: Alessandro Striggio, Luis de Victoria, and Cristóbal de Morales (Barbieri 1994). Even earlier was the use of the so-called “proto-continuo” – i.e., improvisatory repetitions of the same formula in self-accompaniment for a solo song, emulating the Ancient Greek citharode performance - documented in public entertainments in celebration of the marriage between Cosimo I de' Medici and Eleonora of Toledo in 1539 (Ashworth & O'Dette 2007). Examples of such accompanying formulas are notated in publications of tabulaturas for the frottola collections and in the Bottegari *Lutebook* (1574).

The practice of virtuosic embellishments in vocal parts was another common source for the discrepancy between the leading melodic part and the basso continuo. The latter typically moved slower, by higher order rhythmic divisions (e.g., 8th notes versus the 16th notes of a virtuosic solo part), making it noticeably heavier than the melody. Consequently, the basso continuo turned into a “body” that supported a melodic “face” of a music work. The rate of changes of “facial” expressions is normally much higher than that of “bodily” postures. Hence, the contribution of basso continuo to the overall expression of a music piece is substantially more limited than the contribution of melodic parts, which probably explains why basso continuo remained a “shadowy” part, uncounted in the nominal setting of a music composition.

The end of the performance practice of basso continuo did not terminate the use of uncounted thickening of the music texture. This is most evident in the orchestral scores of those composers who started their careers during the basso continuo era. Thus, Haydn was still using basso continuo in his early period symphonies written c. 1760s and specified their settings as, for example, “sinfonia a 8” (i.e., a symphony for 8 parts, as indicated in the autograph of Haydn's Symphony No.26 “Lamentatione”), where basso continuo remained uncounted. Haydn's middle period symphonies switch away from this tradition and neither specify the exact number of parts, nor require basso continuo. Nevertheless, they do not differ from Haydn's symphonies with basso continuo by the sound of their texture.¹⁵ Evidently, the *polyphonic* tradition of sustaining the number of parts throughout the entire music work gave way to the *homophonic* tradition of using as many voices and parts as necessary to reach the optimal “thickness” for each of the movements of a music work or sections within a movement.

The initial simplicity of homophonic texture during the shift of fashions from polyphonic Baroque to homophonic Classicism stood out by its clear-cut binary division of a texture into a solo melody in a foreground and an ensemble accompaniment that usually consisted of a melodic figuration or chords and a bass line (Levy 1982). Such an arrangement did not really preclude the use of basso continuo. However, the further development of big-scale cyclic music forms, especially in the genres of symphony and concerto, led to the hybridization of polyphonic-homophonic styles (Comberiati 1983). Subsequently, contrasts in character within a symphonic cycle required ongoing changes in the number of active parts and voices, increasing their density in those sections that projected dramatic development and decreasing wherever the music relaxed. Once such fluctuations became the commonplace in large-scale compositions, composers had to adopt a full control over the “shadow accompaniment” and write out all the details of the accompaniment in their scoring. This made basso continuo useless.

Nevertheless, the capacity of basso continuo to thicken the texture without nominally adding an extra part remained in the arsenal of expressive means available to a composer (Piston 1955, 355–414). Instruments, such as harp, violins, violas, and cello started routinely playing chords with varying number

¹⁵ This can be easily observed by comparing the sound recordings of Haydn's symphonies Nos.20-26 to his symphonies Nos.30-40, performed by the same orchestra and the same conductor (e.g., Antal Dorati and Adam Fischer recorded all Haydn's symphonies).

of tones in orchestral scores whenever a composer needed a greater thickness. Instruments capable of playing only one tone at a time were used in groups to play chords of various density (e.g., horns, trumpets, trombones, etc.).

Hence, the practice of thickening the texture by cramming more notes in the available tonal space, similar to artists tweaking the perspective, did not disappear along with the practice of basso continuo. Neither disappeared a trick of multiplication of horizons and vanishing points in the post-Baroque fine art. In fact, both traditions are very much alive today. Modern artists still study textbooks that describe the use of 2- and 3-point perspective (D'Amelio & Hohaus 2004). And modern musicians still use the system of figured notation of the succession of harmonies that accompany the unveiling of a tune in a form of chord symbols placed above the notated melody in so-called “fake sheet” (aka, “fake books”) editions of most popular tunes of classical and popular forms of music (Kernfeld 2006).

We talked about the similarity of multiple vanishing points in pictorial composition to basso continuo in music composition. But multiple horizon lines had its own analogy in contemporaneous theory of music composition. Application of multiple horizon lines concurred with and resembled the establishment of standardized schemes of tonal plan for the most important music forms of Baroque: fugue, sonata, and concerto. These schemes were based on 2-3 sequential harmonic compounds (the most common were the successions of 2 keys, tonic-dominant, or 3 keys, tonic-dominant-subdominant, within a tonal plan of a musical movement), where the tonic key remained prevalent, so that the alternative keys essentially tied the cadential plan to specific sections of a music form (Caplin 2001).

In a nutshell, the succession of closely related keys unified an entire music composition very much like the succession of principal harmonic functions unified two adjacent phrases or sentences by means of providing a salient cadence for the first of them. However, at the same time, the change of a key let the composer refresh the set of pitch classes and bring in more chords that were not present in the original key – to diversify a given scheme of tonal organization.

Greater assortment of pitch classes and chords affordable within a certain key enriched the music texture in a way quite similar to how a pictorial composition was enriched by addition of higher or lower horizon. Each additional horizon added importance to objects positioned in the respective sector of a composition. The affected pictorial objects received a “face-lift,” making them appear greater in size and therefore perceptually stand out. By the same token, multiple vanishing points worked as alternative “tonics” of keys that were reserved by the cadence plan.

Here we come to a very important conclusion. Vanishing points suggest vantage points. As the viewer receives more options for his viewing position, he is psychologically released from the function of impersonating the “lord” of the image, which implied certain alienation from the content of the image, as though viewing it from aside, separated by a window (Arnheim 1983, 194). Consequently, introduction of *alternative oblique angles removed the window effect*, enabling the viewer to experience “being right there” - *sharing space* with the depicted objects. By the same token, a spectator was relieved from a duty to stay in a fixed “correct” position of observation and received an opportunity to move from one point of observation to another. In the same vein, a listener of a piece of music became a participant in a journey designed by the composer to take him to a virtual world of music – a journey that required attention, expertise and creativity in capturing and interpreting important details in tonal arrangement of a music work (Hargreaves et al. 2011).

The Discovery of Shading in Compositional Organization

The first noticeable advance toward a greater sense of presence in experiencing an artwork in the field of classical music was the “sensitive style” (*Empfindsamer Stil*) that originated in the 17th century France, invented to compensate the rigidity of earlier Renaissance-born “doctrine of affections” (*Affektenlehre*).

Empfindsamer Stil was supposed to evoke “subjective” quick-passing feelings, intimate to the listener (Coward 1984), as opposed to a single emotional state postulated for the entirety of a work by *Affektenlehre* (Lasocki 1978). Such change in the management of musical emotions reflected greater illusionism in representation of real emotions.

Empfindsamer Stil engaged the listener in a mental “acting-out” of the situation where the listener was as though “there,” next to the stimulus responsible for triggering the emotion. Perceptually, this effect of personal presence brought in the experience of minute fluctuations in an emotional state – fluctuations indicated by the changes in details of textural arrangement, contrasts in the musical material between different sections of the music form, and the tonal plan of a music composition.

40. Audio: C.P.E. Bach – *Trio-sonata* C Minor, Wq. 161/1, H. 579 "Sanguineus und Melancholicus" (1748). An example of *Empfindsamer Stil*. According to the foreword by the composer, the 1st movement here presents the interaction between two persons of different temperament, where the Sanguineus is trying to snap the Melancholicus out of his melancholy. [[See Supplementary Audio File 40](#)]
41. Audio: John Mundy - *Fantasie* No.3 from the *Fitzwilliam Virginal Book* (c.1600-1630). An example of *Affektenlehre*. According to the remarks in the score, the music presents alternations of fair weather and storm (at 0:44), representing states of turbulence and calm. Comparing to the example above, here, each of the contrasting states is illustrated by less prominent melodic intonations, less patterned texture and less pronounced tonal progressions, resulting in a more diffused and general rendition of each of two musical emotions. [[See Supplementary Audio File 41](#)]

Structurally, sensitive style was characterized by its resemblance to the “recitative,” with its diversity of rhythm, melody, and harmony (Helm 1972). The latter was characterized by the extensive use of chromaticism which made an important part of the *Empfindsamkeit* package of expressive means, commonly associated with finesse in coloration in painting and held responsible for the projection of sensitivity and soul (Coward 1987).

Just as chromatic alterations were incorporated into the 18th century concept of a musical key to emphasize tonal hierarchy in sake of intensifying expression, shadowing eventually turned into a theory of spatial organization, at first alternative to perspective, and thereafter complementary to it.

Throughout the 17th century, much effort in French Academy of Arts went into building the unified theory of shading until the shadow-casting was mathematically modeled and incorporated into perspectival theory by Girard Desargues, eventually spreading throughout Europe (Kaufmann 1975). Earlier use of shadow in art was rather controversial, although recognized as a constituent of perspective organization already at Alberti’s times (Bauer 1987). De facto, shadowing was treated by Renaissance artists independently from a geometric perspective in their compositional design, often in contradiction to perspectival organization (Casati 2004).

The ramifications of their mismatch were detrimental to the experience of unity of spatial organization. Cognitive research confirms that the cast-shadow perspective is not any less important than classic linear perspective and, in practice, can perceptually overpower the linear perspectival organization (Dee 2011). The clash between the two and the power of shadow-light contrasts initially inspired Baroque artists to explore creative capacities of shadow perspective, sometimes justifying outright violations of the classic perspective rules.

Image 39. Caravaggio - *Conversion on the Way to Damascus* (1601). The disposition of the highlighted and shadowed areas overpowers the contribution of the geometric perspective to the spatial organization of Caravaggio's composition, creating a dramatic yet spatially distorted conflicting effect. Look separately at the figure of a horse and then at the figure of a lying man – the horse's head appears much further away in the depth parameter, making the horse look convoluted.

Something quite similar can be observed in the use of chromaticism by composers of the 17-18th centuries. Before the beginning of the 17th century, chromatic alterations for the most part were sporadic,

obscuring tonicity rather than emphasizing it (see Nikolsky 2016c).¹⁶ Towards the very end of the 16th century, chromaticism suddenly attracted attention of a number of composers who experimented with it in the genre of madrigal and explored the newly discovered chromatic means of expression in other genres, including ecclesiastic ones (e.g., Gesualdo, Marenzio, Luzzaschi). This trend received a name of “mannerism” - congruent with the period of mannerism in fine arts that preceded musical mannerism by some 50 years (Harran 1969).

Parallels can be drawn even further. The discovery of tenebrism by Caravaggio led to Baroque obsession with darkness that earned international acclaim to such artists as Rembrandt and Velasquez (Rzepińska 1986). Caravaggio’s discovery is remarkably similar to tenebrism of Carlo Gesualdo whose chromatic experiments had attracted attention of generations of composers, from Frescobaldi to Stravinsky (Holmes 1997). The overwhelming use of chromatic inflections in the melodic content of all parts and frequent clashes of harmonically distant chords make this type of music stand out as a special form of tonal organization, although it still conforms with the earlier technical requirements of polyphonic modal scoring (Sabaino & Mangani 2013).

42. Audio: Gesualdo – *Madrigal Beltà, poi che t'assenti* (1611). The chromatic shading here executes variety of expressive functions (from melodic embellishment or increase in harmonic tension to sudden re-coloration of chords), operating on a phrase-to-phrase basis, making the overall tonal palette rather motley yet consistent in its peculiar patchy style. Chromatic alterations tend to obstruct the sense of tonal unity between all parts within an entire composition. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 42\]](#)
43. Audio: Kindermann – *Ballet* (c.1645). The chromatic shading here is tonally patterned to fit into the standard progressions of implied chords that are diatonic to the key of E minor (using the triads of the I, II, III, IV, V, and VII degrees, as well as the 6th-chords, aka, the first inversion of a triad) with the only exception of a modulation to the Dominant key (the key of the V degree). As a result, chromatic alteration does not dissipate the overall tonal unity, but rather enriches the tonal hues by adding tints and shades to them. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 43\]](#)

Gradual tonalization of chromaticism throughout the 17th century led to a substantial increase in uniformity of distribution of chromatic alterations across the tonal material of a musical composition.

44. Audio: Gesualdo - *Omnes amici mei* (1611), responsorium for 6 parts. The graphic visualization by Stephen Malinowski illustrates the tonal relations between the components of a music texture by harmonic coloring, where the circle of 5^{ths} is treated as a color wheel, so that closely related (the intervallic distances of 4th and 5th) diatonic tones are assigned to closely related colors. As you can see, the distribution of colors is quite chaotic. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 44\]](#)
45. Audio: Purcell - *Chaconne ZT680* (1694) for harpsichord. Harmonic coloring here demonstrates a much greater tonal uniformity than in the Gesualdo example above. The colors tend to cluster together. [\[See Supplementary Audio File 45\]](#)

Evidently, during the course of the 17th century, composers discovered that chromaticism can be used systematically to express gloomy and conflicting affective states. Musicians learned how to manage chains of chromatic alterations, so that they fit into a tonal key without deforming its diatonic skeleton. Quite contrary to the earlier use of chromaticism, composers at the turn of the 17-18th centuries were able to employ chromaticism to emphasize the integrity of a tonal key. For example, the Fugue B Minor

¹⁶ The exceptions were quite rare: e.g., special cases of “tone-painting” where Western composers tried to represent a peculiar semantic content. One of the most famous examples was a rondeau “*Fumeux fume par fume*”, c.1390, by Solage, that depicted the pleasures of smoking.

from the Well-Tempered Klavier by J. S. Bach BWV 869 uses a theme that features all 12 tones in a span of only 3 bars. Nevertheless, the entire fugue remains within the realm of tonality, not even slightly reminding the sound of atonal dodecaphonic compositions by Schoenberg, famous for his emancipation of dissonance.

Somehow, the extreme use of chromaticism by Bach does not get on a way of the tonal integrity of a key. Notably, Schoenberg's use of dodecaphony denies the framework of tonality, treating all 12 pitch classes as perfectly equal in their tonal status. Subsequently, music of Schoenberg and his followers (so-called "serialism") is extremely difficult for perception even for well-trained musicians (Lerdahl 1992). Big part of lack of intelligibility of this kind of music is consistent disruption of rules of voicing (Huron 2001) in atonal music texture that makes its perception virtually impossible.

Along the same line, the 17th century painters discovered the expressive means of contrasting highlights with shadows and eventually learned to conform cast-shadow perspective to linear perspective.

Image 40. Le Seuer – *Phaeton asking Apollo* (1654). The perspectival organization here is done in accordance with the teaching of Abraham Bosse (Goldstein 1965), which was based on Girard Desargues' geometric theory (Kaufmann 1975).

As we see, both, tonal organization and perspectival projection, can be highly informative of the relations between parts/voices in musical texture as well as pictorial objects through gradations in crowdedness-emptiness, stability-instability, and highlight-shading.

Information Density of Composition in Music vs. Composition in Fine Arts

At this point we can draw conclusions from our overview of the historic development of pictorial and musical compositions.

The similarities between spatial organization of realistic works of visual arts and tonal organization of music are robust for the Renaissance and later periods of Western arts. All 3 main rules of perspective find close matches in rules of vertical and horizontal harmony in theory of Western music composition. In light of the available evidence on perception of music and visual arts, it looks like the emergence of linear perspective in Western fine arts and of tonality and functional harmony in Western music constitute two sides of the same coin – both relying on the same schemes of grouping constituent elements and components into a coherent whole. This congruence justifies the adoption of linear perspective and Western tonality as a “classic” model of cross-modal theory of composition that can be used as a reference for examination of synchronic and diachronic varieties of compositional practices in the world.

Post-Renaissance compositional methods demonstrate even closer match between specific aspects and devices of tonal organization of music texture, thematic material, harmony and tonal plan, on the one hand, and spatial organization of pictorial objects, rendition of a subject, and shading, on the other hand. Similarities also involve the pragmatics of compositional arrangement and the role that an author adopts in relation to an artwork and the consumer of it. If music theory catered to post-Renaissance composers’ aspiration to compete in compositional complexity for originality of compositional schemes, “classical” theory of perspective became “tweaked” and “individualized” to afford more complex and original organization of compositional components.

On the contrary, pre-Renaissance arts and music show less in common between their compositional principles – the more distant from the times of Renaissance, the weaker their relation. The same applies to geographic distance: territories closer to Western Europe seem to nurture traditions that share more common traits in compositional organization. The strongest case for the co-influence of pictorial and musical methods of arrangement presents the Greco-Roman tradition of Antiquity and the derivative traditions of the Middle East. The only principal link that they miss in comparison to the Renaissance model is the scaling of an empty space between material objects in pictorial compositions and the estimation of changes in tonal plan and of harmonic progressions in musical compositions.

The earlier cultures of the Bronze Age seem to have discovered a number of compositional devices that characterize Ancient Greek fine art and music. Similarities can be found between the application of the rule of centrality and the rule of scaling/ratio onto musical textures and modes, on the one hand, and representation of the depth parameter and distribution of figures of the foreground in pictorial art, on the other hand.

The prehistoric correspondences are very weak. To begin with, the very idea of drawing parallels between spatial organization of European rock art and tonal organization of music cultivated by modern hunter/gatherer societies that live in environments akin to those of prehistoric Europe, contemporaneous to its rock art, is rather tentative. It is only the prehistoric evolution of pictorial composition that can be studied with certainty in surviving artefacts. The prehistoric music composition will hardly ever be reconstructed. The only documented source that can provide a glimpse into tonal organization of prehistoric music is the tuning of wind (and possibly string) musical instruments uncovered by archaeologists (Nikolsky 2015c). The developing fields of research in experimental archaeology and archaeoacoustics might supply additional information. However, all in all, modern scholars are deprived of means to establish what kind of music structures prehistoric musicians cultivated. There is no guarantee that the schemes of tonal organization found in music of modern hunter/gatherer societies are the same as those used by prehistoric people even if their environmental conditions are perfectly matched.

Nevertheless, I believe that drawing such parallel will be fruitful and useful for building a comprehensive repertory of music textures and for inferring a plausible timeline of their evolution based on similarities between the compositional principles of verified prehistoric artworks and compositional principles of known forms of indigenous music reported by ethnomusicologists and indigenous music-users themselves. The data of paleoneurobiology, paleoaesthetics, paleophonology, geomusicology, biological motion, demography and statistic modeling might corroborate the hypothetical schemes of prehistoric tonal organization (Nikolsky & Perlovsky 2020).

The tentative compositional parallels in prehistoric cultures drawn in this paper are limited to very general similarities between the numerosity of constituent compositional objects, the extent of their contrast/similarity, the manner of their rendition, and patterns of grouping.

On the whole, it seems reasonable to conclude that the rise of Bronze Age civilizations was responsible for the significant boost in the emergence of similarities between the spatial and tonal organizations. The apex of this development was the Ancient Greek civilization, followed by the decline during the Dark Ages and the early Middle Ages. The Renaissance revived the achievements of the Greco-Roman artists and musicians, bringing them to new heights, when newly encoded theories of linear perspective in art and modal counterpoint in music clearly reflected similarities between the disposition of pictorial figures in a painting and laying out parts in a music texture. Further development during the Baroque period brought to life the alternative methods of perspectival organization along with their analogs in the practice of basso continuo, scoring music, orchestration rules and the theory of Western tonality.

In the very conclusion of this paper, we approach our last issue, disclosed by our exploration of history and prehistory of compositional arrangement of realistic visual arts and music.

The historic development of fine art has led to the emergence of a highly effective method of capturing immensely complex visual data and encoding it in an intelligible and coherent manner that can be rationally learned and objectively discussed. Just compare two disconnected depicted objects of Image 2 (*Spotted horses* from Grotte de Peche Merle) to hundreds of interconnected objects in Image 38 (Veronese – *The Wedding at Cana*) to appreciate the progress in the transmission of visual information.

The historic development of music has led to even more informatively dense method of encoding auditory data. Here we have to put aside the first Audio Examples that demonstrate isophony, since the latter did not engage tonal organization and compare the simplest case of tonal organization in Audio Example 7, with its 3 ekmelic pitches constituting mere 3 “sound objects”, to the complexity of Audio Example 34, with thousands of “sound objects” placed into hundreds of parts and voices.

The pronounced advantage of music over fine art in its capacity to convey information lies in its *temporal* domain. A picture has a dead limit of space that cannot encompass more discrete images than a certain minimal size – traditionally estimated as the 20-time reduction of a real object’s size (Kubovy 1988, 41). Exceeding the limit by squeezing in as many objects as the brush would technically allow, renders the entire picture poorly comprehensible.

A music work does not have such hard limits. Its temporal nature makes it a lot more flexible. A music work can last for a few hours and include millions of auditory events. There are genres of music that can run for a few days, performed by shifting of the musicians – e.g., *Andalusī nūbah* (Davis 2004). The number of musical objects that can be unveiled throughout such performance could run to a billion. And most of this information is normally absorbed by competent listeners.

Music is also informatively denser than verbal speech despite the latter being temporal as well. The advantage of music is that it simultaneously engages multiple voices and parts, the number of which in practice of Western music is routinely about 4-5 layers in texture. The most typical combination is:

- 1) the leading melody,
- 2) bass line,

- 3) melodic figuration of the accompaniment,
- 4) accompaniment in chords,
- 5) sustained pedal tones or chords.

And keep in mind that each of these parts can simultaneously carry at least 10 aspects of expression: melody, harmony, rhythm, meter, tempo, articulation, dynamics, timbre, texture and music form (thematicity) – each with its own proprietary structural patterns associated with specific semantic content by means of public conventions and/or biologically ingrained cross-modal correspondences between the properties of music structures and the properties of real-life objects and events.

It would be worth to note that this common setting of 5 parts constitutes a stereotypical band in Western popular music and in most forms of popular music in non-Western cultures of today. Their typical performance setting consists of:

- 1) the leading singer,
- 2) the bass guitar part,
- 3) the lead guitar solos and licks,
- 4) the accompaniment of a rhythmic guitar,
- 5) the electric keyboard playing pads.

In addition, often a group of singers is engaged to imitate the soloist, present a different thematic material, support the soloist with chords, or interact with the soloist in the manner of call and response. There could be extra guitars and keyboards, as well as wind instruments, possibly grouped into a combo or even a band. Such setting is quite common for many forms of popular music, which reflects the ease of perception of this quite sophisticated music texture even by musically untrained listeners. Moreover, the obvious tendency of societies that have preserved their indigenous traditions of modal and timbral music to import Western popular music and/or assimilate it in their native cultures, instituting new styles and genres of Western-like music, should be regarded as the vital proof of more effective neural encoding of tonal organization by means of tonality as opposed to the pre-tonal methods of tonal organization.

The entire course of evolution of music can be seen as an ongoing process of natural selection of the most effective means of conveying information through music, where the more effective schemes of tonal organization supplant the less effective ones. Any piece of information can be encoded in variety of ways. One way can be more efficient than another, if it requires less resources to proceed, supports higher transmission rate and/or allows for less errors. The same melodic idea solo can be encoded in numerous formats:

- as a succession of horizontal intervals,
- as a succession of broken vertical intervals,
- as the combination of both,
- as a peculiar progression of fixed pitch classes,
- as a succession of degrees in a given diatonic scale,
- as a progression of 12 well-tempered tones, or
- as a spectral map of some sonances unresolved in frequency.

The above-listed methods can be combined, where certain structural elements identified by ear are processed in one way, and others - in some other way.

The presence of multiple options for encoding the same information by musical means is no different than the possibility to encode the same text in unicode-8 or unicode-16, for example. One format can offer advantages over another format for a certain type of information and a certain context of transmission. For a person who is composing music, tonality significantly facilitates the process of

composition as compared to other alternative methods (such as pentatonic, hexatonic or equitonic heptatonic, etc.). The ease of implicit learning must be the underlying reason for a commonly observed situation of today, when non-Western musicians either abandon their indigenous traditions in favor of Western tonality or hybridize their native systems with Western tonality (Nettl 1986). The efficacy of tonality in error-correction during the transmission of information provides yet another reason for the apparent ongoing Westernization of indigenous music cultures all over the world.

There is nothing similar to the textural multi-factorial organization of music in the way in which humans use speech for communication. Simultaneous talking of five different persons would make it impossible to understand what they are talking about, because communication of information through speech completely relies on phonological contrasts that become blurred even when two people try to pronounce exactly the same sentence in sync. The other aspects of vocal expression that verbal prosody shares with music: rhythm, pitch, tempo, dynamics, registration and articulation – are not capable of securing effective communication at the absence of clear delivery of phonological contrasts. In striking contrast, simultaneous performance by 5 musicians is readily understood by millions of listeners across cultural boundaries – as evident from the global spread of Western popular music.

Each of 10 aspects of music expression possess their own idioms of expression. Five of them are used very heavily in most forms of indigenous music traditions:

1. Pitch idioms (such as exciting “leaps” versus smooth “steps”) are mediated by the pitch syntax (such as pitch contour, directionality of melodic motion and intervallic proximity of musical tones);
2. Rhythm idioms (such as an bouncy “dotted rhythm” versus flowing “straight rhythm”) are mediated by the rhythm syntax (such as the rules of grouping the duration values);
3. Metric idioms (such as “marching” binary versus “swaying” ternary meters) are mediated by the metric syntax (such as syncopation, offbeat, anacrusis);
4. Harmonic idioms (such as a happy “major triad” versus sad “minor triad”) are mediated by the harmonic syntax (such as Tonic or Dominant);
5. Texture idioms (such as expressive “melodic line” versus rudimentary “chords”) are mediated by the textural syntax (such as polyphony, homophony, or heterophony).

Other expressive aspects also feature idioms, but lack in syntactic rules proprietary to that aspect – instead, relying on the syntax of the five primary aspects above:

6. Dynamic idioms (such as powerful “forte” versus tender “piano”) are not connected to one another by dynamic means – instead, they depend on harmonic, metric, pitch, and to a lesser extent, rhythm syntax;
7. Tempo idioms (such as tense “ritenuto” versus relaxed “rallentando”) do not follow any tempo-based logic – their appropriateness is decided by pitch, rhythm, and harmony;
8. Articulation idioms (such as nervous or cute “staccato” versus pleasant relaxed “legato”) are not limited by any articulation restrictions, they can be easily combined or alternated – determined by all five primary aspects of expression, plus tempo;
9. Timbral idioms (such as sensual “vibrato” versus stiff and restrained “con sordino”) highlight the changes in pitch, rhythm, harmony, and to a lesser extent, tempo and articulation;
10. Idioms of music form (such as intriguing “introduction,” stable and profound “exposition,” or unstable and uncertain “development”) are integrated from all above-mentioned 9 aspects.

Although the final verdict should come from experimental studies, using some reliable method of cross-modal quantification, it surely looks that under normal conditions a minute of Western orchestral tonal music can transmit substantially more information than a minute of verbal speech.

This evolutionary overview suggests that tonal organization in music and spatial organization in pictures had their head start around the same time and initially shared about the same capacity to compress information. But throughout the cultural evolution and by power of modern globalization, tonal organization has acquired a lead in capacity to effectively transmit high volumes of information amongst large number of people. This advantage must be one of the main reasons for the wide spread and the great importance laid on music in the modern day culture (Rideout, Roberts, and Foehr 2010). The medium of music might be better suited to reflect on the disposition of objects, their interconnections and functions in real world, so that the growth in socio-cultural complexity and technologies, especially prominent in industrial societies, can find closer match in schemes of compositional arrangement of music in comparison to composition of fine art and speech.

Centrality of pitch contour to music makes music exceptional in its capacity to simultaneously transfer large number of signals with relative ease (McDermott et al. 2010). Perceptual ease of processing sensory data transpires into semi-automatic manner of operation (Bidelman & Grall 2014). The auditory system is known to have an edge in urgent and information-intensive communication over other senses (Jerison 1973). Hearing is the only distant sense that has an urgent effect during sleep (Wilson 2000, 235). Auditory input is the most direct in delivering information about the environment. Unlike vision, hearing makes environmental information readily available for the brain right from birth. Neonates are found to have all the main auditory functionality that characterizes adults' hearing in place (Bendixen et al. 2015). Human fetus can discriminate between different frequencies at the age of 27-35 weeks (Litovsky 2015).

All of these lead one to believe that perception of pitch contour provides processing advantages over perception of visual contour. Music seems to be the only medium that allows a person to overcome a perceptual limit of chunking information. George Miller established a chunking threshold at “seven plus or minus two” units of information (Miller 1994). The subsequent research updated Miller's model to the “maximally compressed code” of chunking, according to which “four plus or minus one” chunks sets the processing limit equivalent to “uncompressed” Miller's “seven plus/minus two” rule (Mathy & Feldman 2012). However, music routinely surpasses this limit for those who possess “perfect hearing”. Hearing “absolute pitch” requires instant recognition of at least 12 pitch classes – this is by the most modest estimation - in reality, Western tonality, uses 17 pitch-classes, since enharmonic “C sharp” and “D flat”, “D sharp” and “E flat”, “F sharp” and “G flat”, “G sharp” and “A flat”, and “B flat” and “A sharp” constitute different pitch classes, distinguished by pronounced intervallic differences in tuning (Nikolsky 2020b). If one takes into consideration that “absolute pitch” is perfectly trainable and potentially achievable for anyone who follows the correct ear-training method (I myself can attest to this statement on my own experience as a student of music and as an ear-training professional later in life), then the advantages of music in supporting higher loads of information in cultural transmission become obvious.

These psychological arguments find confirmation from sociological studies. Music behaviors are much more common than drawing behaviors. The difference is especially pronounced at earlier stages of evolution of music. So far, every known indigenous culture possesses some form of music tradition that follows some kind of orally transmitted “music theory” (Blacking 1995, 224), whereas the number of cultures that lack a folk tradition of depiction of real life is rather vast. Furthermore, music occupies an important part of daily activities in pre-industrial societies (Turino 2008). Although it is hard to establish the exact figures, there are field studies that report 2-3 hours daily of collective use of music – and this is in subsistent societies, living under constant environmental pressure that requires much time and effort from every member of a tribe (Huron 2003, 64).

Participation in music activities is usually all-inclusive in indigenous societies (Schyff 2013). The same applies to the earliest ancient civilizations. Growth of professionalism started carrying a negative impact on the participation rates of general population in music production only after AD, and only in the West (Ancient Rome). Still, the spread of early Christian culture reversed this trend for quite a few centuries by making singing of anthems and hymns obligatory for healthy members of a congregation, disregarding their musical capacities. Despite the spike in professionalization of music occupations (including composition) in many Western European countries, noticeable from the 12-13th centuries (Cowen 2009), the growth of music literacy (Dahl 2008) and the levels of public engagement in music-making remained quite high until the 20th century (Ellis 2001). Even in modern times, after the dramatic drop in active production of music due to the explosion of passive consumption of music under the influence of music industry, overall, music-making remains more popular than drawing or painting.

Drawing and painting have never achieved levels of public participation comparable to music – neither in historic retrospective, nor in modern world. Even at its earliest evolutionary stages, rock art demonstrated high levels of technical mastery, indicative of exclusiveness of the painting occupation. The sophistication of pictorial technique in the oldest Paleolithic paintings suggests that much time and labor were invested into artistic training: art historians regard many discovered images as “pupil’s drawings” and “rough drafts” for “master-works” (Hauser 1999, 9). Long apprenticeship would be hard to accomplish without receiving privileges relieving a would-be-artist from the chores of food-seeking. Achieving a mastery level must have been regarded back then as the benefit for the entire tribe. This was hardly possible without the stable cross-cultural association of cave art with magic. The domain of professionalism (or partial professionalism, in case if an artist still had to share some hunting or gathering duties with the rest of the tribe) was likely to be limited to the *figurative* art only – i.e., a representation of visible reality that was recognizable to majority of the tribesmen upon a mere glance. The applied arts, such as tool- or dress-making, as evident from existing hunter/gatherer societies, are usually relegated to a secondary role (Hauser 1999, 10).

Great precaution characterizes the use of figurative art in numerous hunter/gatherer societies of Siberia, Northern America and South Asia: drawings that depict ritual images on tambourines are washed out upon completion of a rite, drawings on snow that accompany Eskimo story-telling are destroyed at the end of the story, faces drawn on masks are burned after their use (V.V.Ivanov 2014, 4:357). Such measures are clearly counter-productive for the development of any stable tradition of public drawing. Arrangement of pictures within caves leads one to believe that the prehistoric art most likely was closely related to shamanic rites, viewed as exercising supernatural power over the entire tribe, and therefore justifying a special social status awarded to the artist (Curtis 2006, 235). Customs observed in modern Aboriginal societies confirm the *exclusive* nature of pictorial image production: drawing is seen as presentation of subjects, which in turn, is associated with dreaming – i.e., entering a world of spirits and requiring restricted access that only the ordained adult male members of the tribe could potentially receive (Myers 2002, 63).

Similar selectivity has been promoted by societies of Antiquity, where depiction remained a prerogative of a narrow professional group, serving the cast of priests, and later – the royalty, although bearing a relatively low social status due to the physical labor involved in production of art (Hauser 1999, 15). Painting was not distinguished from other artisan occupations, and arts were viewed like crafts, disregarding the merits of artistic expression. Arts were appreciated mainly for usefulness, which was secured through the practice of supervising the manufacturing process by professional administrators (R. P. Wright 2008). Palace and court remained the principal sites for employment of artists up until the 1st millennium, when the Assyrian culture flourished and became internationally renowned for its artistry, thereby generating the demand for art outside temples and palaces (Gunter 1990).

Ancient Greeks further democratized art and made the aesthetic appreciation customary, however graphic depiction of real life in Hellenic art was limited to vase painting and remained the business of relatively few craftsmen – nothing close to the popularity of participation in choir singing (Bowie 2011),

enrolling in music competitions (Mark 1995), and performing lyric poetry at symposions - where public display of musical skills was seen as a sign of cultural accomplishment (Hobden 2013, 41–45). Even the most celebrated Spartan generals improvised music on pipe and lyre (Quintilianus 1974, 67) – yet did not paint vases. The chief reason for the low social status of painting was the association of manual labor with slaves, which characterized all societies of Antiquity (Hauser 1999, 15). Even the boom of architectural painting in Augustan Rome (*ibid.*, p.51) did not obliterate this prejudice despite the distinguished personages, like emperors Nero and Hadrian, committing to amateur painting (p.56).

Christian culture initially showed signs of greater accessibility of painting during the brief Catacomb period, when wall frescoes in underground warship locations were distinguished by an informal artisan and amateurish style (p.59). However, this period was quickly put to an end by canonization of rules of iconography, which required prolonged training and thorough selection of candidates for apprenticeship. Future iconographers were to be picked by religious authorities and trained to recognize spiritual values of that which ought to be perpetuated in the picture (Florensky 1996).

The Renaissance did not really turn visual arts into a household occupation (unlike music) despite its general tendency for secularization and popularization of arts. The first time when figurative drawing/painting broke away from the ivory tower of treasury of specially gifted artists to become accessible to a lay person was the 17th century, when amateur painting started earning the reputation of decent pastimes for women, turning into the cultural “female preserve” (Pears 1991, 186). Nevertheless, it took another century before the ability to draw earned the reputation of a norm for a lady in upper-class English, French and Dutch societies and proved to be effective in securing social bonding amongst the local gentry (Heer 1997).

By the end of the 18th century, the salon culture produced an offshoot of private art education – at first for the children of “good” families, and then for children in general – as an organic part of the Enlightenment policy of propagating moral values through art. The political competition between England and France encouraged each of these countries to establish public organizations (e.g., Society for the Encouragement of Arts, Manufactures and Commerce in England) called to develop the “public taste” for morality and “right thinking” (Pearson 1982, 14–30). Amateur painting was part of the agenda of such societies and clubs that spread all over European states during the 19th century. Nationalism, promoted by Romantic artists, merged with family art education, fertilized by the growing involvement of female amateurs in home decoration (Swinth 2001, 78). Only by the end of the 19th century did drawing/painting from real life become the public affair in middle- as well as upper-class families. And only by the 20th century, the emergence of welfare system in Europe and America opened doors to art education for lower classes. States started financing the amateur and semi-professional groups and individuals (Alexander & Rueschemeyer 2005, 120).

As this brief overview of the history of figurative art shows, wide demographic participation in artistic activities is really a very recent phenomenon – probably, related to the growing trend of commercialization of fine art, combined with the rise of the recreational culture that comfortably absorbs painting as an outdoor hobby (Grant 2011).

Music enjoyed substantially greater participation rates in “primitive” and ancient societies and retained this edge over pictorial arts throughout the history of Western civilization. Unlike art education, music education was regarded crucial for practicing Christianity ever since St. Augustine reconciled the Ancient admiration for music with Christian theological concepts in the 4th century AD (Katz & Dahlhaus 1987, 2:7–33). Music education was accessible to wide strata of society already during Middle Ages and Renaissance (Weiss, Murray, and Cyrus 2010) – not to mention the participation of musically uneducated congregation in singing anthems and psalms (Knighton & Fallows 1997). Lutheran culture promoted even greater spread of musical literacy across wide demographics (Mark 2013).

It seems that the overall advantage in popularity of music-making over drawing/painting has to do with the biological limitations of human brain, namely, the cognitive constraints of converting the visible 3D

objects into the pictorial images on the 2D plane. The task of reproducing a melodic contour apparently is less perceptually demanding than the task of reproduction of a visual contour. This could explain why music is distributed across human societies much wider than figurative fine art and why music achieves such high levels of informational density as humanity advances to higher levels of technological complexity through cultural evolution. It could be that music specializes in forging schemes of compositional arrangement in the medium that is most “user-friendly” and, once such schemes are put in place, supports their everyday use through music listening and production, while facilitating the perception of spatial organization in visual domain. In a word, music might supply the methodology for chunking the sensory information wherever the sensory input exceeds the capacity of the brain to detect and interpret the data stream “on-the-fly”.

Note: The audio demonstrations originally linked in this paper (hosted on chirb.it, bit.ly, and goo.gl) are no longer available at their original URLs. They have been collected into supplementary audio files deposited alongside this paper on Zenodo. Each “[See Supplementary Audio File N]” reference in the text corresponds to the respective numbered file in the Zenodo deposit.

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